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AdvanCing behavioural
Change Through
an INclusive Green deal

D3.4 Overall report on the results of the eight thematic research lines: Intersectional and qualitative comparative analyses

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List of Acronyms

EGD	European green deal
RL	Research line
QCA	Qualitative comparative analysis

The ACCTING project

It is acknowledged by now that the global climate crisis is not only an ecological crisis but also an economic, social and political crisis, with devastating effects on individuals and societies. These negative effects are not evenly distributed within societies. It is the poorer, marginalised and vulnerable groups who are the most acutely affected, exacerbating existing socio-economic inequalities. The European Green Deal foresees efficient use of resources for a circular and clean economy. However, inequalities emerge in the context of its policy and interventions.

The EU-funded ACCTING project takes these considerations as a starting point for a complex series of research and experimental activities aimed at identifying, analysing and testing policies and initiatives capable of responding to this crisis, mitigating its effects on the most vulnerable and helping them play a significant role in the pursuit of greater environmental sustainability.

The project mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies and supporting behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

ACCTING explores the impact of Green Deal policy initiatives on individual and collective behaviours, provides evidence, and empowers policymakers and stakeholders to anticipate policy responses and potential negative influences, and mitigate such impacts in decision-making. The project collects new data on Green Deal policy interventions and co-designs and implements pilot actions to reduce or prevent policy-related inequalities and advance behavioural change for an inclusive and equal European Green Deal.

Project Consortium

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	Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)
	ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability, European Secretariat
	Sabancı University (SU)
	Instituto de Geografia e Ordenamento de Território (IGOT)
	South East European Research Center (SEERC)
	Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi (UAIC)
	European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)
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Summary

Climate change progresses rapidly and the need to mitigate and adapt is becoming ever more urgent. The consequences of climate change and the measures to mitigate and adapt to it are, however, unequally distributed: it is the poorer, marginalised and vulnerable groups of people who are the most acutely affected (IPCC 2022, 2023; Hulme et al. 2020). The ACCTING project set out in February 2022 to investigate how policy programmes like the European Green Deal (EGD), which aim to transform societies towards environmental sustainability and climate neutrality, affect individuals and communities who, from a gender+ intersectional perspective, can be considered marginalised or vulnerable. Moreover, the project examined what enables or hinders these groups from partaking in and actively contributing to shaping the green transformation.

ACCTING's **first cycle of research** described, analysed, and reflected on the relation between multidimensional vulnerability factors, inequalities, and behavioural change in the context of an inclusive Green Deal (Zorell & Strid 2023). A theoretical and methodological framework which integrates perspectives of intersectionality and behaviour change as being highly complex built the foundation of the design and analysis. The main conclusions were that for socially vulnerable and marginalised individuals, behavioural change, as envisioned by the Green Deal, is difficult and complex to achieve. While individuals and organisations want to change, economic hardship, material deprivation, social exclusion or marginalisation, and geographic constraints, combined with inequalities such as gender, age, ethnic origin, and/or disabilities, act as major barriers. Inadequate public infrastructures and policies further obstruct changes. However, factors such as having time, knowledge, education, self-efficacy, and access to tools and social networks can substantially enable sustainable lifestyle changes. Social communities and relationships showed to play a particularly crucial role in providing awareness and support.

The **second research cycle** further refined these results via multiple methodologies and experimental activities. The eight research lines, each addressing a Green Deal policy area, implemented 87 quasi-experimental case studies in thirteen countries. The multifaceted insights show that sustainability transitions are most effective when local and community-driven approaches are accompanied by inclusive policies and robust, supportive infrastructure. A central, common finding across research lines is that grassroots initiatives drive change. The experimental case studies further confirm the first cycle results, underscoring the central roles of social networks and collective influence in advancing both individual and collective behavioural changes. Nonetheless, while there is the opportunity to advance social justice and environmental transition hand in hand, few policies are in place that address this dual challenge systematically. Moreover, many grassroots initiatives struggle with economic, regulatory, and structural barriers that limit their scalability and impact. By not addressing these challenges, nor the systemic inequalities and challenges faced by marginalised communities, which often intersect in different ways, societies risk that sustainability policies and transitions will reinforce rather than decrease existing disparities. A just transition requires policies which encourage individual behavioural change and, at the same time, transform economic and political structures to ensure equitable participation. By integrating

community expertise, fostering collaboration across sectors and social groups, and prioritising social justice, societies can move toward a Green Deal that is both environmentally sustainable and socially inclusive.

The design of ACCTING rests on a complex vision of behavioural change, which relies on a multitude of interconnected factors and cannot be framed in a linear, deterministic model. The crucial consideration of intersectional inequalities adds layers of complexity to the analysis. This deliverable presents the results of two analyses that address this complexity, establishing conclusions based on an overall and in-depth analysis of the complex relation between multidimensional vulnerability factors, inequalities, and behavioural change. An intersectional analysis presented in Part I brings together quantitative data generated in the *two research cycles*. The empirical material provides evidence on the factors that tend to enable or hinder behavioural change among individuals and collectives with specific multidimensional vulnerability backgrounds across various spheres of life (analogous to the Green Deal policy areas and research lines). This is followed by Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) in Part II, which is used to examine the *second cycle cases* as complex, dynamic systems and link their outcomes to configurations of factors that explain their variance. In other words, it defines different ‘causal recipes’ (Ragin 2008) that can explain when individual and collective actors move towards inclusive behavioural change. The combination of the two sections provides a rich set of knowledge that can inform the development and implementation of appropriate and successful measures and actions for both policy-makers and civil society actors.

The deliverable is structured into an introduction and three parts: The Introduction briefly recaps the background of the project as well as the approach and aims of the deliverable. Part I presents the results from the quantitative intersectional analysis, which delves into the question of which factors come consistently through as enabling or hindering individual behavioural change depending on varying constellations of gender+ intersectional vulnerabilities. The subsequent Part II is devoted to QCA. Using the second cycle’s case studies, the QCA investigates which configurations of factors seem to be able to causally explain why some cases successfully produce behavioural change, while others do not. Each of the parts concludes with a summary of key findings. The deliverable ends in Part III with a discussion of the central, overarching conclusions of the project, as well as policy recommendations and gaps for future research based on the evidence gathered.

Introduction to the deliverable

Climate change and environmental degradation pose profound and accelerating challenges to societies worldwide. The ecological crises and measures to mitigate their progress and impacts already exacerbate and are predicted to further aggravate existing gendered and intersectional socio-economic inequalities (Guedes et al. 2024). Transformative change is needed (IPCC 2023), which ranges from changes in the behaviours of individuals, communities, and organisations to full-scale changes in societal economic practices (Boström et al. 2018; Davis & Lee 2019; Linnér & Wibeck 2019).

The European Green Deal (EGD) represents a comprehensive policy response, aiming to steer Europe toward this transformation, including climate neutrality, biodiversity restoration, and environmental sustainability, while striving to ensure social justice and economic cohesion. Yet, the success of this transformation hinges not only on technological innovation and regulatory measures, but also on the capacity and willingness of individuals and communities to change behaviours and practices in everyday life.

Behavioural change has traditionally been discussed as an individual responsibility, that is, as an issue of attitudes, awareness, and incentives (Roy et al. 2021). However, such a narrow framing overlooks the structural and systemic conditions that shape what people can realistically do. A wide range of factors at individual, group, and country levels shape and influence intentions to engage in change and the opportunities and possibilities of translating those intentions into robust and sustainable practices. Besides to individual preferences and life circumstances, also broader economic and political developments, geographic and geophysical conditions, as well as community dynamics, political and economic rhetoric, social norms, and established social practices can all affect if and how individuals and societies are engaging for transformative change (Boström 2020, 2023; Zorell 2020; Zorell et al. 2024).

In addition, inequalities such as gender, age, socioeconomic status, ethnicity, urban/rural livelihood, and their intersections, affect not only the capacity and ability for behavioural change in various, different ways, but also the perceptions of problems and policies. The latter is crucial, however, to make transformation the inclusive and successful societal endeavour that it needs to be to successfully avert the worst environmental scenarios (IPCC 2023). On this backdrop, the ACCTING project takes a broad and inclusive approach. It explores the enabling and constraining factors behind behavioural change from an intersectional perspective, focusing on people and groups who are affected by multiple, overlapping forms of vulnerability, based on gender, age, ethnicity, (dis)ability, socio-economic status, and geographic location, among others (Zorell et al. 2022).

This deliverable presents an in-depth empirical analysis of how different vulnerability backgrounds intersect with the potential for behavioural change. It draws on data generated through two research cycles conducted across eight thematic research lines corresponding to core areas of the Green Deal. The first cycle provided a foundational mapping of how social inequalities and structural barriers affect the capacity for sustainable behaviours at the individual level. The second cycle deepened this understanding through experimental and participatory approaches. Engaging directly with individuals, communities, and grassroots initiatives in 87 case studies across 13 countries, it examined how large-scale societal change can be facilitated and accelerated.

The analysis presented in this deliverable is built around two complementary parts. **Part I** provides a cross-cutting **intersectional analysis** of quantitative data gathered in both research cycles. The section identifies which factors are most frequently and consistently perceived as enabling or hindering behavioural change by individuals with different multidimensional vulnerability profiles and inequality backgrounds. The analysis captures trends across diverse life domains, from mobility and energy use to food, disaster management, and civic participation. The insights provide a robust evidence base for targeted, inclusive policy action that can enable change at the individual level.

Part II then turns to a **Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA)** of selected case studies from the second research cycle. QCA treats cases as complex systems shaped by multiple interacting conditions, and it identifies combinations of factors – or “causal recipes” – that lead to successful behavioural change. This approach allows us to understand not just whether change at the collective level occurs, but how and under what circumstances. The insights gained from the QCA are especially valuable in the context of complex social dynamics that shape behavioural change.

Together, the analyses illuminate the multilayered relationship between structural inequality and behavioural changes towards environmentally sustainable behaviours. A final section at the end of each part wraps up **central conclusions**, eventually recapped in an overarching discussion of **implications for policy and practice in Part III**. A common denominator is the clear conclusion that inclusive climate- and environmental action requires more than awareness-raising or individual incentives. It requires much stronger and more proactive policy and action by institutional and collective actors, as putting the responsibility mostly on individuals who have limited power will not advance the implementation of large-scale structural transformations that are really needed. At the same time, it also demands an understanding of the social realities people face, and of the material, institutional, and relational contexts that enable or obstruct sustainable practices.

By integrating quantitative and qualitative perspectives, this report contributes to a growing body of knowledge on how to foster socially inclusive environmental transitions. It offers a solid empirical foundation for policymakers, practitioners, and civil society actors working toward a Green Deal that is both environmentally ambitious and socially just.

PART I: Intersectional analysis

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1 Introduction

The European Green Deal sets out an ambitious vision for a climate-neutral and socially inclusive future. Achieving this vision, however, demands not only technological progress. It also requires deep, far-reaching shifts in everyday behaviours and lifestyles. The ACCTING project investigates how structural inequalities shape the capacity and willingness of individuals and communities to adopt sustainable behaviours. Its aim is to generate knowledge and innovation that supports inclusive, effective, and just behavioural change.

The approach grounds on a theoretical framework of social, economic and environmental vulnerability and its inherently multidimensional character (Poortinga & Darnton 2016). This is complemented by the understanding of vulnerable social groups and communities not only as exposed to risks and negative impacts. Rather, they are understood as capable and oftentimes key actors for managing and enacting change, particularly when they form groups and networks to collectively address the issues they face (Schor & Thompson 2014).

Different grounds of social vulnerability and disadvantage overlap differently with exposure to risks associated with climate change and its mitigation measures. The ACCTING research takes an intersectional gender+ approach to explore those overlaps, and it examines how vulnerability and inequality affect access to and opportunities for engagement in climate action and environmentally sustainable behaviours. Moreover, by combining knowledges in inter- and transdisciplinary ways (Knorr-Cetina 1999) and using trans-epistemic practices (Everett & Jamal 2004), the ACCTING research taps into the wide complexity of behavioural, social, and cultural change (see also Zorell et al. 2025). This respective complexity exposes limitations to the 'one-size-fits-all' models of behaviour change, underscoring that individual choices are influenced not only by attitudes and motivations (such as environmental concern or cost considerations) but also shaped by structural enablers and constraints. The nature and extent of such enablers and constraints, however, vary markedly across and within groups facing different vulnerabilities and inequalities, calling for climate mitigation and adaptation strategies which are responsive to such diversity.

By placing diversity and inclusion at the heart of climate policy, behavioural change can serve not only environmental objectives but also broader goals of social justice. ACCTING contributes to this agenda by offering empirical insights and policy guidance for a Green Deal that leaves no one behind.

This section of the report focuses on *how different vulnerability grounds and inequalities influence individuals' engagement with sustainable behaviours*. Drawing on quantitative data from two research cycles, it identifies *which factors tend to be perceived as enabling or hindering behavioural change among individuals and groups with varying multidimensional vulnerability profiles and inequality backgrounds*. By capturing these patterns across key spheres of life (e.g., energy, food, mobility), the analysis provides an evidence base for developing targeted, inclusive strategies that support fair and equitable transitions towards sustainability.

2 Methodology

In the first research cycle, the ACCTING team conducted narrative interviews. The second research cycle revolved around experimental studies, which were implemented as case studies and included interviews and questionnaires. Both research cycles covered a standardised set of questions, gathered as quantitative data in Excel spreadsheets (Zorell & Strid 2023; Zorell et al. 2025). These two datasets capture factors mentioned among 749 respondents throughout 13 countries as enablers and hindrances of environmentally sustainable behaviours and change thereto. The kinds of behaviours relate to different spheres aligned with the key European Green Deal policy areas: climate change, biodiversity, energy, food, and transport. Respondents' experiences (i.e., enablers and hindrances) were categorised into three domains: resources, social dynamics, and structural conditions, with responses mapped across 16 factors. Participants could identify them as enablers, as hindrances, or as both simultaneously.

National interviewers conducted the interviews and recorded respondents' subjective experiences of vulnerability. This allowed for disaggregated analysis across different identity dimensions. The six vulnerability grounds examined were: gender, age, disability, national minority status, religion and belief, ethnicity, and sexual orientation. Subjective experiences of vulnerability relate to how individuals perceive and describe their own exposure to disadvantage or marginalisation in relation to identity-based grounds. Rather than assuming vulnerability based solely on group membership (e.g., being a woman, an ethnic minority, or a person with a disability), this approach allowed respondents to express whether and how these aspects of their identity actually shaped their experiences in everyday life and in the context of sustainable behaviours.

For example, while gender is often treated as a generalised axis of vulnerability, not all women identified gender as a source of disadvantage, and some men reported gender-related vulnerability depending on the context. Likewise, a person belonging to an ethnic minority group may or may not experience this as a limiting factor in relation to Green Deal-related actions, depending on local social dynamics, institutional discrimination, or other factors. This self-assessed vulnerability lens enables a more nuanced and respectful understanding of lived experiences, avoiding reductive or stereotypical assumptions.

The subjective vulnerabilities were complemented by data on socio-demographic and economic backgrounds, which commonly define inequalities that can shape the roles and positions of an individual, sometimes in unconscious ways (Kaijser & Kronsell 2014; Schlosberg 2013). Eight aspects were covered: gender, age, national background, migration background, education, income, employment status, and disability/health issues.

Interview data from both research cycles were compiled into two master Excel datasets and subsequently analysed using R. The analysis first assessed the relative importance of each of the 16 factors (grouped under resources, structural conditions, and social dynamics) based on the frequency with which they were mentioned as enablers and hindrances across all respondents. Furthermore, we disaggregated the analysis by vulnerability grounds. That is, we conducted a comparative analysis between respondents who reported experiencing a form of vulnerability and/or were recruited on that basis, and those who did not. For each of the six grounds of vulnerability (gender, age, disability, national minority status, religion and belief, ethnicity, and sexual orientation), we examined the distribution of enabling and

hindering factors, highlighting where experiences diverged. This allowed us to identify which aspects were most commonly cited as facilitating or constraining (change to) sustainable behaviours, both in general and across groups with distinct vulnerability experiences within the context of European Green Deal policy areas.

In a second step, we analysed and compared the relevance of the different enablers and hindrances across respondents based on their socio-demographic and economic profiles. This approach added another layer of understanding by disaggregating the role of distinct enablers and hindrances depending on individual profile characteristics that commonly define social inequality: gender, age (recoded as below/above average (48 years)), national background, migration background (recoded into a binary, i.e., migrant or non-migrant), education (recoded into professional training degree or university degree versus everyone else), income (recoded into coping or living comfortably versus everyone else), employment status (recoded into paid work versus everyone else), and disability/health issues. It is worth noting that this part of the analysis draws exclusively on data collected during the second research cycle.

By combining aggregate proportions with disaggregated comparisons, the analysis offers a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of how opportunities and barriers for behavioural change are patterned – both by subjective experiences of vulnerabilities and by more ‘objective’ inequalities. The results also give insights into where certain enablers are consistently lacking or where certain hindrances disproportionately affect specific groups, which can inform targeted recommendations for inclusive policy interventions.

3 Analysis and discussion

3.1 Enablers and hindrances across grounds of vulnerability

Data from the ACCTING project show that respondents report enablers (94%) and hindrances (93%) at nearly equal rates, suggesting that individuals are both aware of opportunities and acutely conscious of constraints to sustainable lifestyle change. However, a breakdown by category (resources, social dynamics, and structural conditions) reveals more nuanced patterns, as visualised in Figure 1, and broken down in Table 1 below.

Figure 1. Relative proportion of mentions of enablers and hindrances, by category ($n = 749$).

Note: The size of bubbles and legends are proportional to the relative number of mentions, i.e. to the parent node. Labels and proportions are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Number and relative/absolute proportion of mentions of enablers and hindrances, by category.

Type	Category	Motivations	No. of mentions	Relative proportion	Absolute proportion
Enablers			704	94.0%	94.0%
	Resources		624	88.6%	83.3%
		Knowledge	459	73.6%	61.3%
		Self-efficacy	302	48.4%	40.3%
		Education	250	40.1%	33.4%
		Time	188	30.1%	25.1%
		Political and social actors	183	29.3%	24.4%
		Equipment	174	27.9%	23.2%
		Money	142	22.8%	19.0%
	Social dynamics		610	86.6%	81.4%
		Community and social networks	436	71.5%	58.2%
		Significant relationships	343	56.2%	45.8%
		Beliefs and values	322	52.8%	43.0%
		Social appreciation	181	29.7%	24.2%
	Structural conditions		401	57.0%	53.5%
		Physical & geographical environment	205	51.1%	27.4%
		Policies and politics	144	35.9%	19.2%
		Infrastructure	125	31.2%	16.7%
		Socio-economic conditions	118	29.4%	15.8%
		Events and developments	80	20.0%	10.7%
Hindrances			696	92.9%	92.9%
	Structural conditions		600	86.2%	80.1%
		Socio-economic conditions	365	60.8%	48.7%
		Infrastructure	316	52.7%	42.2%
		Policies and politics	281	46.8%	37.5%
		Physical & geographical environment	241	40.2%	32.2%
		Events and developments	93	15.5%	12.4%
	Resources		560	80.5%	74.8%
		Money	366	65.4%	48.9%
		Time	243	43.4%	32.4%
		Knowledge	181	32.3%	24.2%
		Equipment	120	21.4%	16.0%
		Political and social actors	100	17.9%	13.4%
		Self-efficacy	94	16.8%	12.6%
		Education	86	15.4%	11.5%
	Social dynamics		304	43.7%	40.6%
		Social appreciation	158	52.0%	21.1%
		Community and social networks	95	31.2%	12.7%
		Significant relationships	83	27.3%	11.1%
		Beliefs and values	73	24.0%	9.7%

Note: Relative proportions are calculated as the number of mentions relative to the parent node (i.e., enablers and hindrances are the parent node for resources, social dynamics, and structural conditions, which are themselves the parent node of motivations), and not the total number of respondents. Absolute proportions are calculated as the number of mentions divided by the total number of respondents (n = 749).

Resources are the most frequently mentioned category by respondents, both as enablers (88.6%) and hindrances (80.5%) to environmentally sustainable behaviour. However, the types of resources referenced differ substantially depending on the context and the role they play (enabler or hindrance). Across all groups (see also figures below), respondents highlight knowledge, self-efficacy, and education as major enablers, pointing to the importance of individuals feeling informed, knowledgeable, and capable of acting. However, only with few exceptions, lack of money, time, knowledge, and know-how prevent engagement and sustained environmentally friendly choices. Especially affordability and the 'need to save time' oftentimes shift attention and priorities to more immediate needs and solutions over medium- to longer-term questions of environmental sustainability and climate change.

By contrast, social dynamics are mostly cited as enablers, and much less so as hindrances. This indicates their great potential in driving behavioural change and long-term engagement in environmentally sustainable behaviours. Community support, social networks, close relationships, and shared values are described as key enablers. They can foster a sense of belonging and collective purpose, which can reinforce individual action (Forsyth et al. 2015). Moreover, family, friends, colleagues, and other acquaintances are frequently cited as sources of information, knowledge, know-how, motivation and inspiration that can produce interest in changing behaviours, as well as persistence in continuing engaging with it even in the wake of hindrances. Yet, a lack of social appreciation and predominant social norms are recurrent hindrances. Environmentally sustainable lifestyles are still not the norm and often not valued by others, leading to discouragement and a sense of social pressure to conform to unsustainable norms. This highlights the social dimension of behaviour change: people are more likely to change when they feel supported and part of a wider collective effort (Forsyth et al. 2015). Hence, any serious efforts to shift societies towards environmental sustainability require a broad shift in societal norms and in what is valued. Otherwise, unsustainable norms will continue acting as hindrances and resistances to change.

This links to the last category, structural conditions. These are visibly more often described as hindrances than as enablers. Primarily highlighted are socio-economic conditions, infrastructures, and politics and policies. Besides economic crises and social inequalities, many physical, infrastructural, and policy aspects hinder and constrain opportunities for change: poor public transport and bicycle lanes (both in terms of availability and accessibility); lack of (easy) access to environmentally friendly product alternatives and opportunities to repair and produce oneself; as well as lack of political and economic actors that are perceived to act in favour of opportunities for change, to name some examples. In reverse, however, the same aspects can facilitate behaviour change and environmentally sustainable choices when present or well-designed and available. In particular, the physical and geographical environment as well as politics and policies. This can include not only the availability of green spaces, walkability, and access to farmers markets and shops, but also opportunities for political participation and civic engagement.

Resources across subjective vulnerability grounds

While there are some relatively consistent patterns in the roles of the various factors as enablers or barriers, especially when looking at the different kinds of resources, their relative importance and the intensity of them being perceived as barriers differ between groups.

Starting with a comparison between individuals who report **gender-based** vulnerability (278 out of 749 respondents) with those who do not (n=471), we see that the former are not citing any enabling factors visibly more often than those who reported no gender-based vulnerability. However, the latter cite more often knowledge, education, and access to political and societal actors as enablers (Figure 2). Individuals with a background of gender-based vulnerability in turn emphasise more often time, money, and knowledge deficits as hindrances to environmentally sustainable behaviours (Figure 3). This pattern highlights the gendered distribution of resources, both material and immaterial as well as political. Gendered structures influence the ability to acquire actionable knowledge and the capacity to act upon it. Likewise, they influence who has access – or the self-confidence and feeling of efficacy to access – to actors who have the power to promote political and societal change at larger scales.

Figure 2. Perceived enablers related to resources, by gender-based vulnerability.

Figure 3. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by gender-based vulnerability.

Age-based vulnerability (i.e., being rather young or old) analysis reveals a distinct resource pattern: individuals with age-related disadvantages (141 out of 749 respondents) often perceive knowledge and feelings of self-efficacy as enablers (but not more so than middle-aged individuals), while they also identify time more often than those without age-related vulnerability as a facilitating factor (Figure 4). By contrast, similar to gender-based vulnerability, those *not* experiencing age-based vulnerability (n=608) seem to have better access to political and societal actors as well as to education, citing them more often as enablers. Conversely, age-based vulnerability is associated with reporting financial constraints considerably more as main hindrance, while time *less* often (Figure 5). This points to important life-course dynamics: young and old individuals may possess time and knowledge for engagements, yet financial barriers hinder action.

Figure 4. Perceived enablers related to resources, by age-based vulnerability.

Figure 5. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by age-based vulnerability.

Individuals experiencing **disability-related** vulnerability (99 out of 749 respondents) cite considerably less often knowledge and education as enablers than those not experiencing this kind of vulnerability (n=650) (Figure 6). Self-efficacy, in turn, emerges as a slightly more frequent enabler. By contrast, there are no major disparities in hindrances, except knowledge as seemingly lacking slightly more among those with disability-related vulnerability (Figure 7). This suggests that available information may not be accessible or actionable for people with disabilities, reflecting broader structural and social exclusion.

Figure 6. Perceived enablers related to resources, by disability-based vulnerability.

Figure 7. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by disability-based vulnerability.

As Figure 8 reveals, respondents with a vulnerability linked to their **national minority status** (81 out of 749 respondents) report nearly the same pattern of resources as enablers as the previous group (disability): knowledge and self-efficacy are the most important enablers, but considerably less often cited than of those *not* experiencing this vulnerability. Hindrances follow a very similar pattern, too, yet money is a substantially more pronounced hinder than among those *not* experiencing minority status (n=668) as vulnerability (Figure 9) and those with disabilities. Moreover, access to equipment seems to be lacking. This suggests a particular absence of material resources like money and equipment, posing a hindrance of environmentally sustainable behaviours among those belonging to a national minority (who mention it more often as enabler, see Figure 8). This double resource deficit, i.e., less access to enabling resources (knowledge, education, equipment, money) and

higher exposure to these as hindrances, reflects both economic inequality and epistemic exclusion national minorities often experience.

Figure 8. Perceived enablers related to resources, by national minority status vulnerability.

Figure 9. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by national minority status vulnerability.

In the group experiencing **ethnicity-based** vulnerability (108 out of 749 respondents), knowledge, feelings of self-efficacy, and education are again emphasised as main enablers, yet they are also fairly evenly recognised across both groups (Figure 11). Lack of money, time and knowledge are in turn much more acutely felt as hindrances by respondents who experience vulnerability due to their ethnicity (Figure 12). These findings point to systemic racialized inequalities in access to material resources and information. Simultaneously, time is reported both as a potential facilitator and as a barrier, highlighting the heterogeneity within ethnic minority groups. As in the case of minority status, lack of access to equipment is mentioned more often as a hinder than by those who are not experiencing ethnicity-based vulnerability (n=641).

Figure 10. Perceived enablers related to resources, by ethnicity-based vulnerability.

Figure 11. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by ethnicity-based vulnerability

Just like all previous groups, respondents reporting vulnerability based on **religion or belief** (30 out of 749 respondents) cite knowledge and sense of self-efficacy very frequently, yet they do so more often than any other vulnerability-based group. Besides that, education and time are common enablers. All four factors are also emphasised much more pronouncedly than by those not experiencing vulnerability (n=719) based on their religion or belief (Figure 12). This suggests that strong internal motivation and possibly also the valuing of

knowledge and education are particularly relevant in faith-based contexts. In addition, more than any other group – both other vulnerabilities and the group not experiencing religion or belief as vulnerability – this group emphasises access to political and societal actors as important enablers. At the same time, they are also substantially more often reporting lack of money, time, knowledge, access to equipment, and education as hindrances (Figure 13). These findings point to material and informational barriers that persist despite strong internal drivers, while also highlighting their already existing access to community institutions. Hence, there seems to lie great potential in partnering with faith-based communities in sustainability initiatives for addressing the structural exclusions that constrain action.

Figure 12. Perceived enablers related to resources, by religion or belief vulnerability.

Figure 13. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by religion or belief vulnerability.

Finally, respondents reporting **sexual orientation-based** vulnerability (26 out of 749 respondents) display a more complex relationship to resource-based factors (but also the number of respondents is small). Similar to the previous comparisons, they view knowledge, education, and self-efficacy as enablers, while also money (Figure 14) – which no other group has emphasised to the same extent. They also cite knowledge, money, and time as main hindrances, yet they are the only group that see money less of a hinder than the group not experiencing this kind of vulnerability (Figure 15). This duality reflects a pattern where high awareness and motivation may coexist with disposition of monetary resources and/or the perception of money as less of a constraint for action per se. Another point to emphasise is the relatively little importance attributed to access to political and societal actors, which is mentioned neither as a considerable enabler nor hinder. This suggests – speculatively – that this group has disengaged from politics and relies more on individual-based action.

Figure 14. Perceived enablers related to resources, by sexual orientation-based vulnerability.

Figure 15. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by sexual orientation-based vulnerability.

Social dynamics across subjective vulnerability grounds

Across the seven different vulnerability groups, social dynamics are considerably more often emphasised as enablers than as hindrances. All vulnerability groups name lack of social appreciation as main barrier in this category, while five out of seven name community and social networks as main enablers. However, the share of the social dynamics across the groups varies here and there, with greater variations in the enablers than hindrances. The following section focuses on these variations.

Among respondents experiencing **gender-based** vulnerability, community and social networks is the most frequently mentioned enabler (Figure 16). However, some other patterns are interesting: for these individuals, beliefs and values seem to be a more important enabler than for those not experiencing this kind of vulnerability. Moreover, compared to analyses based on other vulnerability grounds (figures below), no other vulnerable group regards beliefs and values more relevant than the non-vulnerable group (and to such an extent), except for those experiencing vulnerability based on their **sexual orientation** and **religion or belief** (58 and 77 per cent, respectively; see Figures 28 and 24, respectively). At the same time, community and social networks as well as social appreciation show a reversed pattern: here it is the group that does *not* experience gender-based vulnerability that mentions them more often as enabler. Furthermore, only those experiencing vulnerability based on their sexual orientation and religion or belief exhibit the same pattern. Taken together, this suggests that these three groups experience greater autonomy than any other group and are centrally guided by their beliefs and values at engaging with environmental sustainability.

When it comes to hindrances, the only outstanding pattern is the disparity in mentions of beliefs and values as hindrances, see Figure 17. The disparity is noticeable between those experiencing gender-based vulnerability and those who do not, being double as high in the latter group.

Figure 16. Perceived enablers related to social dynamics, by gender-based vulnerability.

Figure 17. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by gender-based vulnerability.

Another pattern to be highlighted can be seen in the groups experiencing **age-based** and **disability-based** vulnerability. Social relationships are mentioned less often by them as enabler than by those experiencing no such kinds of vulnerability (Figures 18 and 19). For all other vulnerability grounds, except for vulnerability based on **sexual orientation** (see Figure 28), the pattern is the reverse, i.e., social relationships are more important for the vulnerable groups. Likewise, the same three groups place lower emphasis on social appreciation as enabler than those who do *not* experience same vulnerabilities, and they mention

it less often than any other vulnerability-based group. Seeing that also beliefs and values are mentioned relatively often by those groups as enablers, this points again to some degree of independence or individual autonomy present in these groups, which might make them have a lower need for social approval or encouragement than others. However, the central role of community and social networks as enabler suggests that embeddedness in a broader, maybe less personalised network of relationships, is highly relevant for them to engage with environmentally friendly behaviours.

The hindrances mentioned by the groups experiencing vulnerability based on their **age** or **disability** follow the same patterns as those experiencing gender-based vulnerability (Figures 16 and 17).

Figure 18. Perceived enablers related to social dynamics, by age-based vulnerability.

Figure 19. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by age-based vulnerability.

Figure 20. Perceived enablers related to social dynamics, by disability-based vulnerability.

Figure 21. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by disability-based vulnerability.

Individuals experiencing vulnerability related to **national minority status** cite less frequently beliefs and values as enablers than those not experiencing this kind of vulnerability (Figure 22) and any other vulnerability-based group. Social networks, in turn, seem to be particularly important, with only the age-based group mentioning it similarly as often as an enabler. Also, significant relationships are mentioned highly. Looking at hindrances, there is only one that stands out in this group, which is community and social networks. It is perceived by 20 per cent as a relevant hindrance (Figure 23). Interestingly, the relevance and also the fact that the vulnerable group considers it considerably more often a hindrance than the non-vulnerable group is the same in the subsequent three comparisons looking at **religion or belief**, **ethnicity**, and **sexual orientation** as vulnerability grounds (Figures 25, 27, 29). These patterns point to the exclusion of minorities from local social structures and

networks. However, when finding access to community networks and structures, it seems to become the crucial enabler of change towards engagement with environmentally sustainable behaviours.

Figure 22. Perceived enablers related to social dynamics, by national minority status vulnerability.

Figure 23. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by national minority status vulnerability.

Respondents reporting **religion or belief-based** vulnerability cite extraordinarily often beliefs and values as enabler of environmentally sustainable behaviour (Figure 24), reflecting the motivational strength of faith-based ethics such as stewardship and justice. Also, social appreciation is mentioned as enabler to a greater extent in this group than in any other group. At the same time, looking at hindrances, the same factor are mentioned as key hindrances: 20 per cent mention beliefs and values as a hindrance to sustainable behaviour, which is higher than in any other vulnerability-based comparison (Figure 25). Also, the experience of lack of social appreciation seems to be more of an issue in this group compared both to those not experiencing this vulnerability, as well as compared to other vulnerability grounds (except for ethnicity-based vulnerability, see below). Lack of social relationships, in turn, seems to be particularly little of a hinder than in any other comparison. Altogether, this points to the ambiguous role of beliefs, values, and the communities built around them: when aligned with environmental values, these factors can be tremendous forces enabling behavioural change and environmental engagement. Yet, when misaligned, they can become massive barriers. This suggests that the role of religion/beliefs and of religiously motivated environmental action may be undervalued or overlooked in secular or mainstream contexts. Affirming diverse ethical worldviews within sustainability efforts and partnering more closely with faith communities can become crucial facilitators for inclusive, values-driven change.

Figure 24. Perceived resources related to social dynamics, by religion or belief vulnerability.

Figure 25. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by religion or belief vulnerability.

Ethnicity-based vulnerability reveals relatively similar patterns as most other groups discussed above, but also a somewhat more strained relationship with social dynamics: respondents cite slightly less often community and social networks as enablers than other groups (except for those experiencing gender-based vulnerability), while social appreciation and social relationships seem to be particularly important enablers (Figure 26). Simultaneously, the group seems to be particularly likely to report lack of social appreciation, social relationships, and community ties as hindrances (Figure 27). In this, they are following a same pattern as was observed among the group experiencing **religion/belief-based** vulnerability. Taken together, the findings suggest that individuals in this group may experience both external exclusion and internal conflict within their networks when engaging in sustainable behaviour. A lack of recognition, social alignment, or support may deter action or render it invisible. Addressing these challenges requires inclusive recognition practices, culturally sensitive interventions, and community-building strategies that affirm diverse identities and contributions within sustainability spaces.

Figure 26. Perceived enablers related to social dynamics, by ethnicity-based vulnerability.

Figure 27. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by ethnicity-based vulnerability.

The analysis of **sexual orientation-based** vulnerability again needs to be interpreted with care, due to the comparatively low number of participants identifying this kind of vulnerability. However, what we see is a in parts similar dynamics as among those experiencing **gender-based** vulnerability: beliefs and values are the most crucial enabler for this group, whereas social relationships, community networks, and social appreciation play a much less relevant role for them than for any other group. As mentioned above, this points to an experience of great autonomy, guided by their beliefs and values. At the same time, they are particularly likely – more so than any other group – to report (lack of) social appreciation, community ties, and close relationships as hindrances. This highlights the need for inclusive, affirming environments that both validate LGBTQ+ contributions and remove social barriers to participation.

Figure 28. Perceived enablers related to social dynamics, by sexual orientation-based vulnerability.

Figure 29. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by sexual orientation-based vulnerability

Structural conditions across subjective vulnerability grounds

Respondents reported structural conditions considerably more often as hindrances than as enablers for environmentally sustainable behaviours. Physical and geographical environmental conditions are named as the single most mentioned enabler, followed by socio-economic conditions, infrastructure, and politics/policies. Socio-economic conditions, however, also pose the greatest barrier. The shares of enabling and hindering structural conditions vary for the different vulnerable groups. Yet, the category of events and developments ranges consistently very low as both enabling or hindering factor (with one exception, mentioned below in the discussion of religion and belief as vulnerability ground).

Gender-based vulnerability is associated with a significantly lower perception of socio-economic conditions as enablers of sustainable behaviour (Figure 30), and higher rates of reported hindrance from this factor and infrastructure. Furthermore, policies and politics are seen less as enabling factor than in the *not* vulnerable group, pointing to a sense of lack of political representation or disconnect. This aligns with general observations of the gendered limitations of current socio-economic systems, which often fail to accommodate caregiving roles, income differences, and safety concerns, among other things, which disproportionately affect women and gender minorities. Structural conditions seem to translate into gendered barriers and limitations of environmentally sustainable behaviour, underscoring the need for gender-responsive planning and inclusive governance (economic and political) in climate and sustainability transitions (Figure 31).

Figure 30. Perceived enablers related to structural conditions, by gender-based vulnerability.

Figure 31. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by gender-based vulnerability.

Age-based vulnerability is associated with a slightly greater perception of the physical environment as an enabler compared to other groups (Figure 32). This points to the role of well-designed or familiar surroundings as supporting engagement for both younger and older individuals. However, as with gender, policies and politics are less frequently seen as enabling, pointing to a sense of political disconnection or underrepresentation among age-vulnerable groups. Interestingly, reported hindrances from structural conditions are similar between groups, implying that while the presence of enabling factors is shaped by age, barriers are more broadly shared (Figure 33). These findings highlight the importance of inclusive, place-based planning and age-responsive policymaking that values the contributions and addresses the needs of all generations.

Figure 32. Perceived enablers related to structural conditions, by age-based vulnerability.

Figure 33. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by age-based vulnerability.

Disability-based vulnerability is associated with infrastructure and socio-economic conditions being seen more often as enablers (Figure 34), yet also with infrastructure standing out as a major hindrance (Figure 35). This duality reflects the critical importance of accessible design and inclusive systems: when present, they enable environmentally sustainable behaviour; when absent, they impose disproportionate constraints. Interestingly, respondents in this group stand out in how little they mention events and developments as enabler or hindrance, possibly pointing to the scarcity of such occasions that are related to, and potentially affecting, disabled persons. Overall, these results underscore the urgency of embedding accessibility in sustainability infrastructure and ensuring that inclusive policies are implemented in practice, not just in principle.

Figure 34. Perceived enablers related to structural conditions, by disability-based vulnerability.

Figure 35. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by disability-based vulnerability.

Respondents identifying with **national minority status** as a vulnerability do not stand out on any factor compared to the other vulnerability groups. However, compared to those who do generally *not* perceive vulnerability due to national minority status, they report more often socio-economic conditions and less often physical conditions and political frameworks as enabler (Figure 36). At the same time, they cite the same factors, i.e., socio-economic disadvantage, inadequate infrastructure, and unfavourable physical geography as major hindrances to environmentally sustainable behaviour (Figure 37). These patterns reflect entrenched structural inequalities in access to resources and services. This is further underlined by the emphasis also of politics and policies as hindrance, pointing to policy systems' failing to address minority-specific realities. Addressing these barriers requires targeted investments in minority communities, inclusive urban planning, and the active participation of national minority groups in environmental governance.

Figure 36. Perceived enablers related to structural conditions, by national minority status vulnerability.

Figure 37. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by national minority status vulnerability.

Respondents experiencing **religion or belief-based** vulnerability stand out on two factors: the physical and geographical environment as well as events and developments are disproportionately often mentioned as enablers of sustainable behaviour (Figure 38). This suggests a strong place-based or spiritual connection to environmental stewardship and, potentially, to environmental or climate events and developments (e.g., environmental changes, natural disasters). This may reflect faith traditions that emphasise care for creation and community engagement in local ecological contexts. In contrast, structural hindrances such as infrastructure or policy are reported at similar levels to those without this vulnerability (Figure 39), indicating that while religious identity may shape motivation and engagement, it does not necessarily correspond to increased systemic exclusion.

Figure 38. Perceived resources related to structural conditions, by religion or belief vulnerability.

Figure 39. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by religion or belief vulnerability.

Enablers related to structural conditions appear overall similar between respondents with and without **ethnicity-based** vulnerability. Only policies and politics are mentioned at a slightly higher proportion than by any other vulnerability-based group (Figure 40 & 41). Furthermore, those with ethnicity-based vulnerability report more often barriers tied to socio-economic conditions and infrastructure (Figure 41). This disparity suggests that equal access does not translate into equal benefit: ethnically minoritised individuals may face compounded challenges that limit their ability to leverage available resources. Poor-quality infrastructure and systemic socio-economic disadvantage reduce the feasibility of sustainable practices, even in settings where physical systems are in place. These findings underline the need to address the unequal outcomes of structural provisions and to design equity-focused sustainability interventions that explicitly redress racialised patterns of exclusion.

Figure 40. Perceived enablers related to structural conditions, by ethnicity-based vulnerability.

Figure 41. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by ethnicity-based vulnerability.

Finally, respondents reporting **sexual orientation-based** vulnerability are a small group in the sample, producing slightly hard-to-interpret results. Nonetheless, what can be said is that this groups seems to merely regard physical geography and environment as a meaningful enabler of all structural conditions (Figure 42). On the side of hindrances, in turn, they see all structural conditions less often as a hindrance of environmentally sustainable behaviour than those not experiencing this kind of vulnerability (Figure 43). This pattern aligns with observations from the previous two sections, which pointed to a greater reliance on individual responsibility and engagement over seeing sustainability as a social project. Alternatively, it may relate to a broader disengagement from, or invisibility within, mainstream infrastructure and policy systems that do not explicitly address LGBTQ+ needs. In any case, it points to a need for more inclusive planning, participatory governance, and targeted attention to how LGBTQ+ individuals experience space, policy, and infrastructure – vis-à-vis their own roles – within sustainability transitions.

Figure 42. Perceived enablers related to structural conditions, by sexual orientation-based vulnerability.

Figure 43. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by sexual orientation-based vulnerability.

3.2 Enablers and hindrances across inequality grounds

The following analysis is based on data from the second research cycle. It focuses on socio-demographic data and their link with enablers and hindrances to environmentally sustainable behaviours. The degree to which resources, social dynamics, and structural conditions function as enablers or barriers varies across different groups, exposing how social inequalities come with systematically different opportunities and possibilities to enact and hold on to behavioural change and environmentally sustainable behaviours. Hindrances are generally felt more acutely by disadvantaged groups, while enabling factors remain fairly evenly distributed.

Resources across different socio-demographic groups

Men (n=161 out of 392 respondents) and women (n=231) experience resources in similar ways as either enablers or hindrances with a few noticeable exceptions. While knowledge is a key enabler for both groups (Figure 44), it is a greater barrier (Figure 45) and weaker enabler for sustainable behaviour for women than men. Moreover, women report self-efficacy and equipment more strongly as enablers, pointing to greater self-reliance and independence.

Figure 44. Perceived enablers related to resources, by gender.

Figure 45. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by gender.

Comparing those older than the average person in the sample (48 years; n=163 out of 356 respondents) and those younger (n=193), many factors range similarly important, yet some differences become visible: time and, to some extent, knowledge are seen more as enabler by the older than average respondents than by the younger ones (Figure 46), whereas the

younger than average respondents name those two factors as greater hindrances (Figure 47). Apart from that, the younger mention education more frequently as enabler, and the older respondents emphasise lack of money slightly more as a hindrance to environmentally sustainable behaviours. The findings follow the pattern of resource availability of age-vulnerable people (Figure 4 and 5) and underscore the importance of considering life-course dynamics. While younger people have greater access to education, they are limited in time which enables older generations. All age groups however are hindered by financial constraints.

Figure 46. Perceived enablers related to resources, by age.

Figure 47. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by age.

Respondents not affected by disabilities or health issues (204 out of 293 respondents) experience knowledge, self-efficacy, and education as the most impactful enablers (Figure 48), and considerably more so than those affected by health issues or disability. Knowledge, or the lack thereof, is mentioned more as a hindrance by responders with disabilities or health issues (n=89). This group also consider education much less significant. Respondents not affected by disabilities or health issues in turn perceive time and money as greatest hindrances (Figure 49). Respondents vulnerable due to disabilities experience resources as more hindering than respondents affected by disabilities or health issues (Figure 49 and Figure 7). The findings point towards the complex diversity of disabilities and health issues, and the difference between inequalities and vulnerability experiences.

Figure 48. Perceived enablers related to resources, by disability or health issue.

Figure 49. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by disability or health issue.

Respondents without a migration background (191 out of 303 respondents) experience self-efficacy and equipment as more enabling than respondents with a migration background (n=112) (Figure 50). Moreover, the later do not just rely on themselves but also emphasise the enabling role of access to political and social actors. However, lack of access to these actors is also considered a greater hindrance by respondents without migration background than those with a migration background (Figure 51). This could point towards greater awareness of the role of politics in this group. Beside this, money and time are another two usual suspects mentioned by both groups as crucial hindrances.

Figure 50. Perceived enablers related to resources, by migration background.

Figure 51. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by migration background.

Enabling resources for respondents who were born in the country of their current residency (281 out of 369 respondents) show a similar pattern those from respondents without a migration background. Self-efficacy, education and political and social actors are again reported more often as enabling resources for respondents born in the country of residence than for those not born in the country (n=84) (Figure 52). Both groups report knowledge as the most important enabler. Interestingly, time is recognised both as a greater enabler (Figure 52) and hindrance (Figure 53) by respondents who were not born in their country of residence. Generally, hindrances are reported fairly evenly across the groups, with the exception of money, time and knowledge which is more acutely felt by respondents who do not reside in their country of birth. Respondents who live in their home country experience political and social actors more often as hindrances than the other group.

Figure 52. Perceived enablers related to resources, by birthplace.

Figure 53. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by birthplace.

Knowledge, self-efficacy, and education are reported as a key enabler by respondents who live in urban areas (303 out of 369 respondents) (Figure 54). However, the same factors are relevant also for those living in rural areas (n=66). Yet, the latter also cite comparatively often material resources like equipment and money as enabling, as well as access to political and social actors. Time is in turn recognised more often as enabling by the urban population, but it also is a more significant hindrance to them than to rural respondents (Figure 55). Other than that, rural residents seem to generally view the lack of resources more hindering than urban residents. Financial constraint is the most often cited barrier to environmentally sustainable behaviour by both rural and urban populations.

Figure 54. Perceived enablers related to resources, by location.

Figure 55. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by location.

Unsurprisingly, report respondents with higher education (183 out of 359 respondents) knowledge, self-efficacy, education, and money more often as enabling than those without higher education (Figure 56). Respondents without higher education (n=176) instead rely more on resources of time, equipment, and political and social actors. They also name lack of education and financial resources as more acute hindrances to environmentally sustainable behaviour (Figure 57). Respondents with higher education experience time and money as key barriers.

Figure 56. Perceived enablers related to resources, by education level.

Figure 57. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by education level

Respondents who were not in paid work at the time of the data collection (158 out of 363 respondents), experienced all resources, except money, more acutely as enabling than the respondent who were in paid work (n=205) (Figure 58). Those without paid work also ex-

perience resources, except time, as only slightly more hindering than the other group (Figure 59). This could point towards functioning support systems in place. Respondents with paid work experience time as an equally strong hindrance than money.

Figure 58. Perceived enablers related to resources, by employment status.

Figure 59. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by employment status.

The diverse and complex experience of respondents who were in paid work at the time of data collection is reflected in the analysis by income level. Respondents with higher income (188 out of 310 respondents) reported all resources more often as enabling than respondents with low income (n=122) (Figure 60). Especially the resources education, time, political and social actors as well as money are reported as more accessible by the high-income group. Unsurprisingly, financial constraints are the strongest hindrance for low-income respondents, with all other resources being significantly less important (Figure 61). Yet interestingly, also the high-income group views money as the greatest hindrance, followed by time. This underscores that financial support could substantially break down barriers for engagement in low-income groups, yet perceptions are relative and independent of income, people will perceive not having sufficient money to engage in the desired environmentally sustainable behaviours and lifestyles.

Figure 60. Perceived enablers related to resources, by income level.

Figure 61. Perceived hindrances related to resources, by income level.

Social dynamics across different socio-demographic groups

The comparison between men (161 out of 392 respondents) and women (n=231) shows that they experience social dynamics fairly equally as enabling and hindering. Community

and social networks are recognised as the greatest enabler by both groups than women (Figure 62). Men, however, mention all social dynamics proportionally more often as enabler than women. This points to some divergence vis-à-vis the finding above when looking at individuals experiencing vulnerability due to their gender, who mentioned beliefs and values as critical enablers while the non-vulnerable group did not (Figure 16). Furthermore, while social dynamics are barely seen as hindrances, men mention (lack of) social appreciation are substantial barrier to environmentally sustainable behaviour (Figure 63).

Figure 62. Perceived enabler related to social dynamics, by gender.

Figure 63. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by gender.

The respondents who are average age or younger in the sample (193 out of 356 respondents) consider social dynamics generally more relevant as enabling than the older ones (n=163) (Figure 64). The latter in turn view the social dynamics slightly more hindering, with the exception of social appreciation (Figure 65), which poses a significant barrier for the younger respondents. The patterns mirror the enabling and hindering social dynamics of age-based and non-age based vulnerable groups.

Figure 64. Perceived enablers related to social dynamics, by age.

Figure 65. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by age.

Respondents not affected by disabilities or health issues (204 out of 293 respondents) generally feel social dynamics as both enabling and hindering more acutely than those not affected. Community and social network and significant relationships are the most important enabler for both groups (Figure 66). Social appreciation and beliefs and values are in turn substantially more important for respondents of the non-affected group. Respondents affected by disabilities or health issues (n=89) experience social dynamics less as hindrances

(Figure 67). These findings suggest that if social dynamics are available to people with disabilities or health issues, they are significant enablers of environmentally sustainable behaviours.

Figure 66. Perceived enablers related to social dynamics, by disability or health issue.

Figure 67. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by disability or health issue.

Respondents with no migration background (191 out of 303 respondents) report social dynamics as more enabling or hindering than respondents with a migration background (n=112). Community and social networks as well as beliefs and values are especially enabling for respondents without migration background (Figure 68). Both groups highlight social appreciation as the main hindrance to sustainable behaviour (Figure 69), with an equal share of respondents naming this social dynamic as enabling and hindering. Respondents with a migration background, experience social dynamics as less hindering, indicating that a support of enabling dynamics can have a significant positive impact on their sustainable behaviour.

Figure 68. Perceived enablers related to social dynamics, by migration background.

Figure 69. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by migration background.

The pattern of social dynamics as enablers or hindrances is somewhat different in the analysis by birthplace. Compared to the analysis by migration background, respondents who were born in the country of their residence (281 out of 365 respondents) do not report social dynamics as significantly more enabling or hindering than respondents not born in the place of their residence (n=84). Both groups emphasis community and social networks and significant relationships as most enabling, but respondents not living in their home country report these dynamics more often (Figure 70). Social appreciation – or the lack thereof – is

in turn felt more by those not born in the country as a hindrance (Figure 71). The slight difference suggests that those not born in the country tend to generally be well-connected, while those born in the country seem to be well connected too but less reliant or dependent on appreciation by others.

Figure 70. Perceived enablers related to social dynamics, by birthplace.

Figure 71. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by birthplace.

Looking at rural population (66 out of 369) community and social networks, social relationships and beliefs and values are considerably more often mentioned as enablers than by the urban dwellers (Figure 72). The two groups experience them as hindrances to same extents, with social appreciation, or the lack thereof, posing the greatest barrier (Figure 73).

Figure 72. Perceived enablers related to social dynamics, by location.

Figure 73. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by location

The levels of mentions of social dynamics as enablers are similar among those with high and those with low education. However, those with higher education view beliefs and values slightly more important as enablers than those with low education, while the pattern is the reverse for social relationships (Figure 74). Like most previous group distinctions, we can see here that the lack of social appreciation is the most acute hindrance to environmentally sustainable behaviour (Figure 75).

Figure 74. Perceived enablers related to social dynamics, by education level.

Figure 75. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by education level.

The comparison between people in paid work (205 out of 363 respondents) and those who are not in paid work (n=158) follows nearly the exact same pattern as the previous comparison between levels of education – both for enablers and hindrances (Figure 76 & 77). Having high or low income do not provide substantially different results either; however, beliefs and values as well as social relationships are similar important enablers for both groups (Figure 76).

Figure 76. Perceived enablers related to social dynamics, by employment status.

Figure 77. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by employment status.

Respondents who reported receiving a high income (188 out of 310 respondents) and respondents receiving a lower income (n=122) experience social dynamics similarly as enabling and hindering. Beliefs and values, however, play a more significant positive role for respondents with higher income (Figure 78). While both groups report community and social networks as enabling, poses social appreciation or the lack thereof as the greatest hindrance for both groups (Figure 79).

Figure 78. Perceived enablers related to social dynamics, by income level.

Figure 79. Perceived hindrances related to social dynamics, by income level.

Structural conditions across different socio-demographic groups

Men (161 out of 392 respondents) and women (n=231) experience effects of structural conditions fairly the same as enabling or hindering. Both groups cite physical geography and environment as the most important enabler (Figure 80), yet still less often than the frequencies at which most resources are mentioned as hindrances (Figure 81). The remaining structural conditions are named slightly more often as enabler, and less often as hinder, by women than men. This points to some degree of greater independence of women from structural conditions than men.

Figure 80. Perceived enablers related to structural conditions, by gender.

Figure 81. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by gender.

Age comes with distinct perceptions of policies and politics, physical geography and environment, and infrastructure. Older respondents (163 out of 356 respondents) find geography more enabling than younger ones – but also more often a hindrance, whereas the younger respondents (n=193) cite policies and politics considerably more often as enabling than the older ones (Figure 82). For hindrances, it is exactly the reverse: Older than average respondents identify policies and politics as the most significant hindrance (Figure 83), and the younger group infrastructure and geography. This indicates that older individuals are, for one, more sensitive to geographic conditions, be they enabling or hindering. And for another, it points to a potentially greater focus of politics on younger people.

Figure 82. Perceived enablers related to structural conditions, by age.

Figure 83. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by age.

Respondents with disabilities or health issues (89 out of 293 respondents), experience structural conditions slightly less frequently as enabling than respondents without (n=204), especially when it comes to policies and politics, and events and developments (Figure 84). Interestingly, however, respondents with disabilities or health issues report no factors substantially more often as hindrances, on the contrary (Figure 85).

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Figure 84. Perceived enablers related to structural conditions, by disability or health issue.

Figure 85. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by disability or health issue.

People with a migration background (112 out of 303 respondents) report most conditions as slightly more enabling than respondents without a migration background (n=191) (Figure 86). Respondents without a migration background, on the other hand, experience all structural conditions more acutely, especially infrastructure (Figure 87). Social and economic conditions, as well as policies and politics, are the most important barriers to sustainable behaviour for people with a migration background, indicating that both groups face different structural inequalities.

Figure 86. Perceived enablers related to structural conditions, by migration background.

Figure 87. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by migration background.

While both groups feel structural conditions more significantly as hindrances than enablers, respondents born in the country (281 out of 365 respondents) name nearly all factors substantially more often as hindrance than those not born in the country (n=84). For the latter group, social and economic conditions are the most important enabler (Figure 88), but the same condition is also mentioned as the second-most significant barrier (Figure 89). The findings suggest that those not born in the country are less sensitive to the effects of structural conditions. This could be due to a lack of integration. However, considering that this group also mentioned to a greater extent community networks and social relationships as central enabler, it might rather be that these people are in fact particularly well-integrated in social networks, which cushion potential negative effects from structural conditions.

Figure 88. Perceived enablers related to structural conditions, by birthplace.

Figure 89. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by birthplace.

Comparing urban and rural dwellers reveals a rather unusually strong difference between groups. The rural population (66 out of 369) emphasises physical geography and environment as a very strong enabler (Figure 90), but likewise as a very frequently mentioned hindrance (Figure 91). Respondents living in urban areas (n=303) put more emphasis on policies and politics as an enabler – which is a strong hindrance for rural inhabitants. Urban residents, on the other hand, experience infrastructure and social and economic conditions as the strongest hindrances, the latter also being another significant barrier for the rural inhabitants.

Figure 90. Perceived enablers related to structural conditions, by location.

Figure 91. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by location

Looking at education, there is no meaningful variation in enabler across the groups (Figure 92). However, experiences of hindrances vary. In general, structural conditions are more acutely felt as hindrances by respondents with no higher education (176 out of 369 respondents) (Figure 93). The only exception is policies and politics, which is cited particularly often as a hindrance by those with higher education (n=183). This suggests a higher awareness of political processes among the more highly educated, as well as possibly greater access to material and immaterial resources that help cushion the negative effects of structural conditions.

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Figure 92. Perceived enablers related to structural conditions, by education level.

Figure 93. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by education level.

Just like those with higher education, respondents who were in paid work at the time of data collection (205 out of 363 respondents) report policies and politics to be more hindering than those not in paid work (n=158) (Figure 95). All the other factors are more acutely felt as hindrances by the presumably more disadvantaged group, i.e., those not in paid work. However, this group also mentions most factors more frequently as enabling, especially (interestingly) social and economic conditions (Figure 94). Considering that they also experience money as the greatest hindering resource, and community and social networks as substantial enabler, the enabling effect may come more from the social than the economic side. This is underscored by the observation that the analysis by income level (low/high) mirrors the patterns almost entirely (Figures 96 and 97). Moreover, similar to the respondents with higher education, policies and politics are considered central barriers for environmentally sustainable behaviours and lifestyles.

Figure 94. Perceived enablers related to structural conditions, by employment status.

Figure 95. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by employment status.

Figure 96. Perceived enablers related to structural conditions, by income level.

Figure 97. Perceived hindrances related to structural conditions, by income level.

4 Conclusions and recommendations: Synthesis and discussion of insights

The ACCTING project's extensive empirical investigation demonstrates that sustainable behavioural change is shaped by a complex interplay of resources, social dynamics, and structural conditions – and that these factors operate differently across groups defined by multi-dimensional vulnerabilities and socio-demographic characteristics. The results altogether reveal a landscape where enablers and hindrances are almost equally present, and where same factors – resources, social dynamics, and structural conditions – can be both enabling and hindering at the same time. Yet, the disaggregation of the multiple layers of data uncovers critical patterns that point to broader societal dynamics and systemic constraints shaping opportunities for environmental engagement. Moreover, while the separate factors were addressed separately in the analysis, a cross-cutting synthesis reveals how these categories intersect, reinforce, or undermine each other. This emphasises the need to view these elements not in isolation, but as part of a broader set of conditions shaped by subjective vulnerabilities and socio-demographic positionings.

4.1 Interdependences between resources, social dynamics, and structural conditions

Across all groups, knowledge, self-efficacy, and education are major enablers, while, with a few exceptions, lack of money, time, knowledge, and know-how prevent sustained environmental sustainability. However, the impact of these resources is not uniform; their effectiveness depends heavily on both social and structural contexts. For example, knowledge is a widely reported enabler across all groups. Yet, in some groups, including those with gender-, disability-, ethnicity-, or national minority-based vulnerabilities, knowledge is also frequently cited as a hindrance. This suggests that available information may not be accessible or applicable in practice. It also implies that structural factors, such as the format, language, and relevance of information, mediate whether knowledge functions as a resource at all. Likewise, self-efficacy is cited as a resource more often than education by

many vulnerable groups. However, without access to institutional or social support, its practical utility appears limited. Consequently, structural accessibility and social reinforcement are necessary conditions for these internal resources to translate into action.

In fact, social dynamics play a uniquely powerful enabling role for environmental sustainability engagements across vulnerability groups and inequalities. Community and social networks, interpersonal relationships, as well as beliefs and values are consistently mainly experienced as enabling factors. However, lack of social appreciation, that is, the absence of recognition or validation for environmentally sustainable behaviours, emerges as a recurrent hindrance across nearly all vulnerability groups and socio-demographic categories. The consistent presence of this factor highlights a broader misalignment between individual sustainability efforts and prevailing social norms, which are often perceived as discouraging or devaluing environmentally considerate actions. In some groups, particularly those experiencing vulnerabilities based on gender, sexual orientation, ethnicity, and religion/belief, beliefs and values are more greatly emphasised as enablers than social ties. This points toward a form of autonomy or inward motivation.

Yet, the same groups are also more likely to report lack of social appreciation or exclusion from community networks as key barriers. Ethnic minority respondents are especially likely to report both social relationships and appreciation as hindrances, suggesting a combination of external exclusion and internal social tension. This is compounded by consistent disadvantages in money, knowledge, time, education, and equipment, and diminished trust in political or social actors – visible in the fact that ethnicity-based vulnerability is linked to the broadest and most severe resource constraints. Religion or belief-based vulnerability is, in turn, associated with strong enabling effects of self-efficacy, education, and time, likely rooted in value-based motivation. They also seem to have shared ethical or spiritual values as strong motivators and a behavioural compass, facilitating environmental action. Yet, the group experiences a lack of social appreciation, which suggests limited visibility or recognition in secular or mainstream sustainability spaces. The findings then point to the risk that even strong internal motivations can be undermined when they are not accompanied by a supportive social context. Social embeddedness, when positive, can reinforce resource-based enablers like knowledge and confidence; but when lacking or exclusionary, it magnifies existing vulnerabilities and constraints.

Financial and time constraints are another two recurrent critical hindrances across all groups. While individuals with age-related or disability-related vulnerabilities and those not in paid work may report having time as an enabler, this is offset by their increased experience of financial barriers. In reverse, people in paid employment, those with high income, and younger individuals report time as a main hindrance. Still, even those with paid work and high income cite money as a major hindrance. Altogether, this illustrates two dynamics: First, there are some life-course dynamics that shape access to resources, and there are life-course-specific trade-offs between different types of resources. These, in turn, are shaped by structural factors such as employment models and social support systems. But second, as both low- and high-income groups cite money as the greatest barrier, this suggests that perceived financial limitation is not only about absolute income. It is also about relative perceptions and competing priorities, underscoring the subjective dimension of resource-based barriers. What this implies is the need to understand that money will always be an issue for everyone, independent of how rich or poor the people, or how expensive or cheap the issue. Respectively, it is important to acknowledge the need for context-sensitive

interventions that offset financial burdens, as for maintaining a critical resilience toward backlash that is motivated purely by financial worries. Here, interventions can tap into the power of other resources, which can precisely contribute to the offsetting of potential financial problems.

Specifically, social dynamics intersect with these resource patterns by either amplifying or mitigating barriers. Supportive relationships, community networks, and shared values function as motivational resources, particularly for groups that experience institutional or infrastructural barriers. For example, respondents with a migration background, or those not born in their country of residence, often report political actors as both a potential enabler and a key barrier. Yet these same groups cite community support and networks as critical enablers, suggesting that social relationships compensate for institutional exclusion. Similarly, individuals with religion- or belief-based vulnerabilities draw heavily on values and social appreciation as enabling factors, even when structural support is weak. These examples show that social dynamics can fill gaps left by missing or inadequate structural or institutional provisions.

Nonetheless, as highlighted above, lack of social appreciation consistently undermines individual resources across nearly all groups. Even among those who report strong motivation and knowledge, the absence of social recognition acts as a significant deterrent. This is especially evident among respondents with ethnicity- or sexual orientation-based vulnerabilities, where exclusion from social networks coincides with limited access to structural enablers, reinforcing disadvantage through multiple pathways.

4.2 Structural conditions as multipliers of inequality

Structural conditions, especially infrastructure, the socio-economic environment, and policies or politics, emerge more often as hindrances than enablers. Yet their significance lies less in frequency and more in their ability to either compound or alleviate resource-based and social barriers. For example, individuals with disability-based vulnerability cite infrastructure as both a key enabler and a significant hindrance. This reflects that when infrastructure is designed to be accessible, it actively supports environmentally sustainable behaviour. But when absent, it imposes disproportionate burdens. This twofold role is evident in other groups as well. Respondents from rural areas report physical geography as both enabling and hindering, suggesting that it all depends on the case-specific availability of transport, services, and opportunities for engagement, not the rural-urban divide per se.

Thus, structural conditions are not neutral; they either reinforce or buffer pre-existing inequalities. This buffering role is particularly relevant in relation to financial and informational resources. For example, the responses from those with gender-based and national minority-based vulnerabilities point to a disconnection from political and societal actors. They are also the ones who report lower access to enabling resources like time, money, and knowledge, even when a strong internal motivation is present.

Structural conditions also shape how individuals interpret the utility of their own resources. For instance, respondents with a migration background report higher levels of self-efficacy and interest in accessing political actors than those without such a background. However, they simultaneously report more barriers to accessing these actors, indicating a gap between motivation and opportunity that is defined by structural accessibility. These mis-

matches between individual readiness and institutional openness can result in disengagement or disillusionment. What this highlights is that enabling behaviour is not only about individual capacity, but also about structural responsiveness. Structural and political marginalisation constrains the ability to convert internal resources (like knowledge or motivation) into action. Moreover, the experience of exclusion from public infrastructure, policy processes, or geographic advantages does not just function as a physical barrier. It also reinforces social and resource-based inequities, especially when compounded by additional factors like low income or lack of education.

4.3 The unequal distribution of hindrances

A consistent pattern across all categories is that hinderers are more unevenly distributed than enablers. Enablers such as knowledge, self-efficacy, and community networks are widely cited across all groups. In contrast, hindrances like particularly lack of time, money, education, and social appreciation, are reported more intensely and more frequently by disadvantaged or vulnerable groups. This distribution is not coincidental. It reflects the compounding effects of socio-economic disadvantage, structural exclusion, and limited social recognition. For instance, individuals without higher education and less income report lack of education and financial resources as core barriers, while those with higher education and high income identify political frameworks as a major obstacle. This proposes that there is a shift from material constraints to systemic frustrations depending on privilege.

In some groups, such as those not in paid work or living in rural areas, the same structural or resource conditions are experienced as both enabling and constraining, depending on how they interact with other life circumstances. People not in paid work report more enablers overall, suggesting available time and possibly support systems in place. But they also cite money as a core hindrance, underscoring that the presence of one enabler does not automatically offset the absence of others.

Rural versus urban residence also reveals significant differences. While knowledge, self-efficacy, and education are key enablers in both contexts, rural respondents more often cite time as both an enabler and a barrier, likely reflecting the demands of more dispersed infrastructures or seasonal livelihoods. Urban respondents, in contrast, place greater emphasis on material enablers like money, equipment, and access to political and social actors – but also experience these as greater barriers, reflecting the cost-of-living pressures and competitive access to public services typical of urban environments.

In sum, vulnerability shapes how individuals experience the opportunities and constraints of sustainable behaviour. Across all groups, the data show that neither any single enabler nor any hindrances are universal. These differences in access to resources, social support, and structural conditions mean that behavioural change is not equally feasible for all. The findings challenge 'one-size-fits-all' models of behaviour change. Instead, they call for a nuanced, justice-oriented, and pro-active approach to the socio-ecological transformation needed and political programmes like the European Green Deal. Inclusion cannot be an afterthought. Achieving fair and effective environmental and climate action requires taking into account the understanding we have generated in this project of how vulnerability operates in practice: not as a fixed label, but as a lived experience shaped by context, identity, and structural position.

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PART II: Qualitative comparative analysis

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1 Introduction

The second part of D3.4 is devoted to the secondary analysis of the results of the second research cycle of the eight ACCTING research lines (RLs) using Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA). Although QCA is applied to each RL separately, some cross-cutting insights are also discussed.

In this part, after a brief introduction to the main features of QCA and its role in ACCTING, RL-specific QCA reports are featured (sections 1 to 8), followed by brief overall conclusions (section 9).

1.1 Qualitative Comparative Analysis in a nutshell

Qualitative Comparative Analysis is a research methodology intended to bridge the gap between qualitative and quantitative approaches, offering a systematic way to **analyse complex causal relationships**. Developed by Charles Ragin in the 1980s (Ragin 1987), QCA is particularly useful when the aim is to understand the factors (“conditions” in QCA terminology) leading to specific outcomes.

QCA originated as an alternative to conventional variable-based statistical methods, which often struggle to accommodate small and medium-sized datasets while maintaining robust causal inferences. To address these limitations, Ragin, the founder of QCA, focused on set-theoretic relations and case-based comparisons. Unlike traditional statistical methods, that focus on the net effects of variables, QCA employs a case-oriented approach, emphasising **configurational causality**, where conditions interact to produce an effect rather than operating independently, acknowledging that causal relationships are rarely simple or linear (Byrne 2013). For this reason, QCA is particularly suited for comparative case study methodologies (Ragin & Rihoux 2004).

In order to gain a deeper understanding of the phenomena analysed, the method allows for the exploration of causal configurations that lead to the absence of the outcome—recognising that these are not simply the inverse of those producing a positive outcome. QCA is based on the principle of **causal asymmetry** (Ragin 2008a), which holds that the presence and absence of a condition may have different effects, and that distinct combinations of conditions can lead to different outcomes. This enables a more nuanced understanding of causality.

Because of its set-theoretic approach, QCA works by defining whether the cases under study belong to a particular set defined by the research question and identified as the **outcome** (e.g., reduction of inequalities, behavioural change, acceptance of sustainability policies). It does so by assigning each case values that indicate their membership degree to that set.

Among the **fundamental principles** of QCA, the following can be mentioned here: equifinality and causal asymmetry (Berg-Schlosser et al. 2009, Fiss 2009, Thomann & Maggetti 2020). The principle of **equifinality** recognises that different causal pathways may lead to the same result. This means that no single factor is universally necessary or sufficient; instead, varying conditions can contribute to the same outcome in different cases. QCA has evolved into **multiple variants** (Ragin 2009), each catering to different research needs and data characteristics. To the aim of our analysis, the two most important ones can be mentioned.

1. Crisp-Set QCA (csQCA): This is the original form of QCA, where conditions are binary (0 or 1). A case either belongs to a set (1) or does not (0). This approach is useful when clear-cut categorical distinctions exist.
2. Fuzzy-Set QCA (fsQCA): This is an extension of csQCA, allowing for partial set membership by assigning values between 0 and 1. This approach is more flexible and accommodates degrees of belongingness, making it useful for analysing phenomena with continuous variation, allowing for nuanced differentiation among cases.

In the case of the ACCTING research lines, due to the predominantly qualitative, non-scalar nature of the outcome and most of the conditions, crisp set QCA was chosen. Crisp sets were also preferred because RLs had small or very small-N panels.

A QCA study follows a structured **methodological approach** (Ragin 2009, Schneider & Wagemann 2010, Thomann & Maggetti 2020) with subsequent steps which are described in dedicated subsections in each RL-specific QCA report (sections 1 to 8).

1. **Objectives of the study**
2. **Outcome identification:** The original research question is operationalised to identify a measurable outcome that is comparable across cases.
3. **Case selection and identification of conditions:** Cases relevant to the research question are selected, taking care to include cases with different outcomes to allow meaningful comparison. Case selection should ensure sufficient diversity while maintaining analytical comparability. Based on the theoretical setup of the research and its empirical findings, conditions are identified that are more meaningful to test to identify configurations that lead to outcomes.
4. **Calibration of conditions and outcomes:** Calibration is conducted for the definition of the set membership of cases in terms of both conditions and outcomes. In csQCA, binary distinctions are made, whereas in fsQCA, researchers assign membership scores using qualitative anchors and empirical thresholds.
5. **Truth Table construction:** A truth table is built to organise the cases based on their combinations of conditions and associated outcomes. The truth table is the foundation for the analysis, helping to identify consistent patterns.
6. **Logical Minimisation and identification of causal configurations:** Minimisation through Boolean Algebra techniques is performed using dedicated software to simplify complex causal configurations into concise rules, identifying the most parsimonious and empirically supported causal pathways. Robustness measures are considered, like the consistency² and coverage³ of the identified configurations.

² The consistency of a QCA solution is the ratio of cases with a positive outcome in that solution to the total number of cases in the same solution. For example, if a solution contains 15 cases, of which 14 have a positive outcome and 1 has a negative outcome, the consistency would be given by the ratio $14/15 = 0.933333$. The highest consistency would be if all cases in the solution had a positive outcome: $15/15 = 1$. Although the appropriate level for consistency is research-specific, consistency ratios of 0.75 and above are generally considered acceptable.

³ The coverage of a QCA solution is the ratio of cases that have a positive outcome in that solution to the total number of cases in the sample that have a positive outcome. For example, if a solution contains only 14 of the 18 cases with a positive outcome, the coverage is given by the ratio $14/18 = 0.777778$. The coverage is 1 if

7. **Interpretation:** The identified causal pathways are interpreted, comparing them with theoretical expectations. This can entail the need to go back to the empirical results and modify something in calibration criteria or in the assignment of set membership.

QCA offers several **methodological advantages**, such as the possibility of including both qualitative and quantitative data in the same methodological process (Rihoux & Lobe 2009); its application to small and medium N studies, as opposed to regression analysis, which typically requires large data sets (Petesch et al. 2018); its focus on complex causality, which recognises and addresses the fact that social phenomena are shaped by multiple interacting factors (Byrne 2013); and its structured process, which allows for replication and verification of findings (Berg-Schlusser et al. 2009, Thomann & Maggetti 2020).

The **limitations** of QCA must also be recognised. Calibration is a critical step in the process, and poorly defined set membership criteria can lead to biased results. There's also an inherent degree of subjectivity in setting thresholds, which is based on the researchers' assessment and inevitably influences the results (Schneider & Wagemann 2010). Theoretical and substantive knowledge should be used to set the thresholds (Ragin & Rihoux 2004, Schneider & Wagemann 2010). Modest generalisability of results (Ciccina 2016) must also be considered, as QCA focuses on specific case configurations that may not generalise beyond the context studied and the ones that are closely similar.

1.2 The role of QCA in ACCTING

The theoretical design of ACCTING rests on a complex vision of behavioural change, which relies on a multitude of interconnected factors and cannot be framed in a linear, deterministic model. The crucial consideration of intersectional inequalities adds layers of complexity to the analysis. A **complexity-informed approach** such as QCA is therefore used to understand the cases under study as complex, dynamic systems, and to link their outcomes to configurations of factors that explain their variance (Byrne & Barniaux 2017, Walby 2007).

Given the **policy orientation** of the research carried out in ACCTING, this approach is also appropriate because it allows the identification of different 'causal recipes' (Ragin 2008b) for individual and collective actors towards inclusive behavioural change, supporting the identification of appropriate measures and actions for both policymakers and civil society actors.

In this perspective, the research lines in ACCTING have been designed in the second cycle to allow the application of QCA, with multiple case studies selected in each participating country in all RLs. A collaborative and iterative process with RL leaders and teams has been implemented to support the identification of outcomes, the most promising conditions to test and their calibration, as well as the interpretation of the solutions provided by QCA.

It is generally considered that QCA can have different functions (Berg-Schlusser 2009):

- Summarising data to display them in a more compact and effective way, bringing to light similarities between cases that may, at first sight, seem quite different.

the solution contains all 18 positive cases: $18/18 = 1$. Although the appropriate level for coverage is research-specific, coverage ratios of 0.75 and above are generally considered acceptable.

- Checking coherence of data, as it happens when contradicting configurations are detected and there is a chance to get more thorough knowledge of relevant cases and develop a more coherent body of evidence.
- Corroborate or falsify hypotheses or existing theories in a way that is both systematic and empirical by operationalising them through the identification of a series of conditions that should yield a particular outcome.
- Theory building, that is, the development of new theoretical arguments in the form of hypotheses formulated in a "dialogue with the cases" and their results.

Within ACCTING, QCA has been used for different purposes, depending on the different RL setups and results. Considering its application as **a tool for secondary analysis of RL results**, its uses ranged from providing a more synthetic presentation of the results to providing additional insights that may have been lost or unnoticed in the vast amount of qualitative and quantitative material collected under each RL. In addition, in some cases the QCA process led to the identification of inconsistencies and the refinement of the empirical basis of the cases analysed.

In ACCTING, the primary focus was on identifying the causal configurations that enabled the achievement of the outcome. However, noteworthy findings also emerged in some Research Lines when attention was directed towards cases associated with the absence of the outcome.

It is worth noting that only seven of the eight ACCTING Research Lines underwent Qualitative Comparative Analysis. In the case of RL6 (Values Associated with Environmentally Sustainable Food Consumption), an attempt was made to carry out the analysis, but it did not yield significant results. One possible explanation is the predominantly quantitative nature of the study, which did not allow sufficient case knowledge for the specific outcome we intended to analyse through QCA.

2 QCA Reports

2.1 QCA report for RL1: Valorising local knowledge in disaster management

Objectives of the study

Research line 1 focuses on how local communities play an active role in preventing, preparing for and managing disasters brought about by climate-change-related natural hazards. The research seeks to learn from the experiences and insights of local communities, while exploring ways to further empower them.

The second research cycle built upon the findings from the first, which identified significant untapped potential for improving the effectiveness of disaster management within local communities. The focus was not on placing responsibility on vulnerable communities, but rather on emphasising the need for authorities to lead adaptation efforts. The notion of authority here refers to the range of public and private social organisations responsible for managing disasters, from preparedness through to emergency response and recovery.⁴

Outcome identification

In the context of the QCA exercise, the outcome was identified as the ability of authorities to engage with local knowledge in preparing for and responding to natural hazards.

In light of the complexity of this assessment, further intensified by the marked heterogeneity of territorial contexts and the range of entities identified as authorities, it was deemed appropriate to operationalise this outcome at two distinct levels: stronger (STRONG_IMP) and weaker (WEAK_IMP) impact.

STRONG_IMP is recognised if inclusive local knowledge is structurally integrated in the civil protection response.

WEAK_IMP is recognised if significant efforts have been or are being made to consider local knowledge in the civil protection response.

For each case, the main sources for assessing both outcomes were in-depth interviews with authority representatives and with citizens exposed to natural hazards. Finally, the country reports prepared by each research team have been used to contextualise the initiatives' overall effects.

Case selection and identification of conditions

Case selection

A total of ten cases were analysed, in rural, mixed and urban contexts. The countries involved are Italy, Portugal, Sweden, and Türkiye. The cases are very diverse and related to various natural hazards/set of natural hazards. They are presented in Table 2.

⁴ The full RL1 report is authored by James White (ORU), in collaboration with Ayşe Gül Altınay (SU), Catarina Conceição (IGOT), Esin Düzel (SU), Marcelo Fragoso (IGOT), Francesca Pugliese (K&I), Gabriele Quinti (K&I), Lina Sandström (UGOT), Burcu Borhan Türeli (SU), João Vasconcelos (IGOT), and Carolin Zorell (ORU).

Table 2. Types of cases considered by country and natural hazards within RL1.

INITIATIVE	IT	PT	SE	TR
Flood (or flood + heatwaves)	XX	XX		
Landslides (originated by flood)	X			
Forest fires			X	XXX
Non specified			X	

Identification of conditions

The identification of the conditions to be related to the different outcomes of the initiatives was guided by the main theoretical tenets of ACCTING:

- The centrality of gender+, intersectional perspectives in prevention, preparedness and response for disasters
- The identification of priority target groups through multidimensional vulnerability approaches
- The key role of vulnerable/disadvantaged communities in managing environmental transitions
- Valorising local and traditional knowledge through trans-epistemic practices
- The role of inclusive policymaking.

On this basis, the following sets of information have been collected and analysed for each initiative:

- **Context** (urban, peri-urban, semi-rural, rural)
- **General description of the case** (background, scope, relevant natural hazards)
- **Configuration of the authority** (actors involved, the levels concerned, from local to national, the professional profiles represented within the authority, and the presence of women in positions of responsibility).
- **Interactions between the authority and citizens** (how people are involved and who is included, tensions or disagreements, how local knowledge is recognised, enabling and hindering factors, how these interactions relate to change),
- **Intersectional considerations** (how are diversity and gender+ inclusion considered, how is this reflected in policy outcomes, whose voices remain unheard and why, enabling and hindering factors),
- **Effects of the interaction in the local community** (effects of the above on disaster preparedness and response).

Within these sets, the conditions expected to have the greatest impact were selected according to the identified outcomes (stronger and weaker outcome) for RL1. Conditions were also selected based on the **number of cases** exhibiting them, as conditions present in all or only a very few cases are not suitable for comparison in QCA analysis. The selected conditions are listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Codes for conditions within RL1.

CODE	CONDITION
TERR_CONT	Territorial context of the initiative (urban, peri-urban, semi-rural, rural)

HAZARD	Single or multiple hazard
AUTH_CONST	Constellation of public authorities that are involved in the initiative
WOMEN_LEAD	Presence of women in leading positions in the authority(ies) involved
REL_CSO	Existence of structured relations with Civil Society Organisations
SOC_PROFES	Structural embedding of social professions in the authority managing the initiative (e.g., health and social care or community policing)
BOTTOM-UP	Integration of bottom-up perspectives in the preparedness approach
G+_CONSID	Inclusion of gender+ considerations in civil protection response
G+_INCLUS	Gender+ inclusiveness of community engagement

Calibration of conditions and outcomes

To apply crisp-set QCA, the available information was reduced to binary systems (0-1), assigning a set membership score to each case and condition.

The calibration of the two outcomes (i.e., the stronger or weaker ability of authorities to engage with local knowledge in preparing for and responding to natural hazards) was based on the holistic assessment of the responses of both local authority representatives and citizens to the in-depth interview guide. Overall, as shown in Table 3 below, 3 out of 10 initiatives achieved a positive outcome in the first case (STRONG_IMP) and 7 out of 10 achieved the second positive outcome (WEAK_IMP). A table showing the calibration of the main conditions used in the QCA applied to RL1 is presented in the Appendix.

Truth table construction

A final truth table for each causal configuration that was identified ("solution") was produced according to the procedure described in the Appendix, where the truth tables are also presented. As will be explained in the next sections, the solutions analysed in this context are based on the following three combinations of conditions. The first two relate to the achievement of STRONG_IMP and the last to the achievement of WEAK_IMP.

1. TERR_CONT * REL_CSO * BOTTOM-UP * G+_CONSID * G+_INCLUS
2. BOTTOM-UP * SOC_PROFES * TERR_CONT
3. TERR_CONT * AUTH_CONST * G+_INCLUS

Based on the combinations observed in the panel, it was possible to perform a "Standard analysis" for each solution using the fsQCA software, the results of which are presented in the following section.

Identification of causal configurations

The distribution of the ten cases by two different outcomes is shown in Table 4 (for a more detailed description of the panel, see the RL1 report).

Table 4. RL1 panel by case and outcome.

CODE	STRONG_IMP	WEAK_IMP
IT01	0	0
IT02	1	1
IT03	0	1
PT01	0	1
PT02	0	0
SE01	0	0
SE02	0	1
TR01	0	1
TR02	1	1
TR03	1	1
Total	3	7

Different combinations of conditions were tested to explore their relation to the outcome. The results are described below.

*Different combinations of conditions were tested to explore their relationship with the outcomes, starting with those more related to the ACCTING theoretical approaches, and then broadening the scope to test additional combinations. **It is important to note** that QCA aims to identify combinations of conditions, so it may well be that conditions that are highly relevant in a binary correlation do not produce robust results when combined with others, i.e. are not critical in identifying consistent patterns or individual profiles that lead to an outcome.*

The pathway to STRONG_IMP

In terms of STRONG_IMP (local knowledge is structurally integrated into the civil protection response), the first and most important result to highlight is that the positive cases fully share a number of conditions. A single strong pathway emerges from the analysis.

SOLUTION 1 – INCLUSIVE, BOTTOM-UP INITIATIVES IN RURAL AREAS

Analysed conditions:

TERR_CONT (Territorial context of the initiative) * REL_CSO (Existence of structured relations with CSO) * BOTTOM-UP (Integration of bottom-up perspectives) * G+_CONSID (Inclusion of gender+ considerations in “response”) * G+_INCLUS (Gender+ inclusiveness of community engagement)

Solution term in the standard analysis:

TERR_CONT*REL_CSO*BOTTOM-UP*G+_CONSID* G+_INCLUS	Raw coverage	Consistency
	1	1

Solution coverage: 1 (All cases with a positive outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 1 (All cases included in the solution have a positive outcome)

This solution suggests that the achievement of the outcome can be linked to a single solution term: 1. Initiatives that focus on rural areas, have a structured relationship with CSOs, are based on a bottom-up approach and take gender+ into account in defining responses and engaging communities.

As can be seen from the consistency value (=1), the combination of these five conditions is only present in the three initiatives with a positive outcome. In contrast, the cases with a

negative result each show a different combination, with a maximum of three of the conditions considered being present (see the relative truth table in the appendix). Finally, it is worth noting that the BOTTOM-UP condition seems to be particularly relevant to the solution, as it is only present in initiatives with a positive outcome.

This is confirmed by the analysis of the combinations characterising the cases that do not achieve the strongest impact. In these cases, initiatives lack a bottom-up approach and are predominantly urban or peri-urban. The absence of a structural integration of social professionals is also highlighted by the following solution. This second solution is characterised by two solution terms, both of which focus on the lack of a bottom-up approach.

SOLUTION 2 – Leading to non-outcome TOP-DOWN INITIATIVES IN URBAN CONTEXTS

Analysed conditions:

TERR_CONT (Territorial context of the initiative) * SOC_PROFES (Structural embedding of social professions in the initiative) * BOTTOM-UP (Integration of bottom-up perspectives)

Solution terms in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
~SOC_PROFES*~ BOTTOM-UP	0.857143	1
~ TERR_CONT*~ BOTTOM-UP	0.428571	1

Solution coverage: 1 (All cases with a negative outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 1 (All cases included in the solution have a negative outcome)

This solution suggests that the failure in achieving the outcome can be linked to this two largely overlapping solution terms: 1. Initiatives without a bottom-up perspective and without a structural embedding of social professions; 2. Initiatives located mainly in urban or peri-urban areas and without a bottom-up perspective.

A pathway to WEAK_IMP

As mentioned above, a second, weaker outcome was also defined, in which a positive result is achieved in initiatives where significant efforts have nonetheless been made to consider local knowledge in civil protection responses.

The analysis carried out in this framework seems to confirm the relevance of two conditions already present in the stronger outcome, namely rural contexts and gender+ inclusiveness of community engagement. It also shows the importance of a simple institutional structure, i.e. with the intervention of only one administrative level.

SOLUTION 3 – SIMPLE AND INCLUSIVE INITIATIVES IN RURAL AREAS

Analysed conditions:

TERR_CONT (Territorial context of the initiative) * AUTH_CONST (Levels of public authorities that are involved) * G+_INCLUS (Gender+ inclusiveness of community engagement)

Solution terms in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
TERR_CONT*G+_INCLUS	0.714286	0.833333
TERR_CONT*~AUTH_CONST	0.714286	0.833333

Solution coverage: 0.86 (6 of the 7 cases with a positive outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 0.86 (6 of the 7 cases included in the solution have a positive outcome)

This solution suggests that the achievement of the outcome can be linked to these two largely overlapping solution terms: 1. Initiatives that focus on rural areas and adopt gender+ approaches in engaging communities; 2. Initiatives focusing on rural areas and involving only one level of public administration.

Interpretation

The QCA analysis focused specifically on the capacity of authorities to engage with local knowledge in preparing for and responding to natural hazards, thereby strengthening their effectiveness in disaster management. Another key research question within RL1 focused on the extent to which authorities incorporate gender+ and intersectional components in their approaches. This related aspect was used in the QCA process as the basis for identifying two factors that were analysed for their potential contribution to the outcome.

Overall, the results of the QCA analysis largely confirm the findings of RL1, while also offering a few additional insights and clarifying the relevance of certain factors and their combinations, as highlighted below.

The RL1 report identifies the incorporation of local knowledge into disaster management as linked to the inclusion of **bottom-up perspectives** in the preparedness approach and the presence of structured relationships with **civil society organisations**. It also highlights the importance of adopting a **gender+** and intersectional perspective.

- QCA results suggest that when a structured incorporation of local knowledge into civil protection responses takes place (STRONG_IMP) all the four key factors of the analysis are simultaneously present: the integration of bottom-up perspectives, the existence of structured relations with CSOs, the inclusion of gender+ considerations in disaster response and the gender+ inclusiveness of community engagement (Solution 1). This particularly strong result adds weight to the identified factors and, above all, to the need for their combination (no initiative that lacked one of these elements achieved the outcome).
- The initiatives that did not achieve the stronger outcome (Solution 2) are also worth considering. On one hand, they support the importance of the inclusion of bottom-up perspectives, which were consistently absent in those that failed to achieve impact. On the other hand, they highlight the lack of other factors that support integration and inclusiveness among different social actors (no involvement of social professionals) and further confirm the significance of the urban-rural divide (see next point).

Another finding highlighted in the RL1 report is the difference in how inclusive, participatory dynamics unfold in **rural vs urban areas**. In urban contexts, the local knowledge and expertise of citizens tend to be more difficult to validate and incorporate into civil protection processes.

- The QCA emphasises this difference, highlighting the placement of inclusive and bottom-up initiatives in rural areas and the location of initiatives without a bottom-up perspective in urban or peri-urban areas.
- This is confirmed both in situations where a strong impact has been achieved, through the structural integration of local knowledge (Solution 1), and in those where a “weaker” impact is observed, in which integration is not yet structural, but there are ongoing efforts in that direction. In the second case, the rural character of the setting even appears to be the strongest factor contributing to the achievement of the impact (Solution 3). The differing dynamics of community-based disaster management in urban and rural contexts certainly warrant further analysis. These differences may be linked to the distinct relationship rural communities have with their territories, which tends to support the emergence of grassroots initiatives, but also to the contrasting ways in which public authorities deliver services in each context.

A final observation concerns the impact of the authorities' structure on the achievement of the outcome.

- The QCA highlights the importance of a streamlined structure: regardless of whether they are in urban or rural settings, initiatives involving only a single level of public administration appear more likely to incorporate local knowledge into civil protection responses. This finding was particularly evident in initiatives that achieved a more limited impact (Solution 3) and warrants further investigation.

Limitations

The main limitation of applying QCA to the results of RL1 is the very small number of initiatives analysed (ten). Although this falls within the validity limits established for QCA (Schneider & Wagemann 2010), it has inevitably constrained the number of factors that could be tested.

Another limitation lies in the significant heterogeneity of the authorities across the cases analysed. In eight cases, the authority consists of a set of public (and sometimes private) bodies with responsibilities within a defined territorial area, while the remaining two are civil protection-related projects. Given that the outcomes selected for the QCA relate to the integration of local and traditional knowledge in disaster preparedness and management, this variability may have influenced the results.

A third limitation is the diversity of natural hazards considered across the ten cases, which goes beyond the condition we used to distinguish single or multiple hazard cases, ranging from forest fires and landslides to floods and heatwaves, each presenting specific opportunities and challenges for the incorporation of local and traditional knowledge.

Considering the second and third limitations together, a broader reflection emerges. While QCA requires a certain level of case diversity to enable meaningful comparison, excessive diversity can undermine the validity of the analysis. This reflects the principle of balancing

case diversity with comparability (Schneider & Wagemann, 2012). The diversity among the RL1 cases is at the borderline of meaningful comparability.

A final limitation relates to the strength of the empirical base: in many cases, the number of in-depth interviews conducted was fewer than five, with an overall range from two to fourteen.

2.2 QCA report for RL2: Biodiversity and land use restrictions

Objectives of the study

Research line 2 explores human behaviour in relation to biodiversity and protected (or ecologically valuable) areas, with a particular focus on how land-use restrictions for biodiversity conservation intersect with the socio-economic needs of vulnerable groups, analysed through a gender+ lens. The second research cycle centres on settings where individuals and groups actively come together to care for nature. It aims to **understand how communities, families, and individuals in vulnerable contexts engage in environmental stewardship** and what drives individual and collective change towards more sustainable behaviour.⁵

Outcome identification

In the context of the QCA exercise, the outcome of the local environmental initiatives analysed within RL2 has been defined as their **ability to create a space for negotiation between authorities and citizens, thereby gaining legitimacy as interlocutors on local environmental issues**.

To determine whether each initiative had a positive or negative outcome, three main sources of information were considered. First, interviews with the promoters provided insights into the initiatives' goals, missions, and perceived impacts across various areas. Second, interviews with individual participants offered a complementary perspective, highlighting their level of engagement and contributions to environmental stewardship. Finally, the country reports prepared by each research team brought together a broader analysis, incorporating findings from both promoter and participant interviews to contextualise the initiatives' overall effects.

Case selection and identification of conditions

Case selection

A total of eleven cases were analysed, predominantly located in rural settings, with one urban case included. The countries involved are Bulgaria, Hungary, Portugal, Romania, and Türkiye. Despite their diversity, the cases can be grouped into two main categories, as shown in Table 5.

⁵ The full RL2 report is authored by Martin Felix Gajdusek (ZSI) and Gabor Szudi (ZSI), in collaboration with Ayşe Gül Altınay (SU), Esin Düzel (SU), Daniela Ferreira (IGOT), Maria Lucinda Fonseca (IGOT), and Oara Prundeanu (UAIC).

Table 5. Types of initiatives considered by type and country within RL2.

INITIATIVE	BG	HU	PT	RO	TK
Pro-nature initiatives focused on ecological restoration and environmental monitoring		XXX	XX	X	
Pro-nature initiatives actively resisting environmentally harmful business or state-led projects, some threatening local livelihoods	XX			X	XX

Identification of conditions

The identification of the conditions to be related to the different outcomes of the initiatives was guided by the main theoretical tenets of ACCTING:

- The notion of socially just environmental transitions
- The centrality of gender+, intersectional perspectives in assessing the inclusivity of pro-nature initiatives
- The key role of vulnerable/disadvantaged communities in environmental transitions
- Valorising local and traditional knowledge through trans-epistemic practices.

On this basis, the following sets of information have been collected and analysed for each initiative:

- **Context and scale of outreach** (urban/rural and local, regional or national outreach)
- **General description of the initiative** (background, aims, activities, timeframe, resources)
- **Characteristics of the promoters and participants** (types of members and vulnerability profile, motivations and deterrents for involvement, including those specific to vulnerable and gender+ groups, knowledge exchange dynamics, women's active engagement, type of leadership, previous activist experiences)
- **Characteristics of the local administration** (environmental stance, level of support or opposition to the initiative)
- **Network of actors** (partnership with public, private, non-profit actors and groups)
- **Impact on environmental behaviour** (transformative change at personal and/or institutional level).

Within these sets, the conditions expected to have the greatest impact on the outcome were selected according to the identified outcome for RL2. Conditions were also selected based on the **number of cases** exhibiting them, as conditions present in all or only a very few cases are not suitable for comparison in QCA analysis. The selected conditions are listed in Table 6.

Table 6. Codes for conditions within RL2.

CODE	CONDITION
RESIST_ACT	Initiatives actively resisting environmentally detrimental projects
URGENT	Urgent nature of the initiative
ADM_PRO_ENV	Pro-environment administration
ADM_SUPPORT	Administration supporting the initiative
ADM_OPPOSE	Administration opposing the initiative
PAST_NEGOT	Previous participation/negotiation channels
TRUST	Citizens' trust in the local administration regarding the initiative
COMMUNITY	Strong sense of community
PROM_EXP	Prior activism experience of the promoters
PROM_LEAD	Strong leadership within the initiative
EXT_SUPPORT	External support of the initiative from other (environmental) organisations
PART_INCENT	Incentives for participants to engage in the initiative
PART_FEAR	Fear of consequences for participants to engage in the initiative
WOMEN	Women's active engagement in the initiative
INCLUSIVE	Inclusion of gender+/vulnerable groups in the initiative
KNOWL	Importance of traditional and local knowledge

Calibration of conditions and outcomes

Applying crisp-set QCA, the available information was reduced to binary systems (0-1), assigning a set membership score to each case and condition. The calibration of the outcome (i.e., the ability to create a space for negotiation between authorities and citizens), was based on the holistic assessment of responses of both promoters and beneficiaries to the in-depth interview guide.

Overall, 6 initiatives in the panel achieved a positive outcome and the other 5 did not (see Table 3, below). A table showing the calibration of the main conditions used in the QCA applied to RL2 is presented in the Appendix.

Truth table construction

A final truth table for each causal configuration that was identified ("solution") was produced according to the procedure described in the Appendix, where the truth tables are also presented. As will be explained in the next sections, the solutions analysed in this context are based on the following three combinations of conditions.

4. ADM_PRO_ENV * PROM_EXP * PROM_LEAD

5. URGENT * PAST_NEGOT * PROM_EXP * PART_FEAR
6. KNOWL * WOMEN * PROM_EXP

Based on the combinations observed in the panel, it was possible to perform a "Standard analysis" for each solution using the fsQCA software, the results of which are presented in the following section.

Identification of causal configurations

The distribution of the ten cases by country and **outcome** is shown in Table 7 (for a more detailed description of the panel, see the RL2 report).

Table 7. RL2 panel by country and outcome.

CODE	Cases with a positive outcome	Cases with a negative outcome
Bulgaria	0	2
Hungary	2	1
Portugal	2	0
Romania	1	1
Türkiye	1	1
Total	6	5

As mentioned in Section 2.2, the outcome was defined for the QCA analysis as the ability of the initiatives to create a space for negotiation between authorities and citizens, thereby gaining legitimacy as interlocutors on local environmental issues.

Different combinations of conditions were tested to explore their relation to the outcome. The results are described below.

*Different combinations of conditions were tested to explore their relationship with the outcomes, starting with those more related to the ACCTING theoretical approaches, and then broadening the scope to test additional combinations. **It is important to note** that QCA aims to identify combinations of conditions, so it may well be that conditions that are highly relevant in a binary correlation do not produce robust results when combined with others, i.e. are not critical in identifying consistent patterns or individual profiles that lead to an outcome.*

The first finding highlights the importance of a shared pro-environmental stance between the administration and the initiative, which helps establish a basis for dialogue, especially when the groups involved also demonstrate strong leadership and prior experience in similar activist causes.

SOLUTION 1 – KEY ROLE OF SUPPORTIVE CONTEXTS AND ACTIVIST EXPERIENCE

Analysed conditions:

ADM_PRO_ENV (Pro-environment administration) * PROM_EXP (Prior activism experience of the promoters) * PROM_LEAD (Strong leadership within the initiative)

Solution term in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
ADM_PRO_ENV *PROM_EXP	0.67	1
PROM_EXP*PROM_LEAD	0.83	1

Solution coverage: 1 (All cases with a positive outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 1 (All cases included in the solution have a positive outcome)

This solution indicates that successful outcomes are associated with two solution terms: 1. The presence of a pro-environmental administration in the area where the initiative takes place, combined with promoters' prior activist experience in similar causes; 2. Promoters with prior activist experience who also provide consistent, strong leadership.

All cases that achieved a positive outcome and managed to establish a space for negotiation with the authorities share a combination of three conditions. Among these, the promoters' **prior activist experience** (PROM_EXP) stands out as the only factor present in all positive-outcome cases, with only one exception. This suggests that prior experience in similar causes is a key enabler for citizens to be recognised as legitimate interlocutors and to engage effectively with authorities on local environmental issues. Indeed, the same factor also appears in all solutions associated with the outcome.

The second solution includes two pathways combining four conditions and emphasises the importance of the initiative's timeframe.

SOLUTION 2 – FACILITATING CONSTRUCTIVE ENGAGEMENT AND NEGOTIATION: THE ROLE OF TIME AND SENSE OF SECURITY

Analysed conditions:

URGENT (Urgent nature of the initiative) * PAST_NEGOT (Prior participation/negotiation channels) * PROM_EXP (Prior activism experience of the promoters) * PART_FEAR (Fear of consequences for participants to engage in the initiative)

Solution term in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
~URGENT*PROM_EXP*~PART_FEAR	0.83	1
~URGENT*PAST_NEGOT* PROM_EXP	0.83	1

Solution coverage: 1 (All cases with a positive outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 1 (All cases included in the solution have a positive outcome)

This solution indicates that positive outcomes are associated with two solution terms: 1. Non-urgent initiatives, led by promoters with prior activist experience, where participants do not fear consequences for their engagement in the activities of the initiatives; 2. Non-urgent initiatives, with previously established participation channels between authorities and citizens, and led by promoters with prior activist experience.

All cases with positive outcomes are not responses to imminent environmental threats, but rather longer-standing movements formed earlier to address various pro-environmental issues in the area. This **extended timeframe** has allowed for the development of more stable negotiation channels with authorities, which appear crucial for achieving positive outcomes. Additionally, the second solution shows that participants in most positive-outcome initiatives feel safe engaging in the movement, without fearing repercussions.

The third and final pathway for creating a space for negotiation between authorities and citizens highlights the importance of the promoters' values and membership composition.

SOLUTION 3 – THE SYNERGY OF LOCAL KNOWLEDGE, WOMEN'S ENGAGEMENT, AND ACTIVIST EXPERIENCE

Analysed conditions:

KNOWL (Importance of traditional knowledge) * WOMEN (Women's active engagement in the initiative) * PROM_EXP (Prior activism experience of the promoters)

Solution term in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
KNOWL*PROM_EXP	0.83	0.83
WOMEN* PROM_EXP	0.5	1

Solution coverage: 1 (All cases with a positive outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 0.86 (6 out of the 7 cases included in the solution have a positive outcome)

Positive outcomes are linked to two key solution terms: 1. Initiatives that emphasise traditional local knowledge and are led by promoters with prior activist experience; 2. Initiatives with active women's participation, also led by experienced promoters.

While women's active engagement in the initiatives is not a sufficient condition for positive outcomes – being present in half of such cases – and the valuing of traditional/local knowledge is widespread across both initiatives with positive and negative outcomes, these factors become particularly influential when combined with promoters' prior activist experience. In this configuration, they contribute significantly to the achievement of positive outcomes.

Interpretation

The QCA applied to RL2 was designed not only to validate the final RL2 research report's conclusions but also to generate fresh insights that deepen and enrich the findings. Specifically, it focused on an outcome the report did not explicitly examine, namely the initiatives' capacity to create a space for negotiation between authorities and citizens, thereby earning legitimacy as interlocutors on local environmental issues.

Although the RL2 report identified other meaningful impacts – such as heightened environmental awareness among participants, strengthened social cohesion at the community level and contributions to policy advocacy at the systemic level – these were, in some cases, incorporated into the QCA as explanatory conditions rather than as the primary outcome under investigation.

Regarding the **timeframe** of the analysed initiatives, one finding of the RL2 report is that immediate environmental threats often push individuals into action, leaving little choice but to engage. Many participants are motivated by a sense of urgency, systemic failures, or corruption affecting local livelihoods.

- Although urgency-driven initiatives spark engagement, they do not lead to successful negotiation outcomes. Indeed, the QCA reveals that positive results stem from **longer-standing initiatives** that have leveraged their extended timeframe to establish previous dialogue channels with authorities and draw upon promoters' prior activist experience. In these initiatives, participants feel secure and unafraid of consequences (Solution 2).

- Moreover, the QCA findings show the importance of a **shared pro-environmental stance** between administrations and initiative promoters, particularly when paired with strong leadership and prior activist experience. These combinations support constructive engagement and help overcome institutional barriers (Solution 1).

The central **role of women** as leaders and change agents stands out throughout the RL2 findings. Women actively influence decision-making and challenge traditional norms, often becoming role models who inspire others and promote inclusive participation.

- QCA analysis indicates that while women's engagement alone is not sufficient, its combination with prior activist experience contributes to the creation of effective negotiation spaces (Solution 3).

Finally, the RL2 report emphasises the importance of **diverse forms of knowledge** – including intergenerational, experiential, and intangible knowledge – shared through bi-directional exchanges within and across communities. Knowledge fosters empowerment and deepens care for nature.

- The value of traditional local knowledge is confirmed by the QCA analysis as a contributing factor to the success of initiatives. Especially when paired with experienced movements, it becomes a key driver of positive outcomes. The ability to draw on long-standing, culturally rooted knowledge enhances the legitimacy of initiatives and supports the creation of spaces for negotiation (Solution 3).

Limitations

The main limitation of applying QCA to the results of RL2 lies in the significant diversity of the cases analysed. The initiatives ranged from resistance movements actively opposing environmentally harmful projects to initiatives focused on ecological restoration and environmental monitoring. These broad differences in aims, strategies, and forms of engagement with authorities have added complexity to the analysis and made pattern identification more challenging.

Another limitation relates to the multiplicity of administrative levels involved in individual cases. Several initiatives interacted with more than one tier of government, with some administrations showing support and others expressing opposition. This divergence within a single institutional context made it difficult to evaluate the role of local authorities as a uniform factor across cases.

In addition, some factors identified as central in the RL2 report – such as the power of solidarity and sense of community – were present in nearly all cases, regardless of outcome. Their prevalence across the board reduced their ability to discriminate between successful and unsuccessful initiatives in the QCA analysis, even though these elements were clearly recognised in the report as essential enablers of action. Similarly, many initiatives had developed wider alliances beyond the local level, including connections with national or international networks. While these alliances played a critical role in amplifying local voices and resources, their widespread presence meant that they did not emerge as differentiating factors in the QCA.

Finally, another important limitation concerns the focus on socially excluded groups. While all initiatives were situated in vulnerable settings, only a limited number significantly included groups with marked vulnerability profiles – such as migrants or economically disadvantaged individuals. As the RL2 report shows, the participation of these groups is often hindered by systemic barriers – limited mobility, economic precarity, fear of job loss, and ongoing social exclusion. These structural constraints, while central to the RL2 focus, were difficult to fully capture in the QCA due to their limited presence and variation across the cases.

2.3 QCA report for RL3: Energy communities, energy poverty and community energy schemes

Objectives of the study

Research line 3 aims to understand how municipalities and regional authorities can support the establishment and growth of energy communities, conceived as a tool to tackle the problem of energy poverty, and facilitate the active participation of vulnerable groups.

In the second cycle⁶, the research team set out to answer the following questions:

- What variables influence the outcome of energy community projects involving vulnerable individuals and aiming at reducing energy costs?
- What variables in communities influence the behaviour of individuals who promote or join and participate in energy communities that reduce energy poverty?

Outcome identification

The outcome selected for the QCA analysis of RL3 relates to the second question above and is applied to the individual participants in the energy communities/initiatives. It was defined as **an increase in environmental awareness and the adoption of more sustainable energy consumption behaviours** associated with participation in the Energy Community.

In order to attribute a positive or negative outcome, the main sources of information were the interviews with the individual participants in the energy communities, which provide direct access to their personal circumstances, motivations, environmental practices and outcomes. The interviews with the promoters of the initiatives were also used to integrate contextual information. Finally, the country-specific reports compiled by each research team provided supplementary information that helped characterise the individual energy communities and informed the assignment of outcomes and conditions.

Case selection and identification of conditions

Case selection

A total of 20 cases (individuals) participating in five energy communities/initiatives were included in the analysis. The countries involved are Denmark, Italy and Norway. The initiatives are shown in Table 8, while the participants per initiative are shown in Table 10 below (Section 9.6).

⁶ The full RL3 report is authored by Pariman Boostani (NTNU), in collaboration with Marina Cacace (K&I), Giuseppe Pellegrini Masini (NTNU), Francesca Pugliese (K&I), Gabriele Quinti (K&I), Kenneth Vilhelmsen (NTNU).

Table 8. Types of initiatives considered by type and country within RL3.

Type of initiative	Country	Funding	Vulnerability profiles
Renovations and energy up-grade of an apartment building	Norway	Public	Low income, ethnicity, old age, disability
Ecovillage	Norway	Public-private-not for-profit partnership	Low income, old age
Social housing energy community	Denmark	Public-private-not for-profit partnership	Low income, migration background
Energy and solidarity community	Italy	Self-funding by community members	Low-income
Energy and solidarity community	Italy	Self-funding by community members	Low-income

Identification of conditions

The identification of the conditions to be related to the different outcomes of the initiatives was guided by the main theoretical tenets of ACCTING:

- The notion of socially just environmental transitions
- The centrality of gender+, intersectional perspectives in assessing the inclusivity of energy communities and initiatives
- The identification of priority target groups through multidimensional vulnerability approaches
- The key role of vulnerable/disadvantaged communities in environmental transitions.

On this basis, the following sets of information have been collected and analysed for each respondent:

- **Socio-demographic characteristics** (e.g., sex, age, education, income, employment position, migration status)
- **Vulnerability conditions** (e.g., gender⁷, old age, disability, ethnicity/racial, religion/belief, language)
- **Energy poverty profile**
- **Motivations for joining the initiative/energy community** (social, environmental, financial, policy incentives, other individual circumstances, other reasons) and expectations
- **Trust in the project and project leadership** (inclusive atmosphere, diversity of staff, barriers for people in vulnerable conditions, support received by family and friends, etc.)
- **Degree of activism** in participation in the initiative and barriers (including the level of information sharing from the leadership)
- **Intention to change behaviour** in energy consumption.

⁷ Gender includes vulnerability conditions related to gender, gender identity and sexual orientation.

Within these sets, the conditions expected to have the greatest impact on the outcome (more sustainable energy consumption behaviour) were selected according to the theoretical framework and research question of RL3. Conditions were also selected based on the **number of cases** exhibiting them, as conditions present in all or only a very few cases are not suitable for comparison in QCA analysis. The selected conditions are listed in Table 9.

Table 9. Codes for conditions within RL3.

CODE	CONDITION
SEX	Woman/Man/Nonbinary
AGE	Vulnerability condition: Old age
MIGR	Vulnerability condition: Migrant background
DSB	Vulnerability condition: Disability impacting mobility
SEC	Vulnerability condition: Low socio-economic background
MOTIV_ENV	Environmental motivations for joining the initiative
MOTIV_SOC	Social motivations for joining the initiative (e.g. supporting community projects or more vulnerable people)
MOTIV_EC	Economic motivations for joining the initiative
MOTIV_EXT	No personal motivation but external reason for joining the initiative (e.g. related to a public policy for social housing)
SOC_COHES	Perception of social cohesion strengthened by the initiative
ACT_PART	Active participation in the initiative
CAP_BUIL	Capacity building (environmental awareness and energy-saving practices)
TRUST_LEA	Trust in the leadership of the initiative
TRUST_PROJ	Trust in the project planning and results

Calibration of conditions and outcomes

To proceed with crisp-set calibration, the available information was reduced to binary systems (0-1), assigning a set membership score to each case and condition.

The calibration of the outcome (i.e., the increase in environmental awareness and the adoption of more sustainable energy consumption behaviours) was based on the holistic assessment of the responses of the 20 beneficiaries to the in-depth interview guide. Overall, 12 respondents in the panel achieved a positive outcome and the other 8 did not (see Table 3, below). A table showing the calibration of the main conditions used in the QCA applied to RL3 is presented in the Appendix.

Truth table construction

A final truth table for each causal configuration that was identified (“solution”) was produced according to the procedure described in the Appendix, where the truth tables are also presented. As will be explained in the next sections, the solutions analysed in this context are based on the following four combinations of conditions.

1. SOC_COHES * CAP_BUIL * ACT_PART * MOTIV_ENV
2. MOTIV_ENV * ACT_PART * TRUST_LEA

3. MOTIV_ENV * MOTIV_SOC * MOTIV_EC
4. SEC * MOTIV_EXT * CAP_BUIL

Based on the combinations observed in the panel, it was possible to perform a "Standard analysis" for each solution using the fsQCA software, the results of which are presented in the following section.

Identification of causal configurations

Our panel consists of 20 individuals from the five initiatives included in the analysis (Table 2, above). Their distribution by country and outcome is shown in Table 10 (for a more detailed description of the panel, see the RL3 report).

Table 10. RL3 panel by country, gender* and outcome (absolute values).

	Women	Men	Total	POSITIVE OUT- COME
Denmark	1	/	1	1
Italy	6	2	8	6
Norway	9	2	11	5
Total	16	4	20	12

* The panel didn't include nonbinary persons.

As mentioned in Section 3.2, the outcome was defined for the QCA analysis as **an increase in environmental awareness and the adoption of more sustainable energy consumption behaviours** associated with participation in the Energy Community.

Different combinations of conditions were tested to explore their relation to the outcome. The results are described below.

*Different combinations of conditions were tested to explore their relationship with the outcomes, starting with those more related to the ACCTING theoretical approaches, and then broadening the scope to test additional combinations. **It is important to note** that QCA aims to identify combinations of conditions, so it may well be that conditions that are highly relevant in a binary correlation do not produce robust results when combined with others, i.e. are not critical in identifying consistent patterns or individual profiles that lead to an outcome.*

Pathways to the outcome

In our panel, the vast majority of participants who achieved a positive outcome (10 out of 12) share the set of conditions described in the first solution.

SOLUTION 1 – Environmental motivation and active participation, supported by the initiative

Analysed conditions:

MOTIV_ENV (Environmental motivation to join the initiative) * ACT_PART (Active participation in the initiative) * CAP_BUIL (Capacity building) * SOC_COHES (Social cohesion, strengthened by the initiative)

Solution term in the standard analysis:

Raw coverage

Consistency

MOTIV_ENV*ACT_PART*CAP_BUIL	0.666667	1
MOTIV_ENV*ACT_PART*SOC_COHES	0.666667	1

Solution coverage: 0.83 (10 out of 12 cases with a positive outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 1 (All cases included in the solution have a positive outcome)

This solution suggests that the achievement of the outcome can be linked to two largely overlapping solution terms: 1. Participants with environmental motivations, actively participating in the initiative, and receiving capacity building (environmental awareness and energy-saving practices); 2. Participants with environmental motivations, actively participating in the initiative, and perceiving social cohesion, strengthened by the initiative.

In this solution, **personal** characteristics like environmental motivation and agency for active participation combine with **structural** characteristics of the initiatives, such as the provision of opportunities for participation and capacity building, and with characteristics of the **social environment**, such as the existence of a community with a certain degree of cohesion, able to commit to a common endeavour.

Another strong combination blending personal and initiative-related factors puts an emphasis on people's **trust in the leaders of the initiatives** (solution 2).

SOLUTION 2 – Motivation and active participation, supported by the initiative

Analysed conditions:

MOTIV_ENV (Environmental motivation to join the initiative) * ACT_PART (Active participation in the initiative) * TRUST_LEA (Trust in the leaders of the initiative)

Solution term in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
MOTIV_ENV*ACT_PART*TRUST_LEA	1	0.923077

Solution coverage: 1 (All cases with a positive outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 0.92 (12 out of 13 cases included in the solution have a positive outcome)

This solution suggests that the achievement of the outcome can be linked to a single solution term: 1. Participants with environmental motivations, actively participating in the initiative, and trusting the leaders of the initiative.

This clear solution underscores the importance of trust in the promoters of the initiatives, which is particularly significant in this domain given the highly technical nature of many aspects involved, both at the technological and regulatory levels.

Pathways to no outcome

Useful information can also be derived by looking at the most common patterns that lead to no outcome (no significant improvement in awareness and behaviour regarding energy consumption).

Some first indications (Solution 3) come from looking at the motivational side of participants, where the results seem to suggest that in our panel economic motivations are not the ones that led to change. At least not when they are not combined with other motivational drivers (such as environmental and social motivations).

SOLUTION 3 – Leading to non-outcome

ECONOMIC MOTIVATIONS ALONE ARE NOT ENOUGH

Analysed conditions:

MOTIV_ENV (Environmental motivations) * MOTIV_SOC (Social motivations) * MOTIV_EC (Economic motivations)

Solution term in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
~MOTIV_ENV*~MOTIV_SOC*MOTIV_EC	0.875	1

Solution coverage: 0.88 (7 out of 8 cases with a negative outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 1 (All cases included in the solution have a negative outcome)

This solution suggests that the failure in achieving the outcome can be linked to a solution term including: 1. Predominant economic motivations for joining the initiative, in the absence of significant environmental or social motivations.

A second combination leading to no outcome enriches this result by focusing on the socio-economic background of the participant and a feature of the initiative itself, confirming the relevance of capacity building, particularly when people from lower socio-economic backgrounds are involved (Solution 4).

SOLUTION 4 – Leading to non-outcome:

BUILDING CAPACITY IS ESSENTIAL FOR POORER PEOPLE TO BE ABLE TO CHANGE

Analysed conditions:

SEC (Low socio-economic background) * MOTIV_EXT (External motivations) * CAP_BUIL (Capacity building on energy-saving practices)

Solution term in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
SEC*MOTIV_EXT*~CAP_BUIL	0.75	0.857143

Solution coverage: 0.75 (6 out of 8 cases with a negative outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 0.86 (6 out of 7 cases included in the solution have a negative outcome)

This solution suggests that the failure in achieving the outcome can be linked to a solution term including: 1. Low socio-economic background, no personal motivation but 'external' reasons to join the initiative, and lack of capacity building (environmental awareness and energy-saving practices) provided by the initiative.

Looking in more detail, all the cases with a negative outcome in this solution come from an initiative in Norway (renovation and energy upgrade of an apartment building), where the energy community was set up by the municipal authorities in a social housing building. However, external motivation does not necessarily dictate the outcome, as two other participants from the same initiative show a positive outcome. The difference with the others is their strong environmental motivation.

Interpretation

The QCA analysis within RL3 focused on one of the outcomes that were investigated within the Research Line. The outcome was assigned to individual participants in the energy communities/initiatives and related to the **increase in environmental awareness and the adoption of more sustainable energy consumption behaviours** associated with their participation in the initiatives.

The QCA generally confirmed the findings of RL3 and in a few cases provided additional insights. Although the QCA has focused on individual participants, in some cases it was able to provide clues about the characteristics of the initiatives that are associated with a positive or negative outcome.

One finding from the RL3 report is that the biggest enabler of behavioural change for vulnerable individuals was **knowledge**, which includes awareness, experiences, know-how, and information.

- The QCA analysis confirms this finding through the relevance of the factor related to the capacity building offered by some of the initiatives (CAP_BUIL), which appeared in combinations leading to positive outcomes (Solution 1); however, the relevance of this factor appears even more clearly in combinations leading to no outcome, when no capacity building was offered and participants from lower socio-economic backgrounds (SEC) were involved (Solution 4).

Another finding highlighted in the RL3 report is that many vulnerable people expressed **trust** in those leading the energy communities or initiatives, which supported their involvement.

- Trust (TRUST_LEA) also emerged as a relevant factor in the QCA analysis (Solution 2). In addition, QCA specifies that it is not trust alone, but a combination of trust, environmental motivation to participate (MOTIV_ENV) and active participation (ACT_PART) that are associated with awareness and behaviour change.

The importance of **fostering strong community ties and empowering residents** to actively participate in the management of initiatives is repeatedly highlighted in the RL3 report. **Pro-environmental attitudes** are also highlighted as drivers of change.

- In QCA, the combination of social cohesion (SOC_COHES) and active participation (ACT_PART) is part of a profile consistently associated with a positive outcome, but with the specification that an environmental motivational component (MOTIV_ENV) should be included (Solution 1).

As concerns **economic motivations**, the RL3 report stresses the relevance of financial considerations to join energy communities/initiatives in vulnerable communities.

- The QCA results complement this finding by showing that in our panel, economic motivations alone do not appear to be sufficient to trigger change among those who actually participate in energy communities/initiatives. Purely economic motivations appear in the profiles of people who show a negative outcome when they are combined with the lack of environmental and social motivations (solution 3).
- A partially related finding concerns those cases where there is no specific motivation, so that participation in an energy initiative depends only on an external reason (e.g., related to a public policy for social housing: MOTIV_EXT). In these cases, it is not surprising that the outcome of increased awareness and personal change is difficult

to achieve, especially when participants come from lower socio-economic backgrounds (SEC) and no capacity-building initiatives are offered (CAP_BUIL).

Limitations

The main limitation of applying QCA to the results of RL3 was that the research tools were mostly designed for an assessment at the level of the initiatives (which were ultimately not sufficient for a QCA application), while the information available on individual participants, although rich, was less comprehensive.

Another limitation is related to the difficulty in assessing the outcome by establishing clear thresholds in terms of the increase in awareness when participants reported already having pro-environmental attitudes before they joined the initiative. Similarly, improved energy-saving practices were sometimes difficult to clearly assess in the case of the most disadvantaged participants. They reported extreme energy-saving measures that could be more related to their pre-existing energy poverty habits than to their increased awareness and participation in the project.

Finally, comparisons between the behaviours and outcomes of women and men didn't yield significant results. This is probably due to the gender imbalance in the panel (16 out of 20 participants were women).

2.4 QCA report for RL4: Intensifying the adoption of energy-efficiency and pro-environmental measures in micro/small SMEs

Objectives of the study

Research line 4 focuses on the role that micro-entrepreneurs can play in the transition process towards environmental sustainability. In fact, many SMEs (and even more micro-enterprises led by people in vulnerable situations) are excluded from this process, both because those who run them often have little or no awareness of climate change issues, and because – if they do – they face multiple obstacles (lack of resources and skills, lack of incentives and support from third parties, etc.).

In the second cycle, RL4 focuses on how the most vulnerable entrepreneurs change their behaviour in the management of their enterprises, and more generally, towards climate change mitigation in relation to the planning and adoption of pro-environmental measures, and what are the enabling and the hindering factors in this process.⁸

Outcome identification

The outcomes of RL4 are analysed at the level of the micro-entrepreneurs. This means that, considering the size of the micro-enterprises, the cases correspond to individual respondents. These are vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs who have initiated (or at least planned) a change process to improve their business's environmental sustainability. From this perspective, the outcome was considered positive if, despite their vulnerability, such entrepreneurs were able to successfully make their business (more) environmentally sustainable.

In order to assign a positive or negative outcome to the cases analysed, the following **criteria** have to be met:

- **Significant investments/expenditures** (i.e., an expenditure that is not routine but needs to be planned; that requires foregoing or deferring other expenditures; and that is then spread over time) have been made in environmental sustainability, relative to the size and purpose of the business.
- An **integrated/multiple approach** to environmental sustainability has been adopted (taking measures in several areas, e.g., photovoltaic systems, sustainable materials, changing light bulbs, waste sorting or recycling)
- Environmental actions are not one-off, but an **ongoing or established process**.

For each of the three criteria, scores were assigned based on achievement:

- a score = 2 if positive
- a score = 1 if partial/weak
- a score = 0 if negative.

⁸ The full RL4 report is authored by Gabriele Quinti, Francesca Pugliese (K&I), Alain Denis, Aart Kerremans (YW), Giuseppe Pellegrini Masini, Kenneth Vilhelmsen (NTNU), Vassilis Chatzibirros, Christos Stergiadis (SEERC), Andrei Holman, Simona Popusoi (UAIC).

These scores were summed, and the outcome was considered achieved if the total score was equal to or greater than 4, which represents the value immediately above the midpoint between the minimum and maximum values (the sum could vary from 0 to 6).

Case selection and identification of conditions

Case selection

The 21 case studies, each corresponding to a vulnerable micro-entrepreneur and their business, are distributed in different areas of five European countries:

- Liège, Antwerp and Brussels (Belgium)
- Thessaloniki (Greece)
- Rome (Italy)
- Trondheim (Norway)
- Iași (Romania)

These entrepreneurs have embarked on a path towards environmental sustainability by adopting or at least designing measures to improve the sustainability of their business. Table 11 gives an overview of the cases selected by economic activity. While the total number of cases is 21, the number of economic sectors is higher, as some entrepreneurs are active in more than one.

Table 11. Economic sectors covered by the micro-enterprises per country within RL4.

ECONOMIC SECTORS OF ACTIVITY	BELGIUM	GREECE	ITALY	NORWAY	ROMANIA	TOTAL
Hotels/B&B	1	1	-	-	-	2
Food service (restaurant, bar, pub, bakery)	1	1	3	2	3	10
Culture (e.g., bookshop), environmental products, and Leisure	1	-	1	1	1	4
Textile/fashion	2	-	1	-	-	3
Handcrafted products (including jewellery)	1	2	-	-	-	3
Retailers (e.g., plastic, electrical installations)	-	-	-	1	1	2

The micro-entrepreneurs have been selected following the ACCTING gender+ intersectional perspective. Going into the specific vulnerability grounds:

- All the micro-entrepreneurs involved are vulnerable under the social class profile
- 2 out of 3 micro-entrepreneurs involved are migrants
- Almost 2 out of 3 micro-entrepreneurs are women
- 1 in 7 of the micro-entrepreneurs are subject to forms of political, ethnic and/or religious discrimination
- LGBTQ+ status (2 respondents), language (4) and geographical location (1) are the other vulnerability criteria considered.

Identification of conditions

The identification of conditions to be related to the transition process towards environmental sustainability was guided by the main theoretical tenets of ACCTING:

- The notion of socially just environmental transitions
- The key role of vulnerable/disadvantaged communities in managing environmental transitions
- The centrality of gender+, intersectional perspectives in assessing the challenges of the transition process of vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs.

On this basis, the following sets of information have been collected and analysed for each respondent:

- **Background of the micro-entrepreneurs** (gender, age, living situation, vulnerability profile, family, education, attitude towards the environment, work experience, how they became micro-entrepreneurs, etc.)
- **Main characteristics and history of the micro-enterprise** (product/service, turnover, when it was founded, how it has developed and possible crises, etc.)
- **Actors within the enterprise** (employees, associates and, if relevant, their vulnerability profile)
- **External actors**, relations with them and possible benefits (clients, consultants, networks/cooperation arrangements, business associations, ESCos, NGOs, local authorities, etc.)
- **Path towards environmental sustainability:**
 - o Actions undertaken or designed
 - o Motivations (What made you want to adopt more sustainable practices in your company? What made you want to change?)
 - o Satisfaction level (with the process of change)
 - o Opportunities/support encountered in moving towards environmental sustainability
 - o Obstacles/difficulties encountered in moving towards environmental sustainability and how they have been/are being addressed
- **Behavioural change** (if any):
 - o Of the micro-entrepreneur in the management of the micro-enterprise, in relation to environmental issues
 - o Of the micro-entrepreneur in everyday life, in relation to environmental issues
 - o Of the associates/employees, in relation to environmental issues
- **Perception of the adopted environmental sustainability** measures by customers and other external actors.

Within these sets, the conditions expected to have the greatest impact on the outcome (the adoption of pro-environmental measures) were selected according to the theoretical framework and research question of RL4. Conditions were also selected based on the **number of cases** exhibiting them, as conditions present in all or only a very few cases are not suitable for comparison in QCA analysis. The selected conditions are listed in Table 12.

Table 12. Codes for conditions within RL4.

CODE	CONDITION
SEX	Women/Men/Nonbinary
GENDER	Vulnerability condition: Gender
EDU	Level of education
MIGRANT	Vulnerability condition: Migrant status
VULN	Intersecting vulnerability conditions
UNIV	Holding a university degree
MOT_ENV	Motivation: Environmental
MOT_EC	Motivation: Economic
VAL_ENV	Values: Related to the environment/love for nature
VAL_JUST	Values: Related to global justice/equity/inclusion
BEHAV	Personal change towards sustainability (mobility, food, energy, recycling)
NET_ENV	Membership in an environmental network
NET_EC	Membership in an economic network
NET_CULT	Membership in a cultural network
MODEL_BUS	Propensity to adopt or consider measures from other businesses
MODEL_NET	Propensity to adopt or consider measures from ESCos*, networks, etc.
INCENT	Propensity to consider existing incentives or subsidies

* Energy Service Companies

Calibration of conditions and outcomes

To proceed with crisp-set calibration, the available information was reduced to binary systems (0-1), assigning a set membership score to each case and condition.

The calibration of the outcome was based on a holistic assessment of the respondents' open-ended responses to the pre-defined questions. In particular, as mentioned above, an index based on three criteria was created to define whether the outcome was achieved or not (see point 5.2.). Overall, 14 of the 21 entrepreneurs were able to successfully make their business (more) environmentally sustainable.

As with the outcome, the assignment of membership to some of these conditions was based on a holistic assessment of the respondent's open-ended responses to one or a series of predetermined questions. A table showing the calibration of the seven main conditions used in the QCA applied to RL4 is presented in the Appendix.

Truth table construction

A final truth table for each causal configuration that was identified (“solution”) was produced according to the procedure described in the Appendix, where all the truth tables are also presented. As will be explained in the next sections, the solutions analysed in this context are based on the following combinations of conditions.

1. VAL_ENV * MOT_ENV * BEHAV
2. VAL_ENV * BEHAV * MOD_NET
3. SEX * MODEL_BUS.

Based on all the combinations observed in the panel, it was possible to perform a "Standard analysis" for each solution using the fsQCA software, the results of which are presented in the following section.

Identification of causal configurations

The distribution by country, gender and **outcome** is shown in Table 13 (for a more detailed description of the sample, see the RL4 report).

Table 13. RL4 panel by country, gender* and outcome.

	Women	Men	Total	POSITIVE OUT-COME
Belgium	5	/	5	2
Greece	3	1	4	3
Italy	2	2	4	3
Norway	/	4	4	3
Romania	3	1	4	4
Total	13	8	21	15

* The sample didn't include nonbinary persons.

As defined in Section 4.2, the outcome was considered successful if, despite the inherent vulnerability of microentrepreneurs, they were able to successfully make their business (more) environmentally sustainable. Different combinations of conditions were tested to explore their relation to the outcome. The results are described below.

*Different combinations of conditions were tested to explore their relationship with the outcomes, starting with those more related to the ACCTING theoretical approaches, and then broadening the scope to test additional combinations. **It is important to note** that QCA aims to identify combinations of conditions, so it may well be that conditions that are highly relevant in a binary correlation do not produce robust results when combined with others, i.e. are not critical in identifying consistent patterns or individual profiles that lead to an outcome.*

Personal motivations, values and behaviours

A first set of results revolves around the role of personal motivations, values and behaviours in leading to the outcome. One solution highlights micro-entrepreneurs who show a positive outcome and display a very consistent profile in terms of environmental attitudes and personal behaviours, beyond (but generally in relation to) the actions taken in their businesses.

Two overlapping pathways to the outcome emerge, with the adherence to environmental values appearing in both.

SOLUTION 1 – CONSISTENT ATTITUDES AND BEHAVIOURS

Analysed conditions:

VAL_ENV (Environment values) * MOT_ENV (Environmental motivations) * BEHAV (Personal change towards sustainability)

Solution terms in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Raw consistency
VAL_ENV*BEHAV	0.642857	1
VAL_ENV*MOT_ENV	0.428571	1

Solution coverage: 0.79 (11 of the 14 cases with a positive outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 1 (All cases included in the solution have a positive outcome)

This solution suggests that the achievement of the outcome can be linked to two partially overlapping solution terms: 1. Micro-entrepreneurs with strong environmental values who adopted sustainable personal behaviours; 2. Micro-entrepreneurs with strong environmental values and a predominant environmental motivation to make their business sustainable.

The importance of models of practice

Looking at other potentially relevant conditions, another solution emerges, presenting a consistent profile of micro-entrepreneurs who are successful in making their businesses more sustainable.

Three strongly interlinked combinations of factors confirm the relevance of environmental values and personal behavioural change and highlight the role played by business networks and associations in providing examples of viable environmental practices.

SOLUTION 2 – MODELS FROM NETWORKS AND ASSOCIATIONS

Analysed conditions:

VAL_ENV (Environmental values) * BEHAV (Personal change towards sustainability) * MOD_NET (Propensity to adopt or consider measures from ESCos, networks, etc.)

Solution terms in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Raw consistency
VAL_ENV*BEHAV	0.642857	1
VAL_ENV*MODEL_NET	0.5	1
BEHAV*MODEL_NET	0.5	1

Solution coverage: 0.79 (11 of the 14 cases with a positive outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 1 (All cases included in the solution have a positive outcome)

This solution suggests that the achievement of the outcome can be linked to three largely overlapping solution terms: 1. Micro-entrepreneurs with strong environmental values, who adopted sustainable personal behaviours; 2. Micro-entrepreneurs with strong environmental values, who are inclined to consider examples of sustainable business practice from networks of micro-enterprises, Energy Service Companies, etc.; 3. Micro-entrepreneurs who adopted sustainable personal behaviours and are inclined to consider examples of sustainable business practice from networks of micro-enterprises, Energy Service Companies, etc.

Further analysis of the openness of micro-entrepreneurs to learn from others revealed a fairly clear gender difference, particularly in terms of the willingness to adopt practices from other micro-entrepreneurs (MOD_BUS) in a direct peer-to-peer exchange (Solution 3).

SOLUTION 3 – MODELS FROM OTHER BUSINESSES

Analysed conditions:

SEX (Woman/Man) * MODEL_BUS (Propensity to adopt or consider measures from other businesses)

Solution terms in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Raw consistency
SEX*MODEL_BUS	0.5	0.875
~SEX*~MODEL_BUS	0.357143	0.714286

Solution coverage: 0.86 (12 of the 14 cases with a positive outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 0.80 (12 of the 15 cases included in the solution have a positive outcome)

This solution highlights two different and even opposed pathways to the outcome for women and men, suggesting that women who reach a positive outcome are more inclined than men to adopt or consider practices supporting the sustainability of their businesses from other micro-entrepreneurs.

Interpretation

The application of QCA was instrumental in confirming and synthesising some of the main conclusions of the final RL4 research report, in a few cases integrating them.

The findings of RL4 have shown that, contrary to general expectations, there are vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs who successfully address the environmental sustainability of their business, and that this process is linked to a **change in personal behaviour** that goes hand in hand with the intention to improve the sustainability of the business.

- The QCA analysis adds some information on the factors strengthen the possibility of a positive outcome, thus refining the profiles of micro-entrepreneurs, who succeed in making their business (more) environmentally sustainable (Solution 1). In the set of 21 micro-entrepreneurs who have initiated a change process to improve their business's environmental sustainability, those reaching a positive outcome are mainly those:
 - Who have strong environmental values
 - Who adopted sustainable personal behaviours
 - Who have a predominant environmental motivation to make their business sustainable.
- This highlights a related point that was touched upon in the RL4 report and emerges very clearly through QCA, namely that the motivations are not necessarily only or predominantly economic, as can sometimes be assumed when it comes to vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs.

Another RL4 finding is that a driver of success in making one's business environmentally sustainable is **engaging with networks dealing with environmental issues**. In this perspective, two factors were analysed: the propensity to adopt or consider measures from Energy Service Companies, networks, etc. and the propensity to adopt or consider measures from other businesses.

- In the frame of the QCA, factors related to outcomes are not considered separately, but rather in combination with others. We therefore learn (Solution 2) that micro-entrepreneurs are more likely to reach a positive outcome if – beyond having strong environmental values and adopting sustainable personal behaviours – they tend to

consider examples of sustainable business practice from networks of micro-enterprises, Energy Service Companies, etc.

The importance of models can be further refined if we integrate a **gender perspective**.

- Through QCA, it became clearer that the women who achieve a positive outcome in improving the sustainability of their business are more likely than men to have considered or adopted practices learned from other microentrepreneurs in a peer-to-peer learning process. Conversely, the men who did not consider practices from other micro-enterprises are more likely to fail to successfully improve the sustainability of their businesses (Solution 3).

Limitations

The main difficulty in applying QCA to the sample of 21 vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs was that, for reasons explained in the report for Research Line 4, the selected micro-entrepreneurs were all engaged in efforts to make their businesses more sustainable. While we were able to identify a significant scale of success in these efforts thanks to the in-depth knowledge of the cases, this made it impossible to compare positive outcomes with truly negative ones, thus weakening the comparative strength of the analysis.

Another limitation stems from the composition of the sample, where migrant micro-entrepreneurs accounted for two-thirds of the total. This was in line with the aim of the Research Line and the overall ACCTING project, which focuses on intersectional vulnerable groups. However, it made it more difficult to make robust comparisons between migrant and non-migrant micro-entrepreneurs.

2.5 QCA report for RL5: Improving food security and healthy diets in vulnerable communities

Objectives of the study

Research line 5 addresses the key issue of food security, with a particular focus on food accessibility, healthy and sustainable food consumption, and waste reduction. In the first cycle, research focused on identifying the key enablers and hindrances driving access (purchase and consumption) to healthy, affordable, and sustainable food by people with different levels of vulnerability.

In the second research cycle, RL5 engaged with a wide range of stakeholders, from individual citizens and their families to community-level collective actions and sought to establish whether participation in a local initiative was the key to changing individual and collective behaviour.⁹

Outcome identification

The outcome of the local initiatives that have been analysed within RL5 to the aim of the QCA exercise has been defined as their **capacity to support vulnerable participants in adopting a healthy and environmentally sustainable diet**.

In order to assign a positive or negative outcome to each initiative, two main sources of information were used. First, the interviews with the promoters, where a number of relevant questions were asked to assess the impact of the initiative in different areas. Second, the interviews with the individual participants, as a parallel source of information providing direct access to their actual food practices and outcomes. The country reports compiled by each research team provided supplementary information that helped characterise the individual initiatives and informed the assignment of outcomes and conditions.

Case selection and identification of conditions

Case selection

A total of ten cases were analysed, mostly in urban or semi-urban contexts, except for one non-urban case. The countries involved are Austria, Greece, Portugal, Sweden, and Türkiye. The cases, although very diverse, fall into two main categories and are presented in Table 14.

⁹ The full RL5 report is authored by Luís Moreno, Patrícia Abrantes, Daniela Ferreira, Maria Lucinda Fonseca (IGOT), Ayşe Gül Altınay, Burcu Borhan Türeli, Esin Düzel (SU), Carolin Zorell (ORU), Vassilis Chatzimpyros, Vasiliki Miliadi, Christos Stergiadis (SEERC), Martin Felix Gajdusek, Olga Bolibok (ZSI).

Table 14. Types of initiatives considered by type and country within RL5.

INITIATIVE	AU	GR	PT	SE	TK
Community gardens	X		XX		XX
Initiatives supporting people in need with an emphasis on healthy, environmentally sustainable diets	X	XX		XX	

Identification of conditions

The identification of the conditions to be related to the different outcomes of the initiatives was guided by the main theoretical tenets of ACCTING:

- The notion of socially just environmental transitions
- The centrality of gender+, intersectional perspectives in assessing the inclusivity of food-related initiatives
- The identification of priority target groups through multidimensional vulnerability approaches
- The key role of vulnerable/disadvantaged communities in environmental transitions.

On this basis, the following sets of information have been collected and analysed for each initiative:

- **Context** (urban, semi-urban, rural)
- **General description of the initiative** (background, aims, activities)
- **Target populations** (all initiatives target different vulnerable groups)
- **Characteristics of the promoting organisation** (membership, women in decision-making positions, recruitment, resources)
- **Network of actors** (partnership with public, private, non-profit actors and groups)
- **Impact on food behaviour** (impact on healthy/sustainable food consumption, increased food security, other impacts at community level).

Within these sets, the conditions expected to have the greatest impact on the outcome were selected according to the identified outcome for RL5. Conditions were also selected based on the **number of cases** exhibiting them, as conditions present in all or only a very few cases are not suitable for comparison in QCA analysis. The selected conditions are listed in Table 15.

Table 15. Codes for conditions within RL5.

CODE	CONDITION
GARD	Presence of a garden
FOOD	Food distribution
SHELT	Provision of shelter
EDU	Provision of educational opportunities
SOC	Organisation of social activities

INT	Provision of integrated services
COMM	Community-building efforts/initiatives
KNOWL	Food knowledge-integration practices
PARTIC	Participation of beneficiaries in managing the initiative
PROM_CSO	Promoting body: Civil Society Organisation
PROM_LA	Promoting body: Local Authority
PARTN_CSO	Partnerships with Civil Society Organisations
PARTN_LA	Partnerships with Local Authorities
PARTN_PRIV	Partnerships with private companies
VOL	Substantial role of volunteers
WOM	Women in decision-making roles in the promoting organisation
GEND_FOC	Relevant gender focus of the initiative

Calibration of conditions and outcomes

To calibrate conditions according to the crisp-set setup of the analysis, the available information was reduced to binary systems (0-1), assigning a set membership score to each case and condition.

The calibration of the outcome (i.e., the ability to support vulnerable participants in adopting a healthy and ecologically sustainable diet), was based on the holistic assessment of responses of both promoters and beneficiaries to the in-depth interview guide. Overall, 5 initiatives in the panel achieved a positive outcome and the other 5 did not (see Table 16, below). A table showing the calibration of the main conditions used in the QCA applied to RL5 is presented in the Appendix.

Truth table construction

A final truth table for each causal configuration that was identified ("solution") was produced according to the procedure described in the Appendix, where the truth tables are also presented. As will be explained in the next sections, the solutions analysed in this context are based on the following two combinations of conditions.

1. COMM * KNOWL * EDU * SOC
2. FOOD * PARTN_PRIV * KNOWL

Based on the combinations observed in the panel, it was possible to perform a "Standard analysis" for each solution using the fsQCA software, the results of which are presented in the following section.

Identification of causal configurations

The distribution of the ten cases by country and **outcome** is shown in Table 16 (for a more detailed description of the panel, see the RL5 report).

Table 16. RL5 panel by country and outcome.

CODE	Cases with a positive outcome	Cases with a negative outcome
Austria	1	1
Greece	0	2
Portugal	2	0
Sweden	0	2
Türkiye	2	0
Total	5	5

As mentioned in Section 10.2, the outcome was defined for the QCA analysis as the **capacity of the initiatives to support vulnerable participants in adopting a healthy and environmentally sustainable diet**. Different combinations of conditions were tested to explore their relation to the outcome. The results are described below.

*Different combinations of conditions were tested to explore their relationship with the outcomes, starting with those more related to the ACCTING theoretical approaches, and then broadening the scope to test additional combinations. **It is important to note** that QCA aims to identify combinations of conditions, so it may well be that conditions that are highly relevant in a binary correlation do not produce robust results when combined with others, i.e. are not critical in identifying consistent patterns or individual profiles that lead to an outcome.*

The pathway to the outcome

The first and most important finding to highlight is that cases with a positive outcome consistently share a number of conditions. A single, strong pathway appears from the analysis.

SOLUTION 1 – INTEGRATING KNOWLEDGE, BUILDING COMMUNITIES

Analysed conditions:

COMM (Community-building efforts/initiatives) * KNOWL (Food knowledge-integration practices) * EDU (Provision of educational opportunities) * SOC (Organisation of social initiatives)

Solution term in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
COMM*KNOWL*EDU*SOC	1	1

Solution coverage: 1 (All cases with a positive outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 1 (All cases included in the solution have a positive outcome)

This solution suggests that the achievement of the outcome can be linked to a single solution term: 1. Initiatives aimed at community-building, where food knowledge-integration practices take place, educational opportunities are available and social activities are organised.

It can be added that while the combination of these four elements is only present in initiatives with a positive outcome, some of the individual factors are also shared by the other initiatives. However, it is interesting to note that the factor KNOWL (**knowledge-integration**

practices) is present only in initiatives that achieve the outcome, identifying it as the **most influential factor** and as a necessary and sufficient condition to achieve the objective of influencing food behaviour.

It should be noted that all the **community gardens** have this factor in common and have a positive outcome. They naturally encourage the exchange of gardening and plant cultivation techniques between the gardeners, including knowledge of plants from the migrants' countries of origin, as well as local or traditional recipes. This in turn supports community building.

A pathway to no outcome

A second point to highlight is that the more interventions focused on the direct provision of food, the less likely they were to succeed in changing people's behaviour towards healthier and more sustainable diets, regardless of the type of food provided. Indeed, the conditions conducive to the outcome are not frequently included in these kinds of initiatives. For example, while efforts to build community or provide educational opportunities may be present in some cases, the knowledge and expertise of the beneficiaries are rarely considered or valued, which has been shown to be a critical factor in bringing about change.

SOLUTION 2 – Leading to non-outcome PROVIDING “ONLY” FOOD

Analysed conditions:

FOOD (Food distribution) * PARTN_PRIV (Partnership with private companies) * KNOWL (Food knowledge-integration practices)

Solution term in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
FOOD*PARTN_PRIV*~KNOWL	1	1

Solution coverage: 1 (All cases with a negative outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 1 (All cases included in the solution have a negative outcome)

This solution suggests that the failure in achieving the outcome can be linked to one prevalent solution term: 1. Initiatives providing direct access to food, in partnership with private companies, which do not integrate the beneficiaries' knowledge about food.

The inclusion of private companies in the solution term is related to the characteristics of the initiatives directly providing food, which often have arrangements, for example, with supermarkets or restaurants that make their leftovers or surpluses available.

Interpretation

The QCA analysis within RL5 focused on one specific outcome of the many that were investigated within the Research Line. The outcome related to the ability of the initiatives to bring changes in the food practices and behaviours of participants and beneficiaries exposed to vulnerability conditions, with specific reference to environmentally sustainable and healthy diets. Other impacts that are relevant in the overall RL5 report (e.g., food security or collective dimensions of change) were not focused on as outcomes, although in some cases they were included in the analysis as factors potentially contributing to the outcome.

In terms of the selected outcome, the results of the QCA provide some additional insights as they seek to highlight the most relevant of the rich set of factors identified in the qualitative analysis conducted within the RL, and their more impactful combinations.

One finding from the RL5 report (and more generally across the ACCTING research lines) is that being part of a community or social network and building meaningful relationships are significant enablers of change, as is the availability of a safe space for community encounters.

- The QCA analysis confirms this finding through the relevance of the factor related to community-building approaches (COMM) to support change in personal or family dietary habits. Community gardens, in particular, clearly qualify as suitable spaces for community building (Solution 1).

Another finding highlighted in the RL5 report is that cultural adaptation and culturally sensitive approaches, as well as the acquisition of **knowledge** about environmental practices and the consequent increase in **self-efficacy**, are associated with change.

- In the QCA analysis, knowledge integration practices in particular emerged as the single most influential factor among those analysed in supporting dietary change. Knowledge integration practices imply community relations based on the principle of valuing diversity, making people feel socially appreciated and contributing to building positive feelings of self-efficacy (Solution 1).

One of the impacts of the initiatives analysed within the RL5 report was the **provision of ready-made food** to people in difficult situations.

- When it comes to providing direct access to food, the QCA analysis showed that these initiatives, while necessary, have less potential to change dietary habits, regardless of the type and origin of the food provided, and even when accompanied by the provision of educational or social opportunities (Solution 2).
- In our panel, partnerships with the private sector are involved with this type of initiative. However, when looking at the overall results of the QCA analysis, it is clear that it is certainly not the partnerships with private actors that explain the lack of success in improving dietary habits, but the lack of knowledge integration practices that characterises the initiatives, however meritorious, that provide food to people in need (solution 2).
- This leads to an additional conclusion, again replicating broader ACCTING results, that highlights how difficult it is to involve the most vulnerable in behavioural change practices without providing a broader set of measures, from urgent support to community integration, validation of knowledge and expertise, social appreciation and self-efficacy improvement tools.

Limitations

The main limitation of applying QCA to the results of RL5 is the very limited number of initiatives analysed (ten). While this is within the validity limits set for QCA (Schneider & Wagemann 2010), it has necessarily limited the number of factors that could be tested. Another limitation is related to the diversity of the cases analysed, whose objectives ranged from providing food assistance to people in need to more articulated objectives of social inclusion and promotion of health and environmental awareness. Considering the outcome chosen for the QCA (dietary change towards healthy and sustainable food), this is certainly a limitation that somewhat oriented the results of the analysis. However, it had the advantage of making these results very clear and thus providing clear indications of the approaches needed for different types of interventions.

Another limitation concerns the gender perspective. While the RL5 report highlights the gender aspects of the change processes analysed, the QCA analysis didn't produce synthetic results in this respect because the factors analysed (women's decision-making roles in the promoting organisation and the gender focus of the initiatives) did not work in discriminating cases with positive and negative outcomes in terms of dietary change. This means that, although gender emerged as a determining factor in some of the cases analysed (e.g., those in Türkiye), it was not a decisive condition in all or most cases that led to a positive outcome.

Finally, the RL5 report highlighted the need for broad local partnerships to support groups with different vulnerabilities to access healthy and sustainable food. Indeed, partnerships between public and non-profit actors, as well as with the private sector, underpin most, if not all, of the initiatives analysed, both those aimed at providing opportunities to grow or cook food and those aimed at directly providing prepared food. The QCA analysis did not produce any relevant results in this respect, as partnerships characterised both cases with a positive and a negative outcome (except for partnerships with private actors, as seen above). More in-depth analysis of the substantive characteristics of the partnerships would have been needed to better identify the role of specific types of partnerships in the success of the initiatives.

2.6 QCA report for RL7: Cycling initiatives for an inclusive mobility transition

Objectives of the study

Research line 7 focuses on how cycling initiatives and programmes can contribute to an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal. More particularly, RL7 focuses on the impact such initiatives or programmes may have on behavioural change for vulnerable groups and their contribution to cycling inclusion. In the second cycle, RC7 focuses on how different cycling initiatives can help their participants to overcome barriers to cycling (or not), and what factors are important to make this happen¹⁰.

Outcome identification

The aim of the QCA analysis is to analyse the results of RL7 at the level of individual participants in cycling initiatives to assess **whether they have started to cycle regularly as a result of their participation**. To assign a positive or negative outcome to each participant, reference was made to the responses to a specific item in the in-depth interview guide, which explicitly aimed to explore whether the participant cycled regularly after the initiative. In addition, each interview was analysed and considered holistically to better understand the extent and significance of the change for the participant. The country reports compiled by the national research teams provided additional information to assign outcomes and conditions.

Case selection and identification of conditions

Case selection

In total, 47 persons participated in the 12 cycling initiatives considered in six European countries (Belgium, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Romania, and Sweden). The initiatives are reported in Table 17 by type.

Table 17. Types of initiatives considered by type and country within RL7.

INITIATIVE	BE	GR	IT	PT	RO	SE
Bike school	X					XXX
Bike to school	X		X			
Bike kitchen			X	XX		
Bike promotion		X			XX	

Out of a total of 47 participants, 37 were selected for the QCA analysis. The excluded cases mostly corresponded to people who already cycled regularly in their lives, for whom the impact of the initiative would not have been meaningful in terms of the specific outcome

¹⁰ The full RL7 report is authored by Dag Balkmar (ORU) and Lina Sandström (UGOT), in collaboration with Claudia Aglietti (K&I), Marina Cacace (K&I), Vassilis Chatzibirros (SEERC), Alain Denis (YW), Alina Esteves (IGOT), Daniela Ferreira (IGOT), Maria Lucinda Fonseca (IGOT), Andrei Holman (UAIC), Aart Kerremans (YW), Simona Popușoi (UAIC), Francesca Pugliese (K&I), Christos Stergiadis (SEERC), Ana Vivas (SEERC), Martijn Vogelzang (YW).

selected. A few cases were also excluded for lack of specific information needed to assess the outcome.

In the preliminary phase of the QCA analysis, it was considered appropriate to conduct **two separate analyses**: one on the full panel of 37 participants and one on a sub-panel including a selected group of participants (as explained in Sections 7.6.1 and 7.6.2).

Identification of conditions

The identification of conditions to be related to the different outcomes of the cycling initiatives was guided by the main theoretical tenets of ACCTING:

- The notion of socially just environmental transitions
- The centrality of gender+, intersectional perspectives in assessing the inclusivity of sustainable mobility initiatives
- The key role of vulnerable/disadvantaged communities in environmental transitions.

On this basis, the following sets of information have been collected and analysed for each respondent:

- **Socio-demographic characteristics** (e.g., sex, age, education, income, employment position, migration status)
- **Vulnerability conditions** (e.g., gender¹¹, old age, disability, ethnicity/racial, religion/belief, language)
- **Mobility background** (everyday mobility before the initiative and satisfaction about it, degree of cycling diffusion and inclusion in the area, etc.)
- **Motives for joining the initiative** (how the participant learned about the initiative, reasons for joining, possible hesitations, etc.)
- **Cycling inclusion, satisfaction and support** (inclusive atmosphere, diversity of staff, barriers for people in vulnerable conditions, support received by family and friends, etc.)
- **Behavioural change and other impacts** (support received to overcome barriers to cycling, intention to cycle more regularly, actual change of cycling behaviour, other impacts).

Within these sets, the conditions expected to have the greatest impact on the outcome (the uptake of regular cycling) were selected according to the theoretical framework and research question of RL7. Conditions were also selected based on the number of cases exhibiting them, as conditions present in all or only a very few cases are not suitable for comparison in QCA analysis. The selected conditions are listed in Table 18.

Table 18. Codes for conditions within RL7.

CODE	CONDITION
SEX	Woman/Man/Nonbinary
GEN	Vulnerability condition: Gender
AGE	Vulnerability condition: Old age

¹¹ Gender includes vulnerability conditions related to gender, gender identity and sexual orientation.

CODE	CONDITION
MIGR	Vulnerability condition: migrant background
DSB	Vulnerability condition: Disability impacting mobility
SEC	Vulnerability condition: Low socio-economic background
EXC	Vulnerability condition: Social exclusion*
CARE	Care responsibilities
DIFF	Perception of the diffusion of cycling in the area
SAT_TRA	Satisfaction with transport arrangements before the initiative
TRA_WALK	Walking as the main means of transport before the initiative
TRA_PT	Public transport as the main means of transport before the initiative
TRA_CAR	Car as the main means of transport before the initiative
MOTIV_PRACT	Practical motivations for cycling
MOTIV_SUST	Environmental motivations for cycling
MOTIV_HEA	Health-related motivations for cycling
MOTIV_SOC	Social motivations for cycling
HESIT	Hesitation to take part in the initiative
SAT_INI	Overall satisfaction with the initiative
INCL_INI	Perceived inclusivity of the atmosphere of the initiative
SUPP	Support from family and friends
PRE_ACC	Access to a suitable bike before the initiative
POST_ACC	Access to a suitable bike after the initiative
PRE_COMP	Competence in cycling before the initiative
POST_COMP	Competence in cycling after the initiative

* A holistic assessment was made to assess the intersectional vulnerability profile of each respondent and whether this led to a situation of severe social exclusion.

Calibration of conditions and outcomes

To proceed with crisp-set analysis, the available information was reduced to binary systems (0-1), assigning a set membership score to each case and condition.

The calibration of the outcome, as mentioned in section 7.2, was based on the responses to a specific item in the in-depth interview guide, which was designed to explicitly explore whether the participant cycled regularly after the initiative. In addition, each interview was analysed and considered holistically to better understand the extent and significance of the change for the participant. Overall, in the full panel of 37 interviewees (see Section 7.6.1), 21 have a positive outcome; in the sub-panel of 25 interviewees (see Section 7.6.2 below), 19 have a positive outcome. A table showing the calibration of the main conditions used in the QCA applied to RL7 is presented in the Appendix.

Truth table construction

A final truth table for each causal configuration that was identified (“solution”) was produced according to the procedure described in the Appendix, where all the truth tables are also presented. As will be explained in the next sections, the solutions analysed in this context are based on the following combinations of conditions.

With reference to the full panel (37 interviewees)

1. PRE_ACC * PRE_COMP * SUPP
2. PRE_COMP * SUPP * MOTIV_PRACT

With reference to the sub-panel (25 interviewees)

3. SEC * SAT_TRA * SUPP * PRE_COMP * POST_ACC
4. MIGR * PRE_COM

Based on all the combinations observed in the panel, it was possible to perform a "Standard analysis" for each solution using the fsQCA software, the results of which are presented in the following section.

Identification of causal configurations

*Different combinations of conditions were tested to explore their relationship with the outcomes, starting with those more related to the ACCTING theoretical approaches, and then broadening the scope to test additional combinations. **It is important to note** that QCA aims to identify combinations of conditions, so it may well be that conditions that are highly relevant in a binary correlation do not produce robust results when combined with others, i.e. are not critical in identifying consistent patterns or individual profiles that lead to an outcome.*

Full panel analysis

The distribution by country, gender and **outcome** is shown in Table 19. It is worth mentioning that a third of the participants have a migrant background (12) and slightly fewer are confronted with a disability (10). For a more detailed description of the panel, see the RL7 report.

Table 19. RL7 panel by country, gender and outcome.*

	Women	Men	Total	POSITIVE OUTCOME
Belgium	4	/	4	/
Greece	7	1	8	8
Italy	1	1	2	2
Portugal	1	1	2	1
Romania	6	1	7	7
Sweden	14	/	14	3
Total	33	4	37	21

* The panel did not include nonbinary persons.

As defined in Section 6.2, the outcome was considered successful if participants started to cycle regularly in their daily lives, which they hadn't before. Different combinations of conditions were tested to explore their relation to this outcome. The results are described below.

When looking at the full set of participants in the initiatives, the stronger result highlights the crucial role of previous access to a bicycle and previous competence in cycling for the initiative to trigger the uptake of regular rather than occasional cycling. The role of support from family and friends is also important. Two overlapping pathways to the outcome emerge, with previous competence appearing in both.

SOLUTION 1 – THE IMPORTANCE OF NOT STARTING FROM SCRATCH

Analysed conditions:

PRE_ACC (Access to a suitable bike before the initiative) * PRE_COMP (Competence in cycling before the initiative) * SUPP (Support from family and friends)

Solution terms in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
PRE_ACC*PRE_COMP	0.619048	1
PRE_COMP*SUPP	0.52381	1

Solution coverage: 0.81 (17 of the 21 cases with a positive outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 1 (All cases included in the solution have a positive outcome)

This solution suggests that the achievement of the outcome can be linked to two partially overlapping solution terms: 1. Participants who had both previous access to a bicycle and previous competence in cycling; 2. Participants who had previous competence in cycling and support from family and friends.

A similar, slightly less strong combination confirms the importance of previous competence and adds a motivational element.

SOLUTION 2 – CYCLING FOR PRACTICAL REASONS

Analysed conditions:

PRE_COMP (Competence in cycling before the initiative) * SUPP (Support from family and friends) * MOTIV_PRACT (Practical motivations for cycling)

Solution terms in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
MOTIV_PRACT*PRE_COMP	0.714286	0.9375
PRE_COMP*SUPP	0.52381	1

Solution coverage: 0.81 (17 of the 21 cases with a positive outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 0.94 (17 of the 18 cases included in the solution have a positive outcome)

This solution suggests that the achievement of the outcome can be linked to two partially overlapping solution terms: 1. Participants who had practical reasons for cycling and previous competence in cycling; 2. Participants who had previous competence in cycling and support from family and friends.

Sub-panel analysis

Some participants in the panel were involved in focus groups or through other methods that did not allow for the collection of detailed information on their socio-economic background. As the socio-economic background of individuals may provide additional insight into the

factors associated with the outcome, a smaller panel of participants for whom socio-economic information was collected individually was built. The sub-panel includes 25 respondents, distributed by country, gender and outcome as shown in Table 20.

Table 20. RL7 sub-panel by country, gender* and outcome.

	Women	Men	Total	POSITIVE OUTCOME
Belgium	4	/	4	/
Greece	7	1	8	8
Italy	1	1	2	2
Portugal	1	1	2	1
Romania	6	1	7	7
Sweden	2	/	2	1
Total	21	4	25	19

* The panel didn't include nonbinary persons.

Within this sub-panel, a profile emerges of people, mostly from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds, who are dissatisfied with their current daily mobility arrangements, but who have the skills and support to make the most of their participation in the initiative to switch to daily cycling.

SOLUTION 3 – THE SUPPORT AND RESOURCES NEEDED FOR CHANGE

Analysed conditions:

SEC (Low socio-economic background) * SAT_TRA (Satisfaction with current transport arrangements) * PRE_COMP (Competence in cycling before the initiative) * POST_ACC (Access to a suitable bike after the initiative) * SUPP (Support from family and friends)

Solution terms in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
PRE_COMP*POST_ACC*~SAT_TRA	0.684211	0.928571
POST_ACC*SUPP*~SAT_TRA*SEC	0.210526	1
PRE_COMP*POST_ACC*SUPP*SEC	0.368421 0	1

Solution coverage: 0.95 (18 of 19 cases with a positive outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 0.95 (18 of 19 cases included in the solution have a positive outcome)

This solution suggests that the achievement of the outcome can be linked to three overlapping solution terms: 1. Participants who had previous competence in cycling, were dissatisfied with their travel arrangements before the initiative, and had access to a bike after the initiative; 2. Participants who have a low socio-economic background, were dissatisfied with their travel arrangements before the initiative, had access to a bike after the initiative, and received support from family and friends; 3. Participants who have a low socio-economic background, had previous competence in cycling, and had access to a bike after the initiative.

Finally, within the same sub-panel, combinations were tested **that did not lead to the outcome** (daily cycling) but to failure to achieve the outcome despite participation in the initiative. The result shows how the lack of previous cycling competence, which is particularly common among migrants is a major barrier to starting regular cycling. It should be noted that all but one of the migrant participants in this sub-panel are women.

SOLUTION 4 – Leading to non-outcome MIGRANT BACKGROUND AND PREVIOUS CYCLING COMPETENCE

Analysed conditions:

MIGR (Migrant status) * PRE_COMP (Competence in cycling before the initiative)

Solution terms in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
MIGR*~PRE_COMP	0.833333	0.833333

Solution coverage: 0.83 (5 cases of the 6 with a negative outcome are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 0.83 (5 cases of the 6 included in the solution have a negative outcome)

This solution suggests that the failure in achieving the outcome can be linked to one prevalent solution term: Participants with a migrant background who did not have previous competence in cycling.

Interpretation

The results derived from the QCA applied to RL7 were not just intended to validate the conclusions of the final RL7 research report but also to generate additional insights to enhance the overall analysis. Specifically, the data analysed for the QCA place greater emphasis on the individual characteristics of participants rather than the specific types of initiatives, which were the main focus of the RL7 report. Consequently, the following conclusions present a number of findings that either confirm those of the report or complement them, providing an alternative perspective to be incorporated into the broader analysis.

The RL7 report has highlighted that cycling initiatives can provide only limited support in facilitating change, particularly for the most vulnerable individuals, when **(infra)structural barriers** exist and when participants perceive or experience a **lack of cycling safety**, which may also stem from an absence of prior biking culture (in some cases recorded in individuals with a migrant background).

- The QCA analysis further reveals that prior access to a suitable bicycle and, more importantly, previous cycling competence are key factors in achieving the outcome of cycling regularly (Solution 1). This suggests that, despite the support an initiative can offer, it alone is not sufficient to develop the necessary skills and confidence for individuals unfamiliar with cycling to fully integrate it into their daily lives. This finding is reinforced by the negative outcome observed among migrant women, who, even with a strong interest in participating in the initiative and learning how to cycle, could meet more difficulties in achieving the desired outcome and feeling safe enough to use the bicycle in their daily lives due to a lack of prior cycling experience (Solution 4).

In the RL7 report, **support from the community, family and friends** was highlighted as a critical factor in starting to cycle regularly. The report concluded that support plays a key role in facilitating change for all research participants, including and especially those with high vulnerability profiles or those living in areas where cycling is not widespread (low bikeability).

- The solutions identified through QCA confirm the role of support in achieving the outcome (Solutions 1 and 2) and add that the likelihood of success increases when individuals have a practical motivation to change their travel behaviour towards cycling (Solution 2).

Another finding of the RL7 report is that inequalities related to **socio-economic barriers** (access) appear to have been **reduced by the initiatives**, although the cost of purchasing a bicycle suitable for one's needs remained a significant barrier for the most vulnerable groups.

- Within the QCA analysis, indeed, low socio-economic background does not lead to negative outcomes if a set of conditions are met: individuals are dissatisfied with their current mode of travel, have previous cycling competence, could rely on a suitable bike – often provided by the initiative –, and received support from family and friends. These factors collectively enable them to transition to cycling (Solution 3).

Limitations

A first limitation was that, in some instances, the different methods of data collection (in-depth interviews, focus groups, or participant observation) hindered the comparability of respondents' information, allowing for comparisons only on certain topics. Another challenge in assessing the post-competence factor and assigning the outcome was the varying duration of participants' involvement in the initiatives. Since some had been engaged for a longer time than others, it was not always possible to determine whether the behavioural change – starting to cycle regularly – was temporary, linked to their current participation in the initiative, or indicative of a lasting impact.

The differing approaches of cycling initiatives in promoting cycling inclusion also posed a limitation for the QCA. The initiatives varied in their target groups and activities, and we were unable to find a meaningful way to compare them or incorporate them as a factor in the QCA analysis in a way that would yield relevant results.

Regarding intersectional aspects, the panel included individuals with various disabilities who participated either in initiatives specifically designed for them (particularly in Sweden) or in general initiatives open to all. Differences in types of disabilities and the varying goals of the initiatives – some of which focused on teaching specific forms of cycling for individuals with special needs – made it challenging to identify common patterns for a unified 'participant with a disability' profile. As a result, the QCA did not yield meaningful solutions applicable to this category.

Lastly, a significant limitation was the inability to conduct gender-based comparisons. Our panel was composed almost entirely of women (33 out of 37 participants), and some initiatives were predominantly designed for women. Additionally, many male participants were excluded from the QCA analysis as they had already been cycling regularly before joining the initiative.

2.7 QCA report for RL8: Reception of car-free policies by intersectional vulnerable groups

Objectives of the study

Research line 8 examines how a more sustainable transport system can be achieved in the context of the European Green Deal by looking at how to encourage changes in individual behaviour towards more sustainable mobility. In the second cycle, RL8 focuses on the individual responses of vulnerable and disadvantaged people living in deprived urban neighbourhoods to car-free policies, that is, policies that discourage car use and/or promote sustainable transport.¹²

Outcome identification

The outcomes of RL8 are analysed at the individual level (cases correspond to individual respondents). Individual responses to car-free policies were classified according to a tailored version of Hirschman's Exit, Voice and Loyalty analytical framework (Hirschman, 1970 and 1978) with the addition of the Neglect category (Farrell, 1983). Neglect has been preferred to Exit because, in mobility policy, Exit is a more difficult option to exercise, as many people are forced to stay in their area and 'suffer in silence' (Dowding & John, 2012).

The results of the analysis led to the identification of three categories of respondent response, which do not represent different levels on a scale but rather **three discrete and alternative outcomes**, which have been analysed separately.

- **VOICE** refers to those reactions involving some form of **protest** to/engagement with the authorities, whether direct (collective, vertical, e.g., through a petition) or indirect/informal (through lobbying and/or advocacy activities, e.g., in social network groups). The explicit aim of these reactions is **preventing or modifying the policy**. This definition also applies to reactions of dissatisfaction which, during or after the expression of the VOICE, lead to outcomes or intentions to **EXIT**, such as changing neighbourhood.
- **NEGLECT** characterises neutral or negative reception at the individual level, where individuals show a marked **lack of interest and/or 'suffer in silence'**, complaining about the policy only within their personal network without the aim of actively preventing or modifying the policy. People would regard the application of the policy as an **enforced obligation** and might try to circumvent the new rules or comply only to avoid the consequences. This definition also applies to some of the most vulnerable respondents, who are not particularly affected by the car-free policies, as they cannot afford a car.
- **LOYALTY** encompasses reactions ranging from acceptance to **positive reception** at the individual level. Reactions that include engagement in any form of activism in favour of the policies (collective level) are included within this category.

¹² The full RL8 report is authored by Francesca Pugliese (K&I), Marina Cacace (K&I), and Federico Marta (K&I), in collaboration with Claudia Aglietti (K&I), Dag Balkmar (ORU), Vassilis Chatzibirros (SEERC), Alina Esteves (IGOT), Daniela Ferreira (IGOT), Maria Lucinda Fonseca (IGOT), Franziska Gehlmann (NTNU), Andrei Holman (UAIC), Erika Löfström (NTNU), Giuseppe Pellegrini Masini (NTNU), Simona Popușoi (UAIC), Lina Sandström (UGOT), Christos Stergiadis (SEERC), Kenneth Vilhelmsen (NTNU).

Case selection and identification of conditions

Case selection

In six countries (Greece, Italy, Norway, Portugal, Romania and Sweden), policy measures were identified that were reasonably well known to citizens but still in the process of being implemented (none of them had been fully finalised at the time of the fieldwork). This was a necessary methodological choice in order to observe citizens' reactions and mobilisations. Table 21 gives an overview of the policy measures that were selected.

Table 21. Selected policies within RL8.

Country	Policy	Rationale	City
Greece	Construction of a new flyover	Reducing traffic in the city centre	Thessaloniki
Italy	Low-emission zone	Limiting the circulation of polluting cars	Rome
Norway	Bike lane	Encouraging active mobility	Oslo
Portugal	Paid car parking	Reducing car occupation of space	Lisbon
Romania	Dedicated bus lane	Incentivising public transport	Iași
Sweden	New Bus Rapid System (BRT)	Incentivising public transport	Örebro

It can be noted that:

- The policies in Italy, Norway and Portugal are specifically developed to have a direct impact on car use in specific urban areas (**intense car-free policies**)
- The policies in Sweden and Romania are designed to improve the convenience of the bus system, thus indirectly discouraging the use of private vehicles (**moderate car-free policies**)
- The policy measure of Greece (the flyover) is situated somewhere in the middle of these two poles.

In the preliminary phase of the QCA analysis, it became clear that the distinction between intensive and moderate car-free designs would strongly influence the results. It was therefore decided to conduct **two separate QCA analyses** of citizens' reactions to the different types of car-free policy (intense and moderate). For the same reason, it was not possible to include the Greek policy in the analysis, whose insights were anyway considered in the final interpretation phase. In total, 64 citizens participated in the research, representing the QCA cases for RL8.

Identification of conditions

The identification of conditions to be related to the different reactions to car-free policies was guided by the main theoretical tenets of ACCTING, and in particular:

- The centrality of gender+, intersectional perspectives in assessing the impact of the policies
- The key role of vulnerable/disadvantaged communities in managing environmental transitions

- The role of inclusive policymaking.

On this basis, the following sets of information have been collected and analysed for each respondent:

- **Socio-demographic characteristics** (e.g., sex, age, education, income, employment position, migration status)
- **Vulnerability conditions** (e.g., gender¹³, old age, disability, ethnicity/racial, religion/belief, language)
- **Involvement with environmental issues** (e.g., environmental awareness, attitudes, and behaviour, intention to adopt more sustainable behaviours)
- **Involvement with social issues** (e.g., activism on local issues, concern for the impact of the policies on vulnerable groups)
- **Impact of the policy** (e.g., main means of transport, reported impact of the policy at the personal and family level)
- **Involvement in the policy process** (e.g., feeling of powerlessness, dis/trust in policy promoters, feeling of inclusion/lack of inclusion in the process).

Within these sets, the conditions expected to have the greatest impact on the outcome (the nature of the response to the car-free policy) based on the theoretical framework and research question of RL8 were selected and tested. Conditions were also selected based on the **number of cases** exhibiting them, as conditions present in all or only a very few cases are not suitable for comparison in QCA analysis. The selected conditions are listed in Table 22.

Table 22. Codes for conditions within RL8.

CODE	CONDITION
SEX	Woman/Man/Nonbinary
GEN	Vulnerability condition: Gender
AGE	Vulnerability condition: Old age
DSB	Vulnerability condition: Disability
MIGR	Vulnerability condition: Migrant status
SEC	Vulnerability condition: Low socio-economic background
EXC	Vulnerability condition: Social exclusion*
ENV	Environmental awareness/active
ACT	Activism on local issues
IMP	Concern for the impact of the policy on vulnerable groups
AFF	Being directly and severely affected by the policy
TRA	Main means of transport
DIST	Distrust in the policy promoters

¹³ Gender includes vulnerability conditions related to gender, gender identity and sexual orientation.

PRO	Reported inclusion in the policy process
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* A holistic assessment was made to assess the intersectional vulnerability profile of each respondent and whether this led to a situation of severe social exclusion.

Calibration of outcomes and conditions

To proceed with crisp-set analysis, all the available information was reduced to binary systems (0-1), assigning a set membership score to each case and condition.

The calibration of the outcomes was based on a holistic assessment of the respondents' open-ended answers to predetermined questions. Each case (that is, each respondent) was then assigned an outcome of VOICE, NEGLECT or LOYALTY (value = 1 if the case had a full in-membership; value = 0 if the case had a full non-membership). A table showing the calibration of the main conditions used in the QCA applied to RL8 is presented in the Appendix.

Truth table construction

A final truth table for each causal configuration that was identified ("solution") was produced according to the procedure described in the Appendix, where all the truth tables are also presented. As will be explained in the next sections, the solutions analysed in this context are based on the following combinations of conditions.

With reference to the panel "intense car-free policies" (32 interviewees)

1. EXC * ACT * DIST * IMP
2. AFF * ACT * IMP
3. ENV * AFF * ACT * DIST
4. ENV * ACT * SEC
5. SE * ACT

With reference to the panel "moderate car-free policies" (22 interviewees)

6. ENV * AFF * ACT.

Based on all the combinations observed in the panels, it was possible to perform a "Standard analysis" for each solution using the fsQCA software, the results of which are presented in the following section.

Identification of causal configurations

*Different combinations of conditions were tested to explore their relationship with the outcomes, starting with those more related to the ACCTING theoretical approaches, and then broadening the scope to test additional combinations. **It is important to note** that QCA aims to identify combinations of conditions, so it may well be that conditions that are highly relevant in a binary correlation do not produce robust results when combined with others, i.e. are not critical in identifying consistent patterns or individual profiles that lead to an outcome.*

Intense car-free policies

A first analysis was conducted on the more intense car-free policies (for their design and direct effects):

- Low-emission zone (Rome, Italy)
- Paid parking (Lisbon, Portugal)
- Bike lane with removal of parking slots (Oslo, Norway).

These three cases include 32 respondents, distributed by country, gender and outcome as shown in Table 23 (for a more detailed description of the sample, see the RL8 report in D3.3).

Table 23. RL8 panel by country, gender* and outcome/Intense car-free policies.

	Women	Men	Total	OUTCOME: VOICE
Italy	5	5	10	6
Portugal	6	7	13	4
Norway	4	5	9	8
Total	15	17	32	18

* The sample didn't include nonbinary persons.

The outcome which was primarily analysed was the VOICE outcome because of the interest in the widespread opposition to policies that have a strong impact on car use. VOICE was also the more frequent response, followed by NEGLECT (10 cases) and LOYALTY (4 cases).

The most robust resulting solution identifies two emerging profiles of people reacting with VOICE attitudes, representing two broadly overlapping pathways to the outcome, in the perspective of equifinality. Four conditions appear to be the most relevant in leading to a VOICE outcome. Distrust towards policy promoters plays a major role and features in both pathways.

SOLUTION 1 – CONDITIONS LEADING TO VOICE

Analysed conditions:

EXC (Affected by intense/overlapped social exclusion factors) * ACT (Active on local issues) * DIST (Distrusting policy promoters) * IMP (Concerned for impact on vulnerable groups)

Solution terms in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
ACT*DIST	0.736842	1
~EXC*DIST*IMP	0.473684	1

Solution coverage: 0.79 (15 of the 19 cases with outcome VOICE are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 1 (All cases included in the solution have the outcome VOICE)

This solution suggests that the VOICE outcome can be linked to two largely overlapping solution terms: 1. People who are active on local issues and with little trust in policy promoters; 2. Vulnerable but not socially excluded people with little trust in policy promoters and concerned about the impact of the policy on vulnerable groups.

Another solution, closely related to this can be mentioned. In addition to the concern about the policy's impact on vulnerable groups (IMP), it includes another condition (AFF), i.e., being directly affected by the policy at a personal/family level. AFF appears in both the pathways to the VOICE outcome included in this solution.

SOLUTION 2 – CONDITIONS LEADING TO VOICE

Analysed conditions:

AFF (Directly and severely affected by the policy) * ACT (Active on local issues) * IMP (Concerned for impact on vulnerable groups)

Solution terms in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
AFF*ACT	0.263158	1
ACT*IMP	0.684211	0.866667

Solution coverage: 0.74 (14 of the 19 cases with outcome VOICE are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 0.88 (14 of the 16 cases included in the solution have the outcome VOICE)

This solution suggests that the VOICE outcome can be linked to two largely overlapping solution terms: 1. People who are directly and severely affected by the policy and active on local issues; 2. People active on local issues and concerned about the impact of the policy on vulnerable groups.

Still within the “intense car-free policies” sample, further analysis was conducted to explore **gender differences** in the response to policies that promote sustainable transport at the expense of car use. To this aim, the sub-samples of men and women respondents (17 and 15 respondents respectively) were analysed separately. The analysis led to the identification of different paths frequently leading men and women to the VOICE outcome. It is interesting to note that when looking at the combinations separately for men and women, a sixth factor (ENV/Environmental concern) emerges for the first time as relevant in leading to VOICE results, polarising the results for the two genders.

When analysing women respondents with a VOICE outcome, the following solution is the one with the highest consistency and coverage. It includes two pathways to the VOICE outcome, both involving activism on local issues (ACT) and distrust in policy promoters (DIST).

SOLUTION 3 – CONDITIONS LEADING TO VOICE/WOMEN

Analysed conditions:

ENV (Environmentally aware/active) * AFF (Directly and severely affected by the policy) * ACT (Active on local issues) * DIST (Distrusting policy promoters)

Solution terms in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
DIST*ENV*ACT	0.714286	1
AFF*DIST*ACT	0.285714	1

Solution coverage: 0.86 (6 of the 7 cases with outcome VOICE are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 1 (All cases included in the solution have the outcome VOICE)

This solution suggests that the VOICE outcome can be linked to two partially overlapping solution terms: 1. Women with little trust in policy promoters, who are environmentally involved and active on local issues; 2. Women who are directly and severely affected by the policy, with little trust in policy promoters and active on local issues.

Finally, the solution that more consistently lead to a VOICE outcome for men shows relevant differences compared to that for women, with the absence of environmental involvement and a greater relevance of socio-economic background. Activism on local issues (ACT) is present in both pathways to the VOICE outcome.

SOLUTION 4 – CONDITIONS LEADING TO VOICE/MEN

Analysed conditions:

ENV (Environmentally aware/active) * ACT (Active on local issues) * SEC (Low socio-economic background)

Solution terms in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
~ENV*ACT	0.583333	0.875
SEC*ACT	0.75	0.9

Solution coverage: 0.83 (10 of the 12 cases with outcome VOICE are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 0.91 (10 of the 11 cases included in the solution have the outcome VOICE)

This solution suggests that the VOICE outcome can be linked to two partially overlapping solution terms: 1. Men without environmental involvement but active on local issues; 2. Men with low socio-economic background and active on local issues.

Finally, the one solution that emerges from the analysis of the NEGLECT outcome can be mentioned. The analysis only considered the cases in Italy and Portugal, as the respondents in the case of Norway never had NEGLECT as an outcome. As shown in Table 2, above, the two cases include 23 respondents overall (10 in Italy with three NEGLECT outcomes and 13 in Portugal with 7 NEGLECT outcomes).

The solution links NEGLECT outcomes to severe conditions of social exclusion and associated lack of participation in activism, producing an almost symmetrically different profile to that which leads to VOICE, expressed in a simple and single path to NEGLECT.

SOLUTION 5 – CONDITIONS LEADING TO NEGLECT

Analysed conditions:

SE (Socially excluded) * ACT (Active on local issues)

Solution terms in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Consistency
SE*~ACT	0.78	0.78

Solution coverage: 0.78 (7 of the 9 cases with outcome NEGLECT are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 0.78 (7 of the 9 cases included in the solution have the outcome NEGLECT)

This solution suggests that the NEGLECT outcome can be linked to a single solution term: People facing social exclusion conditions and not active on local issues.

Moderate car-free policies

The analysis of what we defined as moderate car-free policies included the following two cases:

- Dedicated bus lane (Iași, Romania)
- New Bus Rapid System/BRT (Örebro, Sweden).

The two cases considered include 22 respondents, distributed by country, gender and outcome as shown in Table 24 (for a more detailed description of the sample, see the RL8 report).

Table 24. RL8 panel by country, gender* and outcome/Moderate car-free policies.

	Women	Men	Total	OUTCOME: LOY-ALTY
Romania	7	3	10	5
Sweden	7	5	12	7
Total	14	8	22	12

* The sample didn't include nonbinary persons.

The outcome which was primarily analysed was LOYALTY, which is the most frequent reaction in the sample, with 12 occurrences (VOICE and NEGLECT have 5 occurrences each). Several combinations of factors were tested, and a solution emerged as the most relevant for identifying recurrent profiles that responded with LOYALTY to policies supporting bus systems.

The AFF condition (not directly and severely affected by the negative effects of the policy) is present in both pathways to the LOYALTY outcome included in the solution. It is important to stress that this condition (AFF) has a different value in policies that promote public transport than in policies that try to discourage car use, because in the former the negative consequences for non-users are generally less frequent or less intense.

SOLUTION 6 – CONDITIONS LEADING TO LOYALTY

Analysed conditions:

ENV (Environmentally aware/active) * AFF (Directly and severely affected by the policy) * ACT (Active on local issues)

Solution terms in the standard analysis:

	Raw coverage	Raw consistency
~AFF*ACT	0.75	0.818182
~AFF*ENV	0.416667	0.833333

Solution coverage: 0.92 (11 of the 12 cases with outcome LOYALTY are included in the solution)

Solution consistency: 0.85 (11 of the 13 cases included in the solution have the outcome LOYALTY)

This solution suggests that the LOYALTY outcome can be linked to two partially overlapping solution terms: 1. People not directly and severely affected by the policy and active on local issues; 2. People not directly and severely affected by the policy and environmentally involved.

Interpretation

The application of QCA was instrumental in confirming and synthesising the main conclusions of the final RL8 research report, in some cases refining and integrating them. The following list details some of these conclusions, highlighting the contribution of QCA.

The QCA results certainly confirm that **gender matters**. RL8 findings have highlighted that women are more likely to react with LOYALTY to the policies analysed and to display environmental awareness and activism, confirming existing literature on the matter (Zani & Barret 2012; Zhao et al. 2021; Matthies et al. 2002).

- QCA adds that even when women do react with VOICE against intense car-free policies and their impact on vulnerable communities, they tend to do so from a different position that includes activism and environmental involvement (Solution 3), unlike men, where lack of environmental involvement is part of the recurring profile of those who oppose car-free policies (Solution 4).

Another RL8 finding is that **those suffering from very disadvantaged socio-economic conditions tend to have a NEGLECT attitude**. This again confirms existing literature (e.g., Adamson, 2007) and it is probably related to the fact that they do not have the resources, opportunities, interest or time to engage with mobility policies.

- In the QCA analysis, a holistic assessment has been made of each respondent based on the in-depth interview. As a result, we were able to analyse the outcomes of those exposed to severe intersectional vulnerabilities. This has led to the identification of a recurring profile leading to NEGLECT, confirming that severe social exclusion and lack of involvement in local issues are at the root of this attitude (Solution 5).

The distinction between the attitudes of the **vulnerable** but still included individuals and groups on the one hand, and the attitudes of the **severely disadvantaged**, intersectionally socially excluded groups on the other, is one of the basic tenets of the theoretical approach of ACTING (Poortinga & Darnton 2016; Ranci 2009). In RL8, it clearly emerges that it is the former group that is more vocal and active in protesting and, in many cases, stopping policies.

- It is no coincidence that in the recurrent profile of men with VOICE, the condition of being vulnerable but not coming from a very disadvantaged social background was found (Combination 4), whereas, as mentioned above, social exclusion appears in the combination of those who react with NEGLECT (Solution 5).

Another point concerns **the double-sided role of activism**. In the RL8 research report, it was documented how activism and networks make a big difference in determining who is going to actively mobilise against car-free policies. Indeed, looking at the dynamics around VOICE, it was easy to see how an activist orientation and the presence of networks are important precursors to VOICE.

- However, through the QCA analysis, it was found that both the profile leading to VOICE (Solutions 1 and 2) and that leading to LOYALTY (Solution 6) have activism as a condition, reinforcing the recommendation in the conclusion of the RL8 report to look for activist groups that can address the environmental/social tension and build bridges between the two polarities.

The RL-level report also highlighted that **policymakers** seem to be particularly worried about involving citizens when it comes to car-free policies. The interviews with policymakers revealed an intention (in some cases explicit) not to adopt a participatory approach, which would make the timing and outcomes of the policy uncertain and, in some cases, risk blocking the policy altogether.

- The results of QCA confirm that these concerns are reciprocated by citizens, who also have little trust in politicians. In fact, distrust is one of the most recurring factors in the combinations that lead to VOICE outcomes (Solutions 1 and 3).

A final reflection can be made about the relevance of citizen's **environmental involvement** as a predictor of acceptance of sustainable mobility policies.

- The QCA analysis confirms that this attitude is not sufficient to guide responses when intensive car-free policies are concerned. In fact, those with a VOICE outcome are equally divided between those with higher and lower environmental involvement scores. Consequently, this factor does not appear in general QCA combinations (Solutions 1 and 2), i.e., there is no combination where a VOICE outcome is related to lower environmental involvement. Environmental involvement only emerges when LOYALTY outcomes are concerned (Solution 6), but limited to less intensive car-free policies, where effects on car use are weaker.

Limitations

The main limitation of applying QCA to the RL8 cases is the diversity of the policies included in the study. As the analysis progressed, it became increasingly clear that no significant result could be obtained from the policies considered together, as their rationale and the nature of their effects on the daily lives of citizens were too different and therefore difficult to compare.

It was therefore decided to split and duplicate the work, analysing separately the policies that severely restricted car use and those that encouraged alternative transport models (push and pull measures to influence travel behaviour, Steg & Vlek 1997). This led to more consistent results, although it reduced the empirical base of each sub-group and limited the possibility of carrying out more complex analyses.

Another limitation relates to the difficulty of including in the sample people exposed to severe intersectional social exclusion factors, who in many cases were not even aware of the policies analysed, which illustrates one of the conclusions of the analysis but made it difficult to obtain in-depth comparable data. This meant that the QCA analysis, particularly for the neglect outcome, remained at a very general level.

3 Cross-cutting insights

This section highlights some overarching findings from all the QCA analyses presented in this report. While the research questions and results from each RL are highly specific, as are the conditions identified to interpret them, they all align with the broader ACCTING research objectives and theoretical framework. This common foundation allows us to draw connections between their findings, at least at a general level.

In the following sections, we will first explain how we created an integrated basis for the cross-cutting analysis (section 8.1). We will then present the conditions more frequently associated with outcomes across the RLs (Section 8.2). Finally, we will show the network of relationships among these conditions (Section 8.3).

3.1 Creating the basis for the cross-cutting analysis

In the analysis of the seven RLs that underwent QCA, 112 conditions overall were identified and tested for their relationship to the outcome. Of these, 48 appeared in the different combinations leading to positive outcomes. Although the conditions were generally formulated to relate specifically to the research questions, there is considerable overlap among them across the different lines. We therefore worked to reduce the number of conditions and to standardise their wording, so that they could be applied across research lines wherever possible.

It is important to emphasise that the QCA analyses were conducted on different outcomes, each pointing to various forms of change in relation to environmental sustainability objectives. In some cases (RLs 3, 4, 7, and 8), the outcome was attributed to individuals exposed to environmental initiatives or policies. In other cases (RLs 1, 2, and 5), the outcome was attributed to environmental initiatives or policies directly. This distinction leads to some differences in the wording of the conditions but has not precluded unification when the conditions consistently pointed in the same direction, even if applied to different types of actors.

This work reduced the number from 48 to 21 conditions, some of which resulted from the merging of similar conditions. For example, conditions such as VAL_ENV (Values related to the environment/love for nature, from RL2) and ENV (Environmental awareness, from RL8) have been grouped together. More significantly, different conditions related to gender+ vulnerability have been combined. This includes conditions concerning individual participants exposed to gender+ vulnerability factors, as well as conditions related to initiatives or policies involving them. Still another example concerns networks, where different types of networks (e.g., social or economic networks) have been considered together in a single condition.

3.2 Conditions associated with outcomes across RLs

The 21 conditions resulting from the merging process are ranked by frequency in Table 25, along with their definitions. These conditions were identified in the different QCA analyses as being associated with at least one of the positive outcomes of inclusive behavioural change. Some conditions relate solely to individuals, others to initiatives, while some are merged, as indicated in the table.

Table 25. Conditions entering combinations leading to outcomes, across the Research Lines, by frequency.

CODE	CONDITION	FREQ.
GENDERPLUS	Participants exposed to gender+ conditions/inclusion of people exposed to gender+ conditions	10
ENV-ORIENT	Individual or collective/institutional environmental attitudes and values	9
ACTIVISM	Engagement in activist initiatives or movements, both before and within the initiative	8
COHESION	Context characterised by social cohesion, sense of belonging and community, both before and within the initiative	6
KNOWLEDGE	Local or traditional knowledge from participants shared or considered within the initiative	6
PARTICIP	Active participation in the initiative/Channels available for active participation in the initiative	4
SAFETY	Safety or security concerns addressed/initiatives addressing safety or security concerns	4
TRUST-LEAD	Trust in decision makers or the leaders of the initiative	4
BOTTOM-UP	Adoption of bottom-up approaches	3
CAP-BUILDING	Participating in capacity building/Provision of capacity building within the initiative	3
ENV-BEHAV	Personal behaviours aligned with environmental values	3
RURAL	Rural context of the initiatives	3
SOCIAL-SUPPORT	Social support from the community, family and friends	3
NETWORK	Inclusion in networks of different kinds	2
PARTNERSHIP	Partnership among different organisations and bodies, also across the public/private divide	2
RESOURCES	Access to economic resources	2
SOCIAL-MOTIV	Social motivations for change (e.g., solidarity, inclusion)	2
ECON-MOTIV	Economic motivation for change (e.g., energy saving)	1
PRACT-MOTIV	Practical reasons for change (e.g., mobility needs)	1
LOC-AUTHORITY LEVEL	The authority involved is local	1
TIMEFRAME	Relatively long timeframe of the initiative	1

The list presented in the table showcases a wide range of features related to positive outcomes and represents a first contribution of the QCA analysis to the overall ACCTING results. The list includes conditions situated at different levels, such as personal attitudes (e.g., ENV_ORIENT), agency (e.g., ACTIVISM), as well as social (e.g., COHESION) and geographical contexts (e.g., RURAL), approaches of the initiatives (e.g., BOTTOM-UP) or other factors affecting them (e.g., TIMEFRAME), reflecting the varied combinations which have emerged from QCA.

3.3 Networks of relations

It is necessary to look beyond individual factors, as the distinctive strength of QCA lies in its ability to identify complex pathways to change. These pathways consist of a combination of factors of different types which, when considered together, suggest a 'recipe' that increases the likelihood of achieving the desired outcome (the 'solutions' presented in RL-specific sections).

The pathways identified for the various research lines are highly specific and not easily lend themselves to generalisation. Nevertheless, to explore whether any combinations of conditions might have broader relevance beyond individual research lines, the 25 solutions derived from all RL-level analyses were checked for recurring patterns of associated conditions. For this purpose, the renamed and merged conditions presented in Table 24 were used instead of the original ones. This allowed for a consistent comparison. We identified 19 binary associations of conditions that recur across the different solutions from both within and across the research lines. These pairs are presented in Table 26.

Table 26. Binary associations of conditions within and across RLs, by frequency.

No.	CODE	FREQ.
1	'ACTIVISM', 'GENDERPLUS'	4
2	'CAP-BUILDING', 'COHESION'	3
3	'ENV-ORIENT', 'TRUST-LEAD'	3
4	'ACTIVISM', 'SAFETY'	3
5	'ACTIVISM', 'ENV-ORIENT'	3
6	'COHESION', 'ENV-ORIENT'	2
7	'ENV-ORIENT', 'PARTICIP'	2
8	'ENV-BEHAV', 'ENV-ORIENT'	2
9	'RESOURCES', 'SOCIAL-SUPPORT'	2
10	'KNOWLEDGE', 'SOCIAL-SUPPORT'	2
11	'GENDERPLUS', 'KNOWLEDGE'	2
12	'ACTIVISM', 'TRUST-LEAD'	2
13	'ACTIVISM', 'COHESION'	2
14	'COHESION', 'TRUST-LEAD'	2
15	'COHESION', 'SAFETY'	2
16	'ENV-ORIENT', 'SAFETY'	2

17	'BOTTOM-UP', 'RURAL'	2
18	'GENDERPLUS', 'RURAL'	2
19	'COHESION', 'KNOWLEDGE'	2

When we visualise the relationships among the conditions in a network graph (Figure 98), not only do the more frequent combinations from Table 25 take a central position, but the complexity and richness of the interrelations among all conditions become clearly visible. In the graph, factors linked only once, and therefore within a single research line, are shown in grey. Co-occurrences of factors appearing in at least two solutions are shown in green and may correspond to associations found within one or, more frequently, two different research lines. Co-occurrences found three times, across at least two different research lines, are shown in blue. Finally, the co-occurrence of “GENDERPLUS” and “ACTIVISM”, which was found four times across three different RLs, is shown in thick black.

Figure 98. Network of relationships among conditions.

This graph is intended for illustrative purposes only, and it is important to emphasise that it does not represent an attempt at a comprehensive QCA encompassing the different research lines, which would have been impossible to carry out. It is also subject to limitations arising from the merging of conditions, which resulted in a degree of generalisation and

approximation that affects the overall accuracy of the representation. It just provides an impression of the conditions (the nodes in the graph) that are more interlinked with others in the effort for inclusive sustainable change.

The heavier nodes in terms of relations are “ENV_ORIENT” (21), “GENDERPLUS” (20), “ACTIVISM” (17), “COHESION” (16) and “KNOWLEDGE” (12). These reflect the core elements of what can be considered the ACCTING theory of change. This places particular emphasis on the barriers to change, and the negative consequences experienced by people facing gender+/intersectional vulnerabilities. At the same time, it draws on their attitudes and agency, centres their expertise and knowledge, and underscores the importance of community building and the social dimensions of change.

4 Conclusions

The main contribution of the QCA analysis to the ACCTING research has been its role in verifying and, in many cases, **validating key findings** that emerged from the comprehensive analyses carried out within the different research lines. QCA also proved useful in **summarising** some of these findings into a few concise 'solutions' that illustrate the main factors and their interrelations, which led to change within specific domains.

Although QCA is instrumental in guiding reflection on the main conditions of change – in this case towards inclusive environmental transitions – it also strives to go beyond this and offer **a more nuanced picture**. It does so by considering how and under which circumstances these conditions can actually lead to change, whether they are contextual, organisational, motivational, or of another nature.

In this framework, we have on the one hand, information on **a wide range of conditions** associated with inclusive environmental transitions. Recognising and focusing on the factors with the greatest potential, in fact, increases the likelihood of triggering transformative change. For instance, the importance of local and traditional knowledge clearly emerges, an element often overlooked that challenges top-down approaches.

On the other hand, considering **combinations of conditions** serves as a caution against pursuing standardised solutions, regardless of their validity. It demonstrates that the same approach may work effectively in certain contexts, such as rural areas or neighbourhoods with strong social cohesion, but may fail elsewhere. It also reveals that a condition may only lead to change when accompanied by specific others. For instance, going back to the previous example, the active inclusion of disadvantaged groups may not succeed if their knowledge and expertise are not recognised and validated.

Among the most noteworthy findings in this respect is the recurring **connection between the inclusion of gender+/intersectional perspectives and activism**, a condition that highlights the agency of vulnerable and disadvantaged groups. The call to consistently consider more complex configurations of factors and to avoid mono-dimensional solutions, even if demanding, therefore represents a practical and well-supported recommendation emerging from this exercise.

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Part III: Implications for policy and practice

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The intersectional analysis and the QCA illustrate that *effective sustainability interventions must address the presence of enabling factors, as well as the balance between them and the barriers that undermine them*. Knowledge campaigns or skill training will be limited in effectiveness if they are not accompanied by measures to reduce financial and time-related constraints. Similarly, investments in infrastructure must be accompanied by inclusive design to prevent them from reinforcing existing inequalities. The QCA also highlights the great level of agency of vulnerable and disadvantaged groups, and hence the value and potential in making both planning and implementation processes of policies and environmental/climate initiatives inclusive from a gender+ intersectional perspective.

This insight ties in with the observed importance of social valuation and appreciation for environmentally sustainable behaviours: if social support and appreciation are absent, few measures will be able to unfold their full potential. More inclusive social infrastructures and the inclusion of all groups of society in designing and realising environmental and climate measures can be central components helping ensure this. Additionally, it will safeguard diverse values and identities are affirmed and promoted.

The overall findings underscore the need for systemic, equity-driven approaches to sustainability. Building on these interdependences, the ACCTING project makes the following specific recommendations for designing and achieving a socially just and inclusive European Green Deal:

1. Make resources accessible, usable, and redistributive

- **Ensure sustainability education and information are inclusive, practical, and life-stage appropriate.** Education must be delivered in formal institutions but also beyond that. Community-based, informal, and experiential learning channels are ideal complements to formal education programmes in schools. They can help ensure sustainability education is accessible, practical, and culturally relevant. Practical, hands-on knowledge, especially when shared peer-to-peer or through trusted local actors, often enables action more effectively than abstract content.
- **Strengthen self-efficacy through targeted empowerment strategies.** Confidence in one's ability to act was repeatedly cited as a key enabler, particularly among groups with histories of exclusion. Policies need to support skill-building, mentoring, and visibility of success stories from diverse backgrounds. When individuals see people like themselves leading sustainable lives, it can disrupt narratives of inaccessibility and promote broader uptake.
- **Recognise and accommodate gendered and life-stage-specific time poverty.** Time constraints are repeatedly cited as barriers by people in paid employment, caregivers (disproportionately women), and younger adults balancing multiple responsibilities. A holistic understanding of sustainability should respect time constraints, and make them less pertinent, by offering flexible participation models, minimising bureaucratic burdens, and aligning with daily routines. Without this, programs risk excluding precisely those they aim to reach.
- **Target financial support toward those facing persistent affordability barriers.** Many vulnerable groups, particularly those with disability-, migration-, or minority-based vulnerabilities, report that financial constraints consistently limit their ability to adopt environmentally sustainable behaviours, even when motivation and

knowledge are present. Subsidies, grants, and cost-reduction programs should be tailored to these groups, especially for up-front investments like insulation, green appliances, food gardens, or transport options.

- **Design cross-sectoral interventions that integrate knowledge-building, access, affordability, and participation.** Many face intersections of different vulnerability and inequality factors, and multiple, overlapping constraints. Policies should therefore bundle educational efforts with structural investments and financial support, ensuring people understand sustainable options but also have the means and opportunity to act on them. For example, providing urban gardens without access to seeds, educational courses, or social networks where people can exchange time and knowledge, will leave many excluded. Likewise, interventions must align across sectors – mobility, education, housing, community development, so that no single gap undermines broader sustainability efforts.

2. Build supportive and affirming social dynamics

- **Support inclusive community-based sustainability initiatives.** Peer-led and community-rooted projects often function as accessible platforms for engagement, particularly when institutional pathways are blocked or mistrusted. Funding and supporting local initiatives, especially those led by women, minorities, and other marginalised groups, can foster a sense of ownership and make participation more accessible. Community initiatives, including faith communities, also tend to be more adaptive and responsive to individual needs, and more resilient over time.
- **Foster safe and welcoming environments within sustainability spaces.** Many individuals with religion-, ethnicity-, or sexual orientation-based vulnerabilities reported lack of social appreciation and exclusion from community networks. Programs should visibly affirm diversity through inclusive messaging, anti-discrimination policies, dedicated spaces for underrepresented groups, and initiatives that break social silos and bring together different groups. Training for organisers and public-facing staff on inclusion and cultural sensitivity is essential to prevent the reproduction of exclusion in green spaces.
- **Improve the recognition and visibility of diverse sustainability efforts.** Environmentally sustainable behaviours often go unacknowledged, particularly in communities where they are not the norm or where actors fall outside the dominant cultural narratives. Public campaigns, storytelling, and awards need to explicitly include and celebrate contributions from all communities, not just as greenwashing but in honest. Visibility counters social discouragement and affirms that everyone's efforts matter, not just those aligned with mainstream models.
- **Integrate ethical and justice-based framings into sustainability messaging.** Environmental policies often focus narrowly on efficiency or individual responsibility, missing broader ethical motivations. Many vulnerable groups are strongly driven by values of justice, care, and collective responsibility. Messaging that reflects these values, rather than technocratic goals, can mobilise deeper engagement and align with culturally meaningful frameworks, particularly in faith-based and solidarity-driven communities. Additionally, this can contribute to shifting what is valued and appreciated in society.

3. Address structural inequalities and regional disparities

- **Invest in inclusive, place-based infrastructure that addresses regional and demographic disparities.** Sustainability infrastructure, including public transport, cycling lanes, green spaces, and energy-efficient housing, must be designed using universal access principles. People in rural areas, disabled individuals, and low-income groups often report poor or inaccessible infrastructure as a major barrier. Investments should prioritise underserved regions and communities with overlapping vulnerabilities to ensure real access to sustainable options, not just formal availability.
- **Prioritise spatial and socio-economic equity in sustainability investments.** Deprived areas and neighbourhoods with high concentrations of marginalised populations, such as national minorities, low-income households, or racialised communities, often lack the structural capacity to support sustainable behaviour. These areas should be explicitly targeted for green infrastructure improvements, such as retrofitting buildings, improving public transport, expanding access to green spaces, and delivering sustainable public services. Without spatially targeted investment, sustainability transitions risk reinforcing existing inequalities.
- **Use place-based approaches that reflect physical, economic, and social realities of different localities.** Assuming uniform starting points across regions or populations leads to ineffective or exclusionary policies. Rural areas, urban peripheries, and historically underserved communities often face very different constraints and opportunities. Policies should be grounded in the lived realities of place, taking into account distances to services, prevailing employment patterns, demographic profiles, and cultural norms, so that the processes and outcomes are feasible, fair, and relevant on the ground.
- **Adapt sustainability planning to the physical, economic, and social realities of different local contexts.** Uniform policies applied across regions fail to account for the divergent capacities of individuals and communities to adopt sustainable behaviours. For instance, urban residents may benefit from walkable neighbourhoods and accessible services, while rural residents face long distances and poor mobility networks. Policy frameworks must enable local governments to tailor interventions to context-specific constraints and opportunities.

4. Reconfigure governance and participation for equity

- **Tailor policies to account for cumulative and intersecting vulnerabilities.** Many respondents experience more than one form of exclusion, e.g., being both disabled and from a minority background, which leads to layered barriers. Interventions must not assume a single-issue profile but offer flexible, tailored support that reflects intersecting forms of disadvantage. This may involve joint programming between sectors, targeted outreach, or integrated service models.
- **Conduct systematic impact assessments focused on equity and lived outcomes.** Policies should be evaluated not only for overall effectiveness, but also for their differential impacts across gender, disability, ethnicity, and other axes of inequality. Moreover, equity assessments must look beyond formal access to identify where structural disadvantages persist in practice.

- **Actively involve marginalised communities in designing and governing sustainability policies.** Respondents consistently cited lack of access to political and societal actors as both a hindrance and a missed opportunity. Participatory processes must go beyond consultation and enable co-creation through citizen assemblies, community advisory boards, and direct representation in decision-making bodies. This ensures that policies are relevant, trusted, and rooted in lived experience.
- **Rebuild trust in public institutions through transparency and responsiveness.** A recurring theme is that trust in institutions, and willingness to engage, is shaped by whether communities feel heard and respected. Transparent decision-making, follow-up on commitments, and visible responsiveness to community input are not peripheral to sustainability, but core enablers. Without them, participation erodes, and scepticism grows, particularly among already-marginalised groups. Living up to the promises and visions developed in the European Green Deal, and truly considering what is needed from an ecological as well as from a social justice perspective, can be a central means to restore and rebuild this trust and societal commitment.

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Appendix

This appendix is intended to provide some background information on the QCA methodology in general and its application to seven research lines of ACCTING project. In particular, the appendix consists of the following three parts:

1. The calibration of the outcome and conditions
2. The construction of Truth tables
3. Some concepts for the evaluation of causal configurations

Calibration of conditions

In Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA), calibration refers to the process of transforming raw data or variables into a standardised format that can be used for analysis. This typically involves converting qualitative data (such as categorical or ordinal data) or continuous variables into set membership scores, usually ranging from 0 to 1, representing the degree to which a case belongs to a certain condition or outcome. Calibration ensures that the data are comparable across cases and allows for meaningful analysis of causal relationships in the QCA process.

There are two main approaches to calibration in QCA:

1. Crisp set calibration: This approach treats variables as discrete categories. Each case is clearly and unambiguously classified as belonging or not belonging to a particular set. For example, a case can be considered as 'yes' (belongs to the set) or 'no' (does not belong to the set) without ambiguity.
2. Fuzzy Set Calibration: In contrast, fuzzy set calibration allows greater flexibility, as variables can take on values that represent degrees of belonging to a set. In this case, a case can belong to a set with a certain degree, between 0 and 1.

When the variables are well-defined and do not allow for nuances or when survey measurements are limited, the use of crisp sets prevents arbitrary thresholding. Crisp sets are also preferred in the case of small-N panels. In fact, crisp sets increase robustness in these cases (Ragin 2009). Instead, the fuzzy set approach is useful for capturing the complexity and nuance of social phenomena, where categories are not sharp and can vary in intensity.

The CRISP sets approach was used in the application of QCA to the seven research lines. Below are the tables containing the calibration of the conditions for each research line.

RL1 – Calibration of conditions

CODE	CONDITION
TERR_CONT	1 = Rural or predominantly rural 0 = Urban or periurban
HAZARD	1 = Single hazard factor 0 = Multiple hazard factors
AUTH_CONST	1 = Only one level of public authority involved in the initiative 0 = More than one level of public authority involved in the initiative
WOMEN_LEAD	1 = Women in leading positions in the authority(ies) involved 0 = No women in leading positions in the authority(ies) involved
REL_CSO	1 = Structured relations with Civil Society Organisations 0 = No structured relations with Civil Society Organisations
SOC_PROFES	1 = Structural embedding of social professions in the initiative 0 = No structural embedding of social professions in the initiative
BOTTOM-UP	1 = Bottom-up perspectives in the preparedness approach 0 = No bottom-up perspectives in the preparedness approach
G+_CONSID	1 = Gender+ consideration in civil protection response 0 = No gender+ consideration in civil protection response
G+_INCLUS	1 = Gender+ inclusiveness of community engagement 0 = No gender+ inclusiveness of community engagement

RL2 – Calibration of conditions

CODE	CONDITION
RESIST_ACT	1 = Initiatives actively resisting environmentally detrimental projects 0 = Initiatives not actively resisting environmentally detrimental projects
URGENT	1 = Urgent 0 = Not urgent
ADM_PRO_ENV	1 = Pro-environment administration 0 = Not pro-environment administration
ADM_SUPPORT	1 = Administration supporting the initiative 0 = Administration not supporting the initiative
ADM_OPPOSE	1 = Administration opposing the initiative 0 = Administration not opposing the initiative
PAST_NEGOT	1 = Existence of previous participation/negotiation channels 0 = Absence of previous participation/negotiation channels
TRUST	1 = Citizens' trust in the local administration regarding the initiative 0 = No citizens' trust in the local administration regarding the initiative
COMMUNITY	1 = Strong sense of community 0 = No sense of community
PROM_EXP	1 = Prior activism experience of the promoters 0 = No prior activism experience of the promoters
PROM_LEAD	1 = Strong leadership within the initiative 0 = No strong leadership within the initiative
EXT_SUPPORT	1 = External support of the initiative 0 = No external support of the initiative
PART_INCENT	1 = Incentives for participants to engage in the initiative

CODE	CONDITION
	0 = No incentives for participants to engage in the initiative
PART_FEAR	1 = Fear of consequences for participants to engage in the initiative 0 = No fear of consequences for participants to engage in the initiative
WOMEN	1 = Women's active engagement in the initiative 0 = No women's active engagement in the initiative
INCLUSIVE	1 = Inclusion of gender+/vulnerable groups in the initiative 0 = No inclusion of gender+/vulnerable groups in the initiative
KNOWL	1 = Importance of traditional and local knowledge 0 = No importance of traditional and local knowledge

RL3 – Calibration of conditions

CODE	CONDITION
SEX	1 = Woman 0 = Man
AGE	1 = Old (70+) 0 = Not old (up to 69)
MIGR	1 = Migrant status 0 = Non-migrant status
DSB	1 = Disability affecting mobility 0 = Disability not affecting mobility or not disability status
SEC	1 = Low socio-economic background 0 = No low socio-economic background
MOTIV_ENV	1 = Environmental motivations for joining the initiative 0 = No environmental motivations for joining the initiative
MOTIV_SOC	1 = Social motivations for joining the initiative 0 = No social motivations for joining the initiative
MOTIV_EC	1 = Economic motivations for joining the initiative 0 = No economic motivations for joining the initiative
MOTIV_EXT	1 = External reason for joining the initiative 0 = No external reason for joining the initiative
SOC_COHES	1 = Perception of social cohesion strengthened by the initiative 0 = No perception of social cohesion strengthened by the initiative
ACT_PART	1 = Intense or medium participation in the initiative 0 = No participation at all in the initiative
CAP_BUIL	1 = Capacity building 0 = No capacity building
TRUST_LEA	1 = Strong trust in the leadership of the initiative 0 = Weak or no trust in the leadership of the initiative
TRUST_PROJ	1 = Strong trust in the project planning and results 0 = Weak or no trust in the project planning and results

RL4 – Calibration of conditions

CODE	CONDITION
SEX	1 = Woman 0 = Man
GENDER	1 = Gender relevant as a vulnerability condition 0 = Gender not relevant as a vulnerability condition
EDU	1 = University degree or more 0 = Secondary school degree or less
MIGR	1 = Migrant status 0 = Non-migrant status
MOT_ENV	1 = Environmental motivation 0 = No environmental motivation
MOT_EC	1 = Economic motivation 0 = No economic motivation
VAL_ENV	1 = Environmental values 0 = No environmental values
VAL_JUST	1 = Related to global justice/equity/inclusion 0 = No values related to global justice/equity/inclusion
BEHAV	1 = Change of behaviour in at least two domains (among mobility, food, energy, recycling) 0 = No change in behaviour or only in one out of the four domains
NET_ENV	1 = Membership in environmental networks 0 = No membership in environmental networks
NET_EC	1 = Membership in an economic network 0 = No membership in an economic network
NET_CULT	1 = Membership in a cultural network 0 = No membership in a cultural network
MODEL_BUS	1 = Propensity to adopt or consider measures from other businesses 0 = No propensity to adopt or consider measures from other businesses
MODEL_NET	1 = Propensity to adopt or consider measures from ESCos*, networks, etc. 0 = No propensity to adopt or consider measures from ESCos*, networks, etc.
INCENT	1 = Propensity to consider existing incentives or subsidies 0 = No propensity to consider existing incentives or subsidies

* Energy Service Companies

RL5 – Calibration of conditions

CODE	CONDITION
GARD	1 = Presence of a garden 0 = Absence of a garden
FOOD	1 = Food distribution 0 = No food distribution
SHELT	1 = Provision of shelter 0 = No provision of shelter
EDU	1 = Provision of educational opportunities 0 = No provision of educational opportunities
SOC	1 = Organisation of social activities 0 = No social activities

CODE	CONDITION
INT	1 = Integrated services (more than 2 types of services provided) 0 = Non-integrated services (max 2 types of services provided)
COMM	1 = Community-building efforts/initiatives 0 = No community-building efforts/initiatives
KNOWL	1 = Food knowledge-integration practices 0 = No food knowledge-integration practices
PARTIC	1 = Beneficiaries regularly collaborating with or structural part of the initiative 0 = Beneficiaries not or only marginally collaborating with in the initiative
PROM_CSO	1 = Civil Society Organisation is the promoter of the initiative 0 = Civil Society Organisation is not the promoter of the initiative
PROM_LA	1 = Local authority is the promoter of the initiative 0 = Local authority is not the promoter of the initiative
PARTN_CSO	1 = Presence of partnerships with Civil Society Organisations 0 = Absence of a partnership with Civil Society Organisations
PARTN_LA	1 = Presence of partnerships with Local authority 0 = Absence of partnerships with Local authority
PARTN_PRIV	1 = Presence of partnerships with private companies 0 = Absence of partnerships with private companies
VOL	1 = The initiative avails itself of volunteers 0 = The initiative does not avail itself of volunteers or only marginally
WOM	1 = Relevant or central role of women in managing the initiative 0 = Limited or no role of women in managing the initiative
GEND_FOC	1 = Central or relevant gender focus in the initiative 0 = Absent or marginal gender focus in the initiative

RL7 – Calibration of conditions

CODE	CONDITION
SEX	1 = Woman 0 = Man
GENDER	1 = Gender relevant as a vulnerability condition 0 = Gender not relevant as a vulnerability condition
AGE	1 = Old (65+) 0 = Not old (up to 64)
MIGR	1 = Migrant status 0 = Non-migrant status
DSB	1 = Disability (both severe disability and less severe but with an impact on mobility) 0 = No disability
SEC	1 = Low socio-economic background 0 = No low socio-economic background
EXC	1 = Person affected by intense and/or overlapped social exclusion factors 0 = Person not affected by intense and/or overlapped social exclusion factors
CARE	1 = Care responsibilities 0 = No care responsibilities
DIFF	1 = Cycling is perceived to be widespread in the area 0 = Cycling is not perceived to be widespread in the area

CODE	CONDITION
SAT_TRA	1 = Satisfaction with transport arrangements before the initiative 0 = No satisfaction with transport arrangements before the initiative
TRA_WALK	1 = Walking main means of transport before the initiative 0 = Walking not main means of transport before the initiative
TRA_PT	1 = Public transport main means of transport before the initiative 0 = Public transport not main means of transport before the initiative
TRA_CAR	1 = Car main means of transport before the initiative 0 = Car not main means of transport before the initiative
MOTIV_PRACT	1 = Practical motivations for cycling 0 = No practical motivations for cycling
MOTIV_SUST	1 = Environmental motivations for cycling 0 = No environmental motivations for cycling
MOTIV_HEA	1 = Health-related motivations for cycling 0 = No health-related motivations for cycling
MOTIV_SOC	1 = Social motivations for cycling 0 = No social motivations for cycling
HESIT	1 = Hesitation to take part in the initiative 0 = No hesitation to take part in the initiative
SAT_INI	1 = High overall satisfaction 0 = Low or medium overall satisfaction
INCL_INI	1 = Perceived inclusive atmosphere 0 = No perceived inclusive atmosphere
SUPP	1 = Support from family and friends 0 = No support from family and friends
PRE_ACC	1 = Access to a suitable bike before the initiative 0 = No access to a suitable bike before the initiative
POST_ACC	1 = Access to a suitable bike after the initiative 0 = No access to a suitable bike after the initiative
PRE_COMP	1 = Able to cycle before the initiative 0 = Not able to cycle before the initiative
POST_COMP	1 = Able to cycle in the traffic after the initiative 0 = Not able to cycle in the traffic after the initiative

RL8 – Calibration of conditions

CODE	CONDITION
SEX	1 = Women 0 = Men
GEN	1 = Gender relevant as vulnerability condition 0 = Gender not relevant as vulnerability condition
AGE	1 = Old (65+) 0 = Not old (up to 64)
DSB	1 = Disability (both severe disability and less severe but with an impact on mobility) 0 = No disability
MIGR	1 = Migrant status 0 = Non-migrant status

CODE	CONDITION
SEC	1 = Low socio-economic background 0 = No low socio-economic background
EXC	1 = Person affected by intense and/or overlapped (intersectional) social exclusion factors 0 = Person vulnerable but not affected by intense or overlapped social exclusion factors
ENV	1 = Environmental awareness/activism 0 = No or little environmental awareness/activism
ACT	1 = Activism on local issues 0 = No activism on local issues
IMP	1 = Concerned for the impact of the policy on vulnerable groups 0 = No concern for the impact of the policy on vulnerable groups
AFF	1 = Directly and severely affected by the policy 0 = Not directly and severely affected by the policy
TRA	1 = Car or motorcycle 0 = Public transport, biking or walking
DIST	1 = Distrust in the policy promoters 0 = No distrust in the policy promoters
PRO	1 = Reported inclusion in the policy process 0 = No reported inclusion/only superficial inclusion

Truth table construction

Truth tables were built in ACCTING using the software fsQCA.

For each solution in each RL, a “Full truth table” was built. Full truth tables contain all possible combinations of the selected conditions, regardless of whether they were found in the reference panel or not.

The example below, taken from RL4, shows the 8 possible combinations of the 3 conditions used, i.e.: VAL_ENV (Environmental values) * BEHAV (Personal change towards sustainability) * MOD_NET (Propensity to adopt or consider measures from ESCos, networks, etc.).

A full truth table

VAL_ENV	BEHAV	MOD_NET	Number	Raw consistency
1	1	1	7	1
0	1	0	6	0.33333
1	1	0	3	1
0	0	0	2	0
1	0	0	2	0.5
0	1	1	1	1
0	1	0	0	
0	1	1	0	

This table contains three main types of information:

- All possible theoretical combinations between the different conditions (e.g., in the first row, the first three columns present a combination with a presence of all the conditions: VAL_ENV; BEHAV; MOD_NET)
- The total number of cases in the panel considered that present that specific combination (e.g., in the first row, fifth column = 7 cases)
- The consistency of each row, i.e., the ratio between the number of cases presenting the outcome and the total number of cases with the considered combination (e.g., in the first row, last column, the consistency is = 1 as all of the seven cases considered present the outcome).

Once the full truth table was built, the relevance thresholds of the existing combinations were defined, i.e. the thresholds related to the consistency of each row (at least 0.75) and the minimum number of cases per combination (just one case, as this is a small-N panel). This second step is functional to eliminate unobserved combinations among the real cases of the panel (the last two rows of combinations in the table above) and to order the observed combinations according to the consistency threshold (3 configurations with a consistency threshold = 1 and 3 configurations with a lower threshold).

From this first table, the “Final truth table” was built, which is needed to start the analysis. This table shows the different combinations of conditions recorded in the panel. For each combination, the number of occurrences (Number), its consistency with the outcome¹⁴ (Raw consistency) and, consequently, its membership or non-membership of the outcome are given (Outcome).

¹⁴ The raw consistency is given by the ratio of cases with a positive outcome to the total number of cases with that combination.

A final truth table

VAL_ENV	MOT_ENV	BEHAV	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	0	1	5	1	1
1	1	1	4	1	1
1	1	0	2	1	1
0	0	1	7	0	0.428571
0	0	0	2	0	0
1	0	0	1	0	0

In the following sections, all final truth tables used in the main text of this report are presented for each research line.

Research Line 1 - Valorising local knowledge in the frame of the community-based disasters' management and mitigating exposure

Final truth table for the Solution 1 in RL1 – “Inclusive, bottom-up initiatives in rural areas”

TERR_CONT	REL_CSO	BOTTOM-UP	G+_CONSID	G+_INCLUS	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1
0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0
0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 2 in RL1 – leading to Non-outcome “Top-down initiatives in urban context”

TERR_CONT	SOC_PROFES	BOTTOM-UP	Number	~OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	0	0	4	1	1
0	0	0	2	1	1
0	1	0	1	1	1
1	1	1	2	0	0
1	0	1	1	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 3 in RL1 – “Simple and inclusive initiatives in rural areas”

TERR_CONT	AUTH_CONST	G+_INCLUS	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	0	0	1	1	1
1	1	1	1	1	1
1	0	1	5	1	0.8
0	1	0	2	0	0.5
0	0	1	1	0	0

Research Line 2 - Biodiversity and land use restrictions

Final truth table for the Solution 1 in RL2 – “key role of supportive contexts and activist experience”

ADM_PRO_ENV	PROM_EXP	PROM_LEAD	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	1	1	3	1	1
0	1	1	2	1	1
1	1	0	1	1	1
0	0	1	3	0	0
0	1	0	1	0	0
1	0	1	1	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 2 in RL2 – “Facilitating constructive engagement and negotiation: the role of time and sense of security”

URGENT	PAST_NEGOT	PROM_EXP	PART_FEAR	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
0	1	1	0	4	1	1
0	0	1	0	1	1	1
0	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	0	0	1	2	0	0
1	0	0	0	1	0	0
0	1	0	0	1	0	0
0	0	1	1	1	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 3 in RL2 – “The synergy of local knowledge, WOMEN’S engagement, and activist experience”

KNOWL	WOMEN	PROM_EXP	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	1	1	2	1	1
0	1	1	1	1	1
1	0	1	4	1	0.75
1	1	0	2	0	0
0	0	0	1	0	0
1	0	0	1	0	0

Research Line 3 - Energy communities, energy poverty and community energy schemes

Final truth table for the Solution 1 in RL3 – “Motivation and active participation, supported by the initiative”

MOTIV_ENV	ACT_PART	CAP_BUIL	SOC_CO-HES	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	1	1	1	6	1	1
1	1	1	0	2	1	1
1	1	0	1	2	1	1
1	1	0	0	3	0	0.666667
0	0	0	0	3	0	0
0	1	0	1	2	0	0
0	1	0	0	1	0	0
0	1	1	1	1	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 2 in RL3 – “Motivation and active participation, supported by the initiative”

MOTIV_ENV	ACT_PART	TRUST_LEA	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	1	1	13	1	0.923077
0	1	1	4	0	0
0	0	0	2	0	0
0	0	1	1	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 3 in RL3 – leading to Non-outcome “Economic motivations alone are not enough”

MOTIV_ENV	MOTIV_SOC	MOTIV_EC	Number	~OUTCOME	raw consist.
0	0	1	7	1	1
1	0	1	5	0	0.2
1	1	0	3	0	0
1	1	1	3	0	0
1	0	0	2	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 4 in RL3 – leading to Non-outcome “Building capacity is essential for poorer people to be able to change”

SEC	MOTIV_EXT	CAP_BUIL	Number	~OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	1	0	7	1	0.857143
1	0	0	4	0	0.25
0	0	1	5	0	0.2
1	0	1	4	0	0

Research Line 4 - Intensifying the adoption of energy-efficiency and pro-environmental measures in micro/small SMEs

Final truth table for the Solution 1 in RL4 – “Consistent attitudes and behaviours”

VAL_ENV	MOT_ENV	BEHAV	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	0	1	5	1	1
1	1	1	4	1	1
1	1	0	2	1	1
0	0	1	7	0	0.428571
0	0	0	2	0	0
1	0	0	1	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 2 in RL4 – “Models from networks and associations”

VAL_ENV	BEHAV	MOD_NET	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	1	1	6	1	1
1	1	0	3	1	1
1	0	1	1	1	1
0	1	1	1	1	1
1	0	0	2	0	0.5
0	1	0	6	0	0.333333
0	0	0	2	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 3 in RL4 – “Models from other businesses”

VAL_ENV	BEHAV	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	1	8	1	0.875
0	0	7	1	0.714286
1	0	5	0	0.4
0	1	1	0	0

Research Line 5 - Improving food security and healthy diets in vulnerable communities

Final truth table for the Solution 1 in RL5 – “Integrating knowledge, building communities”

COMM	KNOWL	EDU	SOC	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	1	1	1	5	1	1
0	0	0	0	3	0	0
0	0	0	1	1	0	0
1	0	1	1	1	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 2 in RL5 – leading to Non-outcome “Providing ‘only’ food”

FOOD	PARTN_PRIV	KNOWL	Number	~OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	1	0	5	1	1
0	0	1	5	0	0

Research Line 7 - Cycling initiatives for an inclusive mobility transition

Final truth table for the Solution 1 in RL7 – “The importance of not starting from scratch”

PRE_ACC	PRE_COMP	SUPP	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	1	1	7	1	1
1	1	0	6	1	1
0	1	1	4	1	1
0	0	0	5	0	0.4
0	0	1	11	0	0.181818
1	0	1	3	0	0
0	1	0	1	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 2 in RL7 – “Cycling for practical reasons”

PRE_COMP	MOTIV_PRACT	SUPP	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	1	1	9	1	1
1	0	1	2	1	1
1	1	0	7	1	0.857143
0	1	0	5	0	0.4
0	1	1	9	0	0.222222
0	0	1	5	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 3 in RL7 – “The support and resources needed for change”

PRE_COMP	POST_ACC	SUPP	SAT_TRA	SEC	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	1	1	0	0	4	1	1
1	1	1	1	1	4	1	1
1	1	0	0	0	3	1	1
1	1	1	0	1	3	1	1
0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
1	1	0	0	1	4	1	0.75
0	1	1	1	0	3	0	0.333333
0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0
0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 4 in RL7 – leading to Non-outcome
“Migrant background and previous cycling competence”

MIRG	PRE_COMP	Number	~OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	0	6	1	0.833333
1	1	4	0	0.25
0	1	14	0	0
0	0	1	0	0

Research Line 8 - Reception of car-free policies by intersectional vulnerable groups

Final truth table for the Solution 1 in RL8 – “Condition leading to Voice”

EXC	ACT	DIST	IMP	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
0	1	1	1	8	1	1
1	1	1	1	3	1	1
1	1	1	0	2	1	1
0	1	1	0	1	1	1
0	0	1	1	1	1	1
0	1	0	1	4	0	0.5
1	1	0	0	2	0	0.5
1	0	0	1	4	0	0.25
1	0	0	0	4	0	0
1	0	1	0	2	0	0
0	1	0	0	1	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 2 in RL8 – “Condition leading to Voice”

AFF	ACT	IMP	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	1	1	4	1	1
1	1	0	1	1	1
0	1	1	11	1	0.818182
0	1	0	5	0	0.6
1	0	1	2	0	0.5
0	0	1	3	0	0.333333
0	0	0	5	0	0
1	0	0	1	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 3 in RL8 – “Condition leading to Voice/Women”

ENV	AFF	ACT	DIST	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	0	1	1	4	1	1
0	1	0	0	1	1	1
0	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	1	1	1	1	1	1
0	0	0	0	3	0	0
1	0	0	0	1	0	0
0	0	1	0	1	0	0
1	0	1	0	1	0	0
1	0	0	1	1	0	0
1	1	0	1	1	0	0

Final truth table for the Solution 4 in RL8 – “Condition leading to Voice/Men”

SEC	ENV	ACT	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	1	1	3	1	1
0	0	1	1	1	1
1	0	1	7	1	0.857143
0	1	1	2	0	0.5
1	0	0	3	0	0.3333330
0	0	0	1	0	

Final truth table for the Solution 5 in RL8 – “Condition leading to Neglect”

SE	ACT	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	0	9	1	0.777778
1	1	6	0	0.166667
0	1	8	0	0.125

Final truth table for the Solution 6 in RL8 – “Condition leading to Loyalty”

ENV	AFF	ACT	Number	OUTCOME	raw consist.
1	0	0	2	1	1
0	0	1	7	1	0.857143
1	0	1	4	1	0.75
0	0	0	8	0	0.125
0	1	0	1	0	0

Some concepts for the evaluation of causal configurations

To facilitate the reading of the causal configurations identified through the QCA (the different “solutions” presented in the main text), some basic concepts used are recalled below.

Solution term(s): The “solution terms” are the individual components (conditions or combinations of conditions) that appear in the final solution used to explain the outcome in QCA. These terms are key to understanding the causal pathways that lead to a given result. There may be one solution term (which will then coincide with the final solution) or several solution terms (which will contribute to the definition of the final solution). Each solution term is presented with its “raw consistency” and “raw coverage”.

Raw consistency: The raw consistency is the ratio of cases with a positive outcome in a specific solution term to the total number of cases in the same solution. For example, if a solution term contains 5 cases, of which 4 have a positive outcome and 1 has a negative outcome, the consistency would be given by the ratio $4/5 = 0.80$.

Raw coverage: The raw coverage of a QCA solution term is the ratio of cases that have a positive outcome in that solution to the total number of cases in the sample that have a positive outcome. For example, if a solution term contains only 7 of the 12 cases with a positive outcome, the coverage is given by the ratio $7/12 = 0.583333$.

Solution consistency: Similarly to the raw consistency, the solution consistency is given by the ratio of the cases with a positive outcome in the final solution to the total number of cases in that solution. The highest solution consistency would be if all cases in the solution had a positive outcome: $X/Y = 1$. Although the appropriate level for consistency is research-specific, consistency ratios of 0.75 and above are generally considered acceptable. It is important to remark that the solution consistency is the result of the combination of the x solution terms obtained from the analysis and not the simple sum of them. In fact, there may be more or less overlap of cases in the different solution terms. Overlapping cases should therefore be considered only once.

Solution coverage: Similarly to the raw coverage, the solution coverage is given by the ratio of the cases with a positive outcome in the final solution to the total number of cases with a positive outcome in the panel. The highest solution coverage would be if all cases with a positive outcome were present in the solution: $X/Y = 1$. A coverage ratio of 0.75 and above are generally considered acceptable. Again, it must be remarked that the solution coverage is the result of the combination of the x solution terms and not the simple sum of them. In fact, there may be more or less overlap of cases in the different solution terms. Overlapping cases must therefore only be considered once.